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**Particularities in the application of practical
knowledge in strategic thinking under the
pressure of crisis**

Doctoral Thesis

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‘Be realistic, always wish the impossible’ Paolo Coelho famously wrote in his book *The Alchemist*. This quote has inspired me ever since I read the book. The impossible has become possible, and due in no small measure to a number of very important people:

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ABSTRACT

Strategic thinking has been described across a multidisciplinary literature as an individual's ability to employ their analytical skills upon their knowledge in order to achieve their goals. However, both the knowledge bases an individual may claim, as well as the cognitive processes upon which they've refined their analytical skills have been influenced by the experiences they have been exposed to. As a disruptive momentum, a crisis context produces a loss of relevance for the knowledge they've based their deductions on and has a direct impact on their ability to foresee eventual implications within decision making. The present thesis explores how leaders use their life experiences as a basis for strategic thinking within a moment of crisis. Data has been collected through a multimethod research design combining storytelling interviews with field notes. While the narrative inquire method was used extracting insights related to a person's path, field notes allowed tracking the crisis in its unfolding. Findings illustrate strategic thinking as a dynamic development continuously evolving through systematic opportunity and risk assessment. Decision making is more likely to be grounded in reflection and risk assessment, rather than emerging spontaneously. The task of identifying internal resources signals group cohesion as an adjacent goal to safeguard, since unforeseen circumstances can also include conflict amongst peers. The research aligns to previous studies demonstrating creativity as the capacity to form coherent configurations out of available knowledge, demystifying preconceptions related to intuition or less explainable skills and circumstances. Practical implications include the design of a strategic tool to identify the relevant precedent for each project. The originality of the thesis lies in the use of the cascade sample selection with no intervention over the participants' recruitment process and the transfer of control over the data collection strategy from the researcher to the interviewee.

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CHAPTER 1. INTRODUCTION

1.1 Background of the Research

The concept of strategic thinking represents, according to the literature, one of the main characteristics of leaders (Dragoni, et al., 2014). Strategic thinking skills facilitate critical thinking and enable complex problem solving and future planning (Rhee, 2011). Businesses rely on strategic thinking skills, particularly in their leaders, to reach the business objectives and address the arising challenges, especially in the times of crisis. Strategic thinking in business is also needed to create dialogues and other interactional means among people in furtherance of the present and future direction of the company (Rhee, 2011).

Strategic thinking results in conceptualising solutions to issues and problems, which then translates into strategic planning. In times of global disruption, strategic thinking and resultant planning is even more critical, such as during the pandemic caused by the Covid-19 virus. The global ramifications of a failure of strategic thought and action are difficult to comprehend. It was a crisis few had anticipated or prepared for. But it was and remains a crisis which requires adaptation and change and much strategic thought and planning: there has been, for example, an increase of online learning in schools and universities and much more remote business dealing (OECD, 2021). The study examines some of the new strategies used by leaders at the retailer to facilitate change and cope with new demands, including remote connections and time management (Walker, 2013).

According to the Merriam-Webster Dictionary (2019), a situation of crisis is “an unstable or crucial time or state of affairs in which a decisive change is impending, especially one with the distinct possibility of a highly undesirable outcome”. Crises contain both the vulnerability and the resilience of both individuals, as well as of the organisations (Stern, 2013). (Boin & Hart, 2003) describe crises as dynamic yet also chaotic and disruptive to an organisation. Crises threaten an organisation’s survival, as well as its reputation. There is an urgent need for quick and strategic decision making. It is critical to come to grips with the crisis as soon as possible. Crises can appear at any time, but it can be dealt with if addressed in an appropriate and effective

manner (Fink, 2000). Crises are preventable if leaders deal with them. However, the pandemic was not able to be foreseen (Lagfadec, 1993).

Before the COVID-19 was declared a worldwide emergency by World Health Organisation in February 2020, the FTSE (Financial Times Stock Exchange) registered a fall by 5 points, signalling the market volatility which was likely to be produced by the virus (Kollewe, 2020). Heads of states declared they are going to monitor the evolution of the pandemic while focusing on how their national health systems will respond. However, the business environment was challenged with the uncertainty of how Governments should intervene in the worst-case scenarios (McMahon 2020). Each of the industries featured under the Fast-Moving Consumer Goods spectrum has been subject to distinctive regulations which were revised under the impact of contamination rates and other public health related data. Such parameters varied under the influence of their own characteristics, but under the impact of the supply and distribution markets they connect. As an intermediary industry, retail had previously shown its vulnerability under the challenges posed to logistics by Brexit, the alignment of ESG goals and the implementation of AI (Retail Economics, 2020).

Crisis situations put leaders to a test and forces them to consider an efficacious solution that protects those under their management and reduces to a minimum the consequences (Boin & Renaud, 2013). To overcome crises, the leaders must guide the teams working together, but also the organisation, which is not a simple task (Ivanescu, 2011). An organisational crisis immensely surges the pressure that falls on the leaders through the event, transforming them in heroes or even scapegoats (Boin & Hart, 2003). Therefore, it is vital to understand the actions of a leader both during and after a crisis, his or her strategic thinking and the resultant effects on the company's success in navigating through the crisis (Keller, 2000). The present research has been conducted at a major UK retail chain which has earned a 15.2 % market share (Kantar, 2021). The retailer's management kept communication between stakeholders open, also kept supply lines open, and met the challenges of increased demand for online shopping. A study conducted in June 2020 (Retail Economics, 2020), immediately after the first wave of the pandemic, highlighted three phases. The first involved survival which demanded focusing on liquidity and working capital. The second one related to the vital aspect of consolidating one's market position and reconfirming or expanding partnerships during the emergency. The third one allowed

innovation, including through new paradigms addressing consumer behaviour. The organisation selected as case study highlighted strategic thinking skills which benefitted the company and ensured its resilience during the pandemic. As a member of the organisation, the researcher partook in the internal communication which enabled a privileged perspective on how resilience was safeguarded from a workgroup to a company level. On an ongoing basis, the company is evaluating its systems and processes, to be able to cope with the next crisis.

The retail industry complied with a regulatory background which was applicable to the same stakeholder synergy that governs the sector. However, as mentioned above, the retail sector connects to various industries across the value chains it creates through its distribution channels. Liaisons with these stakeholders (logistics, suppliers, end consumers) demand distinctive competencies from department or line managers. Furthermore, each of these liaisons expose the management roles representing the organisation to different challenges. Therefore, not only are these department or line managers recruited from different backgrounds (qualifications, previous professional experiences, distinctive work conditions), but also they demonstrate and continuously put in practice different analytical skills than their peers who may perform from a similar hierarchical position within the organisation. Though affirmed within objective and universal settings, strategic thinking emerges through a psychological and cognitive deployment which is distinctively affirmed by each person. Furthermore, the same given target metrics could be differently dissected within goals by different individuals, whereas boundaries may be approached distinctively as limitations or resources. However, through their own role attributions, some leaders (department or line managers) have been exposed to the impact of the crisis than others. Furthermore, they have to set their own goals and metrics, having benefited from an increased autonomy from the management. It is shown in the literature that all the value stays inside the value chain which represents activities that deliver value to the customers and competitive advantage to the organisations, but they must reconfigure their value chain, as it is considered that being effective from an operational point of view is not strategy. Although, strategic positioning is generating a unique value proposition. The crisis context forced the retail sector to revise its value proposition, competitive advantages being built around issues such as health, safety, and promptitude. Such new requirements could be ensured through the wider intervention of some leaders rather than other. As mentioned before in the present paragraph, different roles demand different skillsets which are obtained from different qualifications and

career paths, signalling different paths. The strategic thinking of leaders in distinctive positions across the value chain cannot be studied by disregarding their own personal path. As an individual construction which differs from one person from another, one's biographical trajectory demands an interpretivist approach allows for the explorations of these nuanced approaches to the same goals. These would cast light on the workings of leadership in a particular and unique set of circumstances (Grundy, 2006).

1.2 Covid-19 Pandemic, An Unprecedented High-Velocity Global Crisis

The financial year 20/21 has debuted with a massive crisis the like of which has never happened in our recent history. Media and governments defined it as the worst enemy we could fight, with a much more severe impact than terrorism. The retail sector is one of the key pieces of the world's chess table during the novel coronavirus pandemic. Sainsbury's, Tesco, ASDA, and the other important retailers in the country are encouraging their office workers to work from home as much as possible. The studied retailer is running a lockdown test, closing their headquarters one by one. With a profound impact on all external stakeholders, from suppliers to the end consumers, the pressure of such messages dominating the general discourse weights upon decisions makers, continuously reasserting the severity of an unfamiliar context, while hindering clarity and having a great impact on the broad vision demanded for strategic thinking. Adjectives such as 'unknown', 'unfamiliar', and 'unpredictable' may indicate how existing knowledge and deductions that proved effective in the past have become unusable.

According to Denyer (2020), COVID-19 cannot be compared to other major crises, such as natural disasters, terror attacks, significant fires, and explosions or even the great economic crisis of 2008, that humanity and the economy have faced. The macro context in which decision makers have to perform is one in which Health Bodies, Governments, SMEs and HPOs across the Globe are shaping impressive and innovative strategies to tackle the deadly virus (Woolliscroft, 2020). Additionally, the WHO confirmed that the novel coronavirus is more impactful in developing political disruptions, social confusion, and economic disturbance than any terrorist attack. In the midst of this chaos, one thing is for sure: the organisations around the

world must rethink resilience to survive. During this unprecedented global upheaval, leaders are stretched to make quick, but strategic decisions, which can have significant impact in both a short and a long run. An important question to be answered in this unique context is how leaders can build a strategic approach to develop and strengthen organisational resilience, a vital characteristic during global disruption.

Before discussing an approach for developing organisational resilience, it can be useful to briefly define resilience. According to Trijp and Kees (2018), resilience is known as the ability to anticipate events and trends, to develop a plan in this regard, to adapt to the new context and probably most importantly to learn from the upheavals and challenges faced to get through and to maintain prosperity. The same definition was offered by British Standard BS65000 in 2014. While most of the previous global disruptions were slow-moving, the Covid-19 Pandemic exhibited an accelerated unfolding. Under severe public health restrictions announced to simply prohibit the physical presence of people in public places, leaders stretched their strategic and creative thinking to develop realistic last-minute solutions that could maintain their brick-and-mortar channels (Murray, 2021).

During such challenging times, empathy is one of the most valuable characteristics of a strategic thinking leader, claims Denyer (Denyer, 2020). In this context, empathy was shifted towards envisioning every stakeholder’s understanding of safety and how being exposed to both public health policies, as well as the messages dominating the public discourse influences their behaviour. Estimates on each stakeholder’s response are addressed by the organisation through a fusion between a defensive and a progressive understanding of resilience, as presented in the figure below (Fig.1).

Figure 1. Organisational Resilience Strategy Framework

(Trim & Lee, 2008)

Caniëls & Gelderman (2005) classified the strategic directions to be approached when building organisational resilience. Illustrated in the figure below (Fig.2), their schema was further adopted by Professor Denyer. The framework is developed around two dimensions, defensiveness, and progressiveness, complemented by consistency of the processes, routines, behaviours and flexibility of ideas, views, and actions.

The next step after setting up these four strategies, is active observation of the crisis's evolution pattern. As per the below diagram (Fig.2), the crisis can move around the four squares from the preventive control up to the adaptive innovation, evolving from a defensive – consistent approach to a more progressive – flexible attitude. Strategic thinking calls for new goals-actions configurations as the organisation transitions from each quadrant.

Figure 2. The Strategic Tensions Quadrants Model

(Caniëls & Gelderman, 2005)

The Preventative Control stage highlights the pivotal importance of revising the institutional framework which allows the systematic, continuous, and interdependent functioning of health and safety norms and instrumentalities. For decision makers within the headquarters, such a phase implied identifying the components and channels and links affected within the

organisation when regards as a system. The vulnerable components are the frontline (end consumer) units, logistics, and supply pipelines. The channels and links emerge from interior regulations which translate the statutory background issued for the overall society, as well as for the retail sector. Implementing the Preventative Control stage implied separating roles that required a physical contact with stakeholders from those that could be performed through remote work. For frontline workers who delivered the organisation's core function, strategic thinking implied analysing scenarios of consumer behaviour as expressed within physical metrics such as visiting hours, distance maintained while queuing or store visits conducted with another individual such as carers or spouses.

The second stage directed strategic thinking towards the terrains and margins in which adaptability and flexibility could be feasibly implemented. Therefore, strategic thinking called for anticipating the dimensions and the effects in which force majeure unfolding could manifest itself.

When the defensive strategies have been formulated and implemented, the company can migrate to a progressive dimension which debuts with performance optimisation. Strategic thinking emerged by anticipating the phases and the most responsive components or channels in the recovery stage. Each component highlighted its own KPIs that needed to be revised from their default prognosis and rhythm to realistic estimations within the new macro context. Targets were therefore adapted to the feasible limits descending from the new dimensions of the market (Cuellar-Fernandez, 2019).

Once the expected deployment, time length, and results within the performance optimisation were identified, strategic thinking was diverted towards detecting eventual innovation opportunities within the institutional and social boundaries, leading to new paradigms for distribution, such as omnichannel marketing (Hwang, 2020).

Crises can also be explored through the response attracted by very stage of their unfolding, as highlighted in Fig. 3 (Turner & Rindova, 2012). Recognised as the period in which the imminence of a crisis is acknowledged, the incubation period raises concerns of preventive control which will continue up until the group succeeds in optimising performance. Such expectation enriches strategic thinking with the opportunity of observation and reflection and enables critical assessment of how the organisation managed to anticipate the effective strategy

in preventive control. Eventual insights in the crisis deployment are further used for analysing the areas in which the organisation must revise its business model and consider innovating.

Figure 3. The Typical Crisis' Pattern and the Evolution of Leaders' Focus on the Four Strategies

(Groh, 2014)

1.3 UK Food Market Brief Analysis

The research aim investigates how leaders translate their life experience into insights to be further used in crisis management. The scope of the research refers to the retail industry. Though life experience is not resumed to one's professional path, the concept of intuitive familiarity which will be developed across the literature review indicates that the career one has built for themselves in a particular industry is more likely to be prioritised when contemplating what insights of their past experience are relevant to a possible response. Such deductions demand a brief overview of the UK food market. Furthermore, understanding the deployment and impact of the crisis mentioned as a core element of the research aim creates an imperative for studying the mutations produced by the COVID-19 pandemic on the food market.

In March 2020, the industry reported a record performance of 20.6% growth compared to the previous month. Primarily driven by the customers panic buying, the average household bought groceries for an extra £62.92, equivalent to an extra five days 'worth of groceries. Analysing the market share from a channel perspective, online sales have increased by 13%, while convenience stores and small branches have gone up by 13.8%, as people are shopping more often during the pandemic. Overall, the 'big four 'retailers saw an increase of 17.7% in sales compared with no growth in February. Sainsbury's reports the highest growth with 21.6% versus 1.2% in February, gaining 13bps market share compared with a loss of 4bps in February. (Kantar, 2020).

Figure 4. Grocery Market Share (12 weeks ending) in Great Britain

(Kantar, 2020)

As people started self-isolating, the number of home deliveries increased between 23-38% per week. The Government's advice of reducing shopping sessions to, one per week had a massive, negative effect on spontaneous purchases. Both fears over the development of the crisis, and an immersion in cooking as a recreational activity determined the distinctive dynamics exhibited by some essential groups of food such as flour and yeast.

1.4 The Rationale, Scope, and Importance of the Study

Strategic thinking leadership explored in this study has the main purpose of preventing organisation from sleepwalking into failures during global disruption such as being experienced at present in the form of the Covid – 19 pandemic. In other words, this thesis discusses different strategies adopted by leaders to survive and to prosper. Particular attention is paid to the Retail sector, considered a key sector during global disruption, when countries around the world face lockdowns, travel restriction and social distancing. Supermarkets enhance their workforce and leaders make important decisions at a fast and unprecedented pace to ensure that food is available for everyone. The non-essential shops close, while food stores run at maximum capacity. The business environment is shaken up and only those who can strategically turn the crisis into an opportunity may survive.

A question arises around this global crisis: how can organisations customise their strategies and initiatives to meet customers' needs to survive while remaining competitive and most importantly, to keep their employees safe, engaged, and motivated? In short, this is about the importance of stretching the mind of strategic thinking leaders to accomplish their mission to build organisational resilience. The study thus analyses the insights gained from their life stories, to be able to identify what counts as strategic leadership and how this works successfully within a business. Because the milieu in which they are functioning is so crucial to the economy, and the decisions they make so vital, the research is very focussed on highlighting that importance and strives to ascertain the level of strategic thinking they exhibit and apply in their day-to-day lives.

As indicated by the literature review, the field of strategic thinking has been comprehensively explored. I have focused on an open question – one that relates to the actual experiences of leaders who make use of strategic thinking in their day-to-day roles. The pursuant Narrative Inquiry forms the main thrust of the study and provides illumination on a unique scale: the reader is party to the personal thoughts, decisions, and experiences of the company's senior strategic thinkers. Their personal lives are interwoven in their stories (Craig and Huber, 2007). A further aspect of the open question is the influence of the Covid-19 global pandemic over both the studied leaders, as well as the company. The disruption caused by the pandemic has been unique

in the history of business. A characteristic of the pandemic has been the practice of working from home and conducting business remotely, with all its attendant challenges: this and other facets of conducting business in this environment, which will be elucidated in the data analysis, are novel. The impact of the pandemic on business has yet to be fully explored, researched, and documented (Delardas, 2022).

The scope of the study falls within the disciplines and theoretical fields explaining how previous circumstances have been assimilated as reference used in the individual response to external factors. I wished to answer this question in a positive way and to show how the approaches of the leaders at the retailer could make organisational resilience possible: the context of the pandemic is widely known, but the implications for leaders doing business in these times and their solutions and decisions have not been widely documented, thus, the delimitations and contribution of the study are proposed to be within the area of strategic thinking in business. Data points not used would be related more to general business insights and personal anecdotes, but the data related to the impact of strategic thinking would be used.

1.5 The Aims and Objectives of the Doctoral Thesis

The aim of this doctoral thesis is to answer the following question: How do leaders translate their life experience into insights for strategic thinking in times of crisis? On a more specific note, this research explores the topic of strategic thinking leadership in the context of the Covid-19 pandemic. The research's aim is divided into several subsidiary objectives, such as establishing the definitions promoted by the researcher's community for strategic thinking, leadership, organisational resilience, and global disruption, as well as analysing the main leadership theories and their relevance for strategic thinking and building organisational resilience during global disruption.

The focus of this thesis is on leadership styles emerged within the retail sector under the pressure of a crisis such as the COVID-19 pandemic. Leaders in any organisation are ultimately responsible for its success or failure (Schlossberger, 2022). The present research provides the same consideration for the two major leadership profiles -the transformational and transactional styles -that are attached to a higher number of complementary or unrelated traits, modus

operandi, or ethical values under a growing corpus of literature. Past experience is related not only to one's own individual actions, but also to the insights attained through the observation of others, the dynamics of group cohesion, and the patterns, as well as the limits of inter-peer cooperation, aspects capitalised by transformational leadership in task assignment, team allocation, guidance, or development. Furthermore, objective parameters as inter alia the time of project delivery invoked when contemplating eventual outcomes generated by past collaborations with particular peers justify the mention of transactional leadership within the theoretical background.

Practice highlights leadership as unlikely to be rigid or immutable. Adaptability becomes an imperative, demanding that personal experiences are analysed as a relevant precedent which can provide clarity over any new circumstances to be accounted for in decision making. Decision-making is articulated in objectives that are elevated on a diagnosis of the organisation's existing and potential performance. Measurable targets formulate the company's goals. Strategies are nothing else than vectors pointing towards these objectives. However, strategies can be converted into objectives and vice-versa (Ansoff et al, 2019). Effectiveness may be upgraded through reactivity. Decision makers should focus on conceiving objectives that enhance each other, while endorsed by a proper timing that reduces their exposure to their industry's risks (Porter, 1980). Decision making culminates in strategic planning which is viewed as a response to the constant transformation of both organisations as well as their environment (Argyris et Schön, 1978). Strategic planning is formulated through management capability and implemented through functional capability (Ansoff et al, 2019). Such a conclusion has never been more visible in the retail industry than during the global pandemic, where the functional capabilities were challenged by delays within the supply flow and with the pressure of unforeseen factors such as panic buying. In a regular setting, the company benefited from a regular operation flow sustained by its members to the end-consumer level. Maintaining the same functional parameters during the pandemic implied a higher focus on how the ethos is preserved and the usual levels of commitment to the organisation are not jeopardised. Pressure came as extreme health concerns over an – at that moment – untreatable disease, could cancel any incentive used by leaders in their motivation.

There are a set of aims in the study which revolve around the topic of strategic thinking of leaders. At first, theories by the research community are examined for the important concepts making up this field of study such as strategic thinking and leadership, and their relevance for building organisational resilience during global disruption. Understanding how prior experience shapes strategic thinking in times of crisis is essential to train one's cognition in order to promptly identify solutions which have proved effective in similar circumstances and reconfigure them to respond to the particularities of a new context. The practical implications of the findings could also be extended towards a tool which can be used by both individuals as well as teams. Such tool could allow assessing the extent to which one's personal contribution or that some other peers might have provided for a particular project can be replicated for a distinctively new challenge.

The objectives of the study specify how the study is going to fulfil the research aims.

Considering my aims and the method of data analysis, the researcher planned to answer the main research question meeting the following research objectives:

1. To examine the life stories of senior leaders within the retailer and identify factors in their personal backgrounds which may have had an influence on their development as leaders
2. To use the insights gained regarding their professional life to evaluate skills they developed in their careers that formed them as potential leaders.
3. To assess the characteristics of their strategic mindset through their skills, capabilities and important decisions made during their careers, particularly in times of crisis.

The elements of the research question to be qualified are strategic thinking, leadership, organisational resilience, and global disruption. These are the layers to the questions and are interwoven. To achieve the objectives, the aims have been clarified and expounded. In this regard, the importance of proving that strategic thinking in senior leaders is of paramount importance for the survival of the business is core. The objective is to use Narrative Inquiry with largely unstructured interview techniques: the rich vein of data to be gathered this way will reveal the distinctive variables each individual may consider within the same given settings.

CHAPTER 2. REVIEW OF LITERATURE

2.1 Introductory argument on the selected approach to the literature review

The research aim indicated the foremost directions with which to identify the concepts around which the relevant literature could be compiled, as well as the disciplines and fields such theoretical background could be extracted from. Three cardinal concepts indicate the disciplines and subfields in connection to which the relevant literature can be identified, notably those of leadership, strategic thinking, and crisis. The core concept of my thesis is strategic thinking. However, the scope demands further concentration of the concept from strategic thinking in a general perspective to that affirmed in leadership. Though drawing upon three core concepts, the research aim imposes separating the compiled literature into two key momentums. The research aim demanded the identification of mutations activated within strategic thinking by a crisis context. Consequently, the structure of the literature review had to answer the same main question by contrasting the occurrence of a phenomenon in a default as well as in a crisis setting.

Strategic thinking preoccupies scholars of both social and business environments. The relevant literature transpires from the research scope which could be identified by framing the exact scholarly terrain to be explored within such inter-disciplinary approach. Though present in an exhaustive range of areas of interest, strategic thinking is not privileged by an unanimously accepted definition. Concepts such as cognition, knowledge, personality, and values were the most frequently mentioned arguments in the business studies approach to strategic thinking.

Investigating the sources of strategic thinking also demanded a clear perspective on the institutional settings of its issuance. The first condition implied separating strategic leadership from the general practice of leadership. The second condition demanded exploring the manifestation of strategic thinking within strategic thinking and its effects on an organisation. The manifestation of strategic thinking in an organisational setting demands identifying its influences and application but also the barriers to its approach as subject of learning and development.

The second part of the literature review should study how the concepts identified in the default manifestation of strategic thinking unfold in a crisis setting. The foremost area is to identify the leadership style exhibiting the highest level of effectiveness in crisis management. The main argument for which leadership style should be integrated as a possible lens for understanding strategic thinking can be connected to the multiple, unpredictable, and mutating circumstances challenging decision making in its day-to-day practice. Strategic thinking should not be regarded as an abstract construction detached from any coordinates other than goals and actions. Routes to achieving objectives as well as the instrumentalities available to concretely implement these actions are set by dynamic formations of variables that change from one stage of the process to another, demanding a continuous readjustment of strategic thinking. The impact of strategic thinking in a crisis context is analysed at its three levels of manifestation: the organisational culture, group cohesion and individual motivation. Such a multi-dimensional impact highlights the exact areas in which different styles should be analysed.

2.2 Strategic thinking through interdisciplinary lens

Manifested both on an individual, as well as on an organisational level, strategic thinking can be regarded as emerging out of the confluence between management and psychology. Beyond cognitive psychology, according to Olson and Simerson (2015), strategic thinking draws upon system thinking and game theory. Cognitive psychology explores the processes behind analysis and interpretation. System thinking is manifested in connection to the management, alteration, and manipulation of the external environment. Game theory can be detected in discernment, logical deduction, and goal-effort configuration employed in problem solving.

Despite an outstanding spectrum of definitions, as a theoretical concept, strategic thinking is not privileged by scholarly consensus related to rationale, components, or deployment. In an abstract register, strategic thinking has been correlated to diligence, such as authors (Argyris et Schön, 1978, Ansoff, 2019) warn about the existing confusion with strategic planning.

Haycock (2012) signals two key approaches on strategic thinking which is describes as either a stage within the process of strategic planning or an ongoing manifestation found beyond

functions and roles within an organisation. The general consensus identified by Haycock (2012) indicates strategic thinking as a privilege of leaders.

2.2.1 THEORETICAL DEMARCATION FROM COMPLEMENTARY CONCEPTS

Strategic thinking amassed critical thinking, reflective thinking as well as creative thinking. Critical and reflective thinking are the product of predictive thinking which absorbs visual thinking, numerical thinking, and recollective thinking. Reflective and creative thinking are issued through ethical thinking, which is developed upon recollective thinking, empathetic thinking, and verbal thinking (Wootton, 2010). According to Wootton (2010), strategic thinking manifests itself through the capacity of anticipating the dynamics of a macro factor (predictive thinking), of estimating the scale and limitations of an issue (critical thinking), of mentally correlating an issue with the opportunities and threats it generates (reflective thinking), of visualising the pathways to innovation (creative thinking), of identifying the feasibility, stakeholders, sustainability and risks of an issue (ethical thinking), and of communicating an idea from an imagined representation to a coherent and persuasive message (visual thinking).

The absence of a consensus on what strategic thinking may involve is an essential requirement of translating abstract issues into diligence. However, strategic thinking is not to be mistaken with the following concepts which can be considered as complementary both from a theoretical as well as a practical perspective:

2.2.1.1 Strategic planning

Scholars have been rather preoccupied with strategic planning, placing strategic thinking as a preliminary momentum (Bonn & Rundle-Thiele, 2007) and to be explored within the limits of significance attributed. Strategic planning is formulated through management capability and implemented through functional capability (Ansoff et al, 2019). As strategic planning falls into the theoretical spectrum of management, its processes enjoyed peer consensus both in content (Drucker, 1968, Porter), as well as in deployment. According to the objective to be delivered, strategic planning is based on a preliminary phase affirmed through feasibility and market

studies, a development stage in which insights obtained from the preparation processes are integrated into action and a delivery stage encompassing roles and instrumentalities. Unlike the logical framework of strategic planning, strategic thinking has a much more intimate progression, converging intuition, mindsets, and previous experiences. (Bonn, 2005)

Strategic thinking precedes strategic planning which involves elaborating the process of implementing the former's insights (Bonn & Rundle-Thiele, 2007). Decision making culminates in strategic planning which is viewed as a response to the constant transformation of both organisations as well as their environment (Argyris et Schön, 1978) Strategic thinking is therefore employed at any stage and activity covered within the strategic planning.

Strategic planning appears to be more and more based on design thinking. As a cognitive paradigm used for creating bespoke solutions, design thinking transforms insights acquired through observation and ongoing dialogue into eventual practical solutions. As a difference between strategic and design thinking, while the former aims towards long-term outcome, the latter targets contextual practicability. Design thinking privileged strategic analysis through its use of visual representations. (Knight et al, 2020)

Strategic thinking is directed towards limitations exhibited across the experience acquired with strategic planning (Bouhali et al, 2015). On such grounds, strategic planning emerges as a pipeline for informal knowledge upon which the precedent used in any further manifestations of strategic thinking is grounded.

2.2.1.2. Creative thinking

Creativity represents the pivotal trait of good management in the light of problem solving as a component of strategic thinking. Strategic thinking inherently contains the essence of creative thinking. Creativity involves reassembling concepts in configurations that have never been used in experimentation. The displacement of or insertion of certain elements can redirect problems either towards a positive or a negative deployment (Ackoff, 1978), signalling how strategic thinking operates on conceptualisation.

Creativity is explained as the product of design thinking, which implies achieving innovation and new strategic approaches to solve complex problems (Simon, 1997). The exact relevance which justifies the approach of any precedent is withdrawn by the new areas and localised variations of impact of an unfamiliar occurrence. As existing knowledge is less likely to be effective and even applicable in a disruptive event, the only pathways for reaction which are not by default invalidated are those which have not been tested. Consequently, experimental approaches within paradigm innovation represent the only safe alternative for an organisation.

When producing marketable outcomes, creativity gives rise to innovation which may target the product, the process, the beneficiary, or the paradigm. The cognitive process behind innovation emerges out of a synergy between intersectional and interdependent systems within an organisation, in which the process of creating novelty by repairing such systems in new compounds is key to strategic thinking, thus it should be placed at the core of this process. (Bonn, 2005) As pipeline for innovation, creativity unfolds as the coherent synchronisation between objective elements such as the structure of a task and a subjective dimension elevated by a person's own cognitive style. However, such polarity raises the issue of creativity as the ability to produce a wider volume of new configurations of the same elements into different purposes or that of exploring new interpretations or sequences of the same issue, and thus, the same destination. While the first prospect is typical of systematic individuals, the latter is highlighted by intuitive individuals. Regardless of profile, structured conditions which descend from a leader's guidance are demonstrated as fundamental for elevating both the volume, as well as the depth of creativity (Sagiv et al, 2010).

Cultivating creativity requires the assignment of tasks that best highlight individual competencies. Leaders use their creative, strategic skills to lead as individuals and as part of teams, acknowledging and rewarding their team's commitment (Bonn, 2001). Creative thinking must be however separated from strategic thinking on grounds of purpose as scope. Strategic thinking aims at the highest level of effectiveness in reaching a desired outcome. Unlike creative thinking which demands exploring new pathways for attaining goals, the processes, instrumentalities, and sequence of tasks employed through strategic thinking may unfold in an identical manifestation to previous experiences.

2.2.2. THE DIMENSIONS OF STRATEGIC THINKING

Strategic thinking emerges as a cycle between three mutually dependent manifestations: creating usable knowledge from past experiences (1), direct present action from correlating goal formulation with outcome prediction (2) and improving future performance through decision making (3) (Wootton, 2010). Consequently, strategic thinking demands envisioning the optimal balance between an immediate effect and long-term consequences. Strategic thinking highlights analysis and prediction abilities. Though both analysis and prediction depend on one's cognitive deductions, they remain vulnerable to one's familiarity with the variables affecting a given context. Strategic thinking is organically developed under the assimilation of formal and informal learning. The acquisition of knowledge implies context discernment and learning transfer, as information is assessed according to its meaning, purpose, and implications. Strategic thinking emerges as a fusion between intuition and analysis. Intuition, however, must be regarded as the cognitive process through which latent knowledge acquired by means of similar experiences is highlighted in the person's reasoning as a possible solution. Analysis implies reflecting on the feasibility, limitations and outcomes of such insight awakened by intuition if applied to the given context. (Sloan, 2019) Leaders benefit most when they can direct their strategic thinking outside of the area of the problem they're supposed to solve and operate with a multidisciplinary knowledge. While a focused mindset would best favour professionals in the early stages of their career, leaders are expected to have a more exhaustive understanding of the micro, meso, and macro environment of an organisation (Gallup, 2015). Even though best favoured by one's cognitive abilities, strategic thinking also benefits from accumulated work experience which is itself highly vulnerable to one's personality and general charisma (Dragoni et al, 2011). Exploring the use of the Go board game as a tool for training strategic thinking amongst Japanese executives, Henkel (2011) argues that character traits such as patience and moderation are more important than cognition in strategic thinking. The concept behind Go is that of developing a comparative advantage by prioritising reasoning rather than calculation. Players advance by contemplating, rather than estimating the consequences of their moves. Reflection is based not on gains, but on reflection over the development opportunities and the further decisions launched by every move. Reflected through inaction or articulated through a

hasty approach grounded on previous experience, leadership hubris is an equal influence in how the impact of a crisis is registered across an organisation (Villanueva and Sapienza, 2021).

The formal and informal knowledge attained through work experience also affects ethics which may be integrated within strategic thinking. The intersection between an individual's psychology in cultural and social settings such as their upbringing raises the issue of moral values as an influence on strategic thinking. Such juxtaposition elevates four distinctive profiles -the humanistic type, the competitive type, the elitist type, and the entrepreneurial type - identified by whether a manager sees human capital as related to the person or the outcome of their work (Bolander et al, 2017). Signalled by a person's view on work, the demarcation is vital to understand whether the leader is open to a participative approach or not. Operating on the differences between the individuals and task execution, the profiles may highlight distinctive performance assessment frameworks which may favour both inputs, as well as output. The perspective affirmed in each of the profiles indicates the leader's belief as to whether potential is innate or acquired, as well as whether competence is transferable or context dependent. Individuals may confirm at least one profile.

Cognition and knowledge as the two core components of strategic thinking will be further analysed in this study.

2.2.2.1. Cognition - the catalyst of strategic thinking

Cognition transpires from the four types of thinking identified by Wootton (2010): recollective, numerical, visual, and verbal thinking. Recollective thinking describes the capacity to access key memories that would provide the insights. Numerical thinking implies the ability to correlate an issue with quantifiable values such as scale. Visual thinking is grounded on foresight and the capacity to create mental representations of the deployment of a phenomenon. Verbal thinking allows you to visualise various implications, configurations, and structural components launched by the connotation of a word just by mentally searching for its definition or synonyms (Wootton, 2010).

The cognitive dimension of strategic thinking also covers the mindset of decision-makers. (Bonn, 2005). The cognitive dimension of strategic thinking is particularly advocated by means of the Trait Theory which excludes the possibility of acquiring leadership skills through training as

opposed to the behavioural thought. A person's mindset determines their acknowledgement and response to incentives and threats, but also how such stimuli would dictate the sequence of stages within the cognitive process. Reactive responses are directed towards eliminating existing or hypothetical issues, whereas proactive efforts are channelled towards attaining an input. Problems are regarded in synergy, never independent, and uncontrolled variables launch alternative procedures towards reaching the objective. The objectives are also influenced by the a priori projections of the potential outcomes for effective strategies. Since a priori assumption limits creativity; the challenge is acknowledging the occurrence of such beliefs, ultimately eliminating them, arguing that efficiency is measured on the probability of delivering the targeted outcome (Ackoff, 1978).

The use of memories or past experiences in decision making implies developing analogies between events or objects which can be regarded as references and a new context. Analogies are developed systematicity of the explicit causal structure in which various references such past experiences are inserted in new configurations such as the problems to solve (Gentner and Turpin, 1986) Gentner and Markman (1997) signal analogies as sophisticated processes employed in the creative discovery which can be separated from similarities which are grounded on perception. Analogies represents the product of structural mapping which is activated by separating commonalities from differences. Analogies expand possible routes in decision making through interference. However, connecting two objects through analogies can highlight asymmetries as they present communalities in some aspects rather than all.

Analogies emerge from different cognitive processes reaching structural similarities which are detected on a process level or superficial similarities which are connected to an element level. Arguments brought by individuals in their real-life decision making indicate structural similarities as the source of analogies. However, lab studies conducted by Blanchette and Bunbar (2000) signal analogies as based on superficial similarity, whereas structural relations are rather activated when facing an appropriate task. Applied to the research aim, the management dimension of leadership may reach structural similarities such as methodologies, whereas the human component of leadership may relate to superficial similarities detected between personality types or behaviours.

Applying the precedent within problem solving can employ both objects, as well as story lines. Identifying and extracting a relevant precedent employs accessing and using those memories.

Superficial similarities are detected in both the use and access to the story lines and objects individuals take as reference when connecting a problem they face in the present to decision which past experiences indicate as relevant (Ross, 1989). Furthermore, individuals are more inclined to reject sources which appear superficially dissimilar, without contemplating over the implications or the connections in which the objects or the stories have developed (Heydenbluth and Hesse, 1996) If superficial similarities are not employed, past experiences may be inserted in decision making through schema abstraction or mental representations individuals make when disassembling a present problem. Categorisation is however more frequently employed than cue-based reminding (Snoddy and Kurtz, 2021).

Studies conducted by Gregan–Paxton et al (2000) indicate that investment-related decision making is based exclusively on the data available on the company and not the investors' personal knowledge. However, the investors' personal knowledge is perhaps surprisingly employed when engaging in predictions over the company's future. Leaders, however, differ from investors through both a direct experience with the company culture and command chain, but also through a compact perspective on its evolution which is concentrated on the leaders' direct role in the organisation. As previously mentioned, resilience can be regarded as a projection of the company's future. The leaders' contribution to the company's goals accounts for a personal knowledge gained through direct experience. Therefore, findings on investors' use of existing knowledge is also relevant in the study of leaders.

Sources become solutions for present problems under the effect of a direct hint. Analogies emerge differently amongst experts and novices. Experts to whom leaders can be assimilated are likely to engage in relational mappings between the target and the reference. Novices, however, to whom team members can be assimilated are more likely to use analogies for illustration, mapping objects in relation to attributes (Bearman et al, 2007).

Differences are demonstrated to be identified faster than similarities (Sagi et al, 2012) However, differences can be separated based whether they present any commonality. Differences that do not align or present no commonality, have a wider impact than alienable differences in the judgement of similarities from differences (Estes and Hasson, 2004). Representations employed by novices facilitate the understanding of similarities, whereas induction is achieved by the ability to connect

non shared attributes (Lassaline, 1996). However, analogies and the assessment of similarities remain highly vulnerable to the individual's perception of the context (Goldstone et al, 1997).

Pure rationality cannot be expected of human behaviour which is rather inclined towards heuristics. Furthermore, human nature should not be attributed self-control as a default characteristic. Personal involvement affects the rationality of forecasts or evaluations, while an already existing patrimony is more prized than probable achievements. In fact, the attitude towards risk is reversed when contemplated from the perspective of a gain or a loss. The most notable illustration comes with the concept of 'transaction utility' which attracts the frustration by opposing a given cost which individuals cannot influence to one that they judge as fair for the particular purchase (Thaler, 2015).

2.2.2.2. Knowledge - the key resource for insights development

Knowledge ensures the rational dimension of decision making. Value judgements assess stakes that benefit the organisation and that therefore can be appropriated as goals, whereas factual judgments assume strategic planning. Whilst values are given the certitude of planning, facts depend on hypothetical circumstances. However, facts are constructed on information that is available on the environment they depend on, whereas values are defined by the organisational identity and are only limited by legislation and ethics (Simon, 1997).

The importance of knowledge has highlighted the competency model under which leaders are handed the challenge to scrutinise individuals that confirm the highest impact on an organisation's performance. Regardless of role, knowledge work such as management is exclusively justified and measured according to results (Drucker, 2006). Competency models are introduced with the purpose of detecting behavioural patterns that may result in specific traits, insights which could further set either the methodology or the curricula for L&D programs. Critique rises as such patterned abstraction may not appropriately cover all manner of relevant behaviours encompassed in leadership. An adjusted approach accommodating various areas of expertise is to be favoured compared with a standardized perspective on competency models. Shortcomings of competency models are related to overlooking the occurrence of certain behavioural traits and evaluation-related challenges, as well as to a poor synergy with other talent management practices (Goldman, 2016).

Strategic thinking draws upon both formally as well as empirically acquired knowledge which may be attained through exploitative to explorative learning. Exploitative learning encompasses a more focused use of knowledge highlighted within a certain field. Explorative learning embraces a multidisciplinary approach to knowledge governing an area (Miller and Ireland, 2005). The cognitive processes employed within strategic thinking imply recognising similar occurrences within personal experiences (Goldman, 2008). Intuitive familiarity can be understood as the product of exploitative learning (Wang and Rafiq, 2009). Such perspectives can be related to how exploitative learning allows an understanding of how repeating patterns compose one's experience within a role of a profession. The continuous exposure to such situations allows a more accurate discernment of how similar occurrences may unfold. Such ability can be connected to exploitative learning. However, within an organisational setting, intuitive familiarity is rather attained by generalists responding to diversified tasks and enforcing explorative learning, in contrast to specialists who have earned their competencies by performing within an exclusive knowledge terrain which they manage to master in limited connection to correlated areas (Pasamar, 2019). An additional informal pipeline for the acquisition of knowledge comes from proactivity and notably, receptivity to feedback. On such grounds, knowledge should also involve a constant and alert transformation of strategies according to the feedback received for every phase that has been implemented (Ansoff, 2019).

Though benefitting from formally acquired knowledge, strategic thinking raises a key issue for reflection. Regardless of their emergence and manifestation, leadership styles remain behaviourally issued, confirming no connection to expertise or competencies (Alban-Metcalf, 2013), (Caniëls & Gelderman, 2005).

2.2.2.3 Strategic thinking at the intersection between cognition and knowledge

On a subconscious level, cognition employs practical knowledge assimilated from direct experience or empirical observations passed through judgement filters which are unique to every individual. The rational dimension, accommodating insights stored from formal learning whether self-directed or guided, is only surveyed later. As an intimate process, cognition is at most explained in regard to catalysts and eventual references, but not through process or connections. According to such a pattern, strategic thinking blends universal knowledge which has been

attained by an individual through formal pipelines with insights extracted through personal experience. Though uniquely fostered by each individual, practical knowledge may highlight distinctive patterns connected to assimilation (Okoro, 2012).

Employing inductive and deductive reasoning, strategic thinking emerges as a mix between insights and rationality. Calabrese and Costa (2015) used Peirce's theory of abduction to theorise cognitive processes generated within strategic thinking. Peirce's theory of abduction implies building a conclusion on the available knowledge, regardless of how complete it may objectively be considered. Decision making within leadership follows a similar pattern as strategic thinking is used to deduct insights from known facts and use induction to estimate the void of information.

2.2.3 THE ROLE OF STRATEGIC THINKING IN LEADERSHIP

Leadership has been theorised and explored in regard to style (Lewin, Bass 1985, Avolio 1991, Brown, 1991, Meij, et al., 2016, Urbano 2018) persuasion, reward (Bonn, 2001) and the ability to transform potential, whereas cognition behind efficient delegation has been overlooked. Leaders employ strategic thinking in goal formulation, process structuring, inter-peer collaboration and team empowerment (Olson and Simerson, 2015). Strategic thinking is employed in various stages of decision making starting from the imperative of studying the organisation's competitive environment in order to engage in predictions on its future evolution to issues related to governance such as formulating objectives, translating them into action plans, and critically assessing proposals from various stakeholders (Wootton, 2010) Strategic leadership is applied through the effort of gathering strategic intelligence and the ability to discern the appropriate insights to generate strategic change (Olson and Simerson, 2015).

2.2.3.1 The peculiarities of strategic leadership in contrast to general leadership

The key characteristic distinguishing strategic thinking from general thinking resides in goal formulation. Strategic leadership differs from the general notion of leadership in two key areas. The first connects strategic thinking to the highest hierarchical levels of issuance. In contrast,

leadership can be found all across the organisation, regardless of authority. The second highlights strategic leadership as dependent on strategic thinking which implies creating opportunities to complete goals by assessing available options (Norzailan et al, 2016).

Strategic thinking can function as an indicator of leadership styles. When directed towards cognitive and motivational goals, strategic thinking highlights task-oriented leadership styles. By contrast, people-oriented leadership styles reflect behaviour-targeted strategic thinking (Bajcar et al, 2015).

The earliest research (Mitchell, 1970) on leadership styles highlights how an individual can exclusively embody one leadership style and the same person maintains the same approach regardless of situation. The continuous revision of urgencies and their translation into goals determines an individual's shift from one leadership style to another. The literature also exhibits how leadership styles are likely to overlap. The present literature review aims to utilise a selection of works focused on how the discernment of insights is conducted and how team coordination responsibilities are synchronised to deliver a strategic response. Olson and Simerson (2015) posit that the same person integrates four different leadership styles in accordance with the requirements of each context. The Visionary Type is characterised by the ability to convert personal experience into insights. The Directive Type is demanded in the application of structures and processes, notably in assigning work group, task delegation and establishing the sequence of activities. The Incubating Type is characterised by the ability to empower others, identifying both their potential, as well as the best, most appropriate contexts in which to reveal, amplify, and capitalise on the traits detected in each team member. The Collaborative Type can be observed in a leader's capacity to develop partnerships and adjust their input for cocreation.

2.2.3.2 Effectiveness in strategic thinking

As a core concept of Drucker's work, effectiveness represents the foremost goal which validates instrumentalities considered within the achievement of specific objectives. Effectiveness in strategic leadership starts with strategic thinking, continues with the ability to formulate policies as the guidance expected from the team, and reaches its highest complexity through change management (Norzailan et al, 2016). Confirmed a posteriori, once a tested approach has

delivered the expected outcome, effectiveness represents the core indicator for precedents to be taken into account as potential configurations for the further momentum of strategic thinking. Effectiveness may be upgraded through reactivity. Decision makers should focus on conceiving objectives that enhance each other, while endorsed by a proper timing that reduces their exposure to their industry's risks (Porter, 1980).

Leadership differentiates itself from authority by the ability to inspire a sense of participation which has team members contemplate their potential input (Drucker, 1968). Team members should coordinate experience and viewpoint exchange, as this does not originate from abstraction but from concrete accounts. (Hudson, 2004). Though leaders should learn how to delegate tasks, effectiveness demands they encourage initiative, thus limiting unnecessary interventions that can delay their team in delivering results (Drucker, 2006). Initiative, however, represents an issue of people empowerment which leadership can deliver by promoting autonomy and encouraging inter-peer cooperation.

The real importance behind strategic thinking lies in the capacity to predict future events and neutralise their impact. Through effective strategic thinking, leaders are likely to affect the course of change, rather than positioning themselves under its influence (Arayesh et al, 2017). Capacities such as forecasting emerge as combination skills (Wootton, 2010). Leaders must demonstrate knowledge both regarding the type of insights they should request, as well as in connection to their interpretation. Further skills amassed include being able to anticipate the time span and expectation for each variable identified in the insights.

Reaction to unexpected changes consumes more organisational resources than anticipating and preparing for them. Neglecting the necessity to cultivate forecast maintains a reactive posture according to which organisations become overwhelmed with day-to-day issues instead of channeling efforts into growth. Such dynamics appear as urgencies claim all energy without allowing the required clarity for goal formulation (Bouhali et al, 2015).

Scenario planning plays a vital role in crisis management, challenging strategic thinking to envision deployments judged as unpredictable. Planning techniques play a key role in the accuracy and effectiveness of collected insights. Strategic thinking can be directed towards both identifying and creating these tools, as well as for employing them. In scenario planning,

strategic thinking is used to fathom the entire area of action, to envision consequences, and to identify limitations (Brooks and Curnin, 2021).

2.2.3.3 Self-efficacy: the primary terrain for intuition and analysis

Strategic thinking also opens a perspective on self-efficacy which stands out as the sine qua non condition for anticipating one's own response to a crisis, as well as the areas and the strategies one would adapt. In order to effect change and work creatively, self-awareness is essential to drive the process of strategic thinking. Resilience is also dependent on a proper knowledge of one's own values, beliefs, and ethics (Dartey-Baah, 2015)

Newly received information is processed and interpreted in patterns that have been established under the influence of the most frequently replicated previous experiences. However, training self-efficiency demands reflections on the premises considered in decision making. When delivering the conclusions emerging out of strategic thinking, one should verify whether their critical analysis has covered all variables driving this process (Gibbins-Klein, 2017).

Self-efficacy also determines time management which requires focusing on the essential by eliminating all activities that compromise productivity (Sheats, 1968) Time management should dictate both the enactment of a team, as well as the coordination which is to arise between its members (Drucker, 2006).

2.2.4. PARADIGMS FOR THE DEVELOPMENT OF STRATEGIC THINKING IN AN ORGANISATIONAL SETTING

Both in their central strategic approach, as well as in their day-to-day operations, leaders must focus on simultaneously addressing two key issues: the context itself and how their teams respond to it. The context itself demands sense-making, scenario analysis, contingency planning, and nevertheless, estimating organisational resilience. The teams' response is influenced by mental wellness and effective communication (Crous, 2020). Models for developing strategic thinking should connect an individual or group-oriented approach to the social context, challenging the organisation they are engaged with, while profiling a strategic thinker as one

who challenges and overcomes uncertainty by a multi-oriented focus that allows, considers, and even targets the analysis of divergent hypotheses (Bonn, 2005).

2.2.4.1 Diagnosis

Problem solving has a preliminary stage in strategic diagnosis which implies evaluating the structure and the instability that characterise all areas a company operates in. It also features the required time frame within which the new outline can be fully completed and start to produce benefits. When acting within various industries, decision-makers can opt for a strategic portfolio analysis, which evaluates expectations arising in each area. Estimated opportunities call for a diversification analysis that can redirect operations towards new fields. An insightful diagnosis should nevertheless draw conclusions regarding the prospect of future environment turbulences affecting each field of enterprise. (Ansoff et al, 2019) Decision-making is articulated in objectives that are elevated on a diagnosis of the organization's existing and potential performance. Measurable targets formulate the company's goals. Strategies are nothing else than vectors pointing towards these objectives. However, strategies can be converted into objectives and vice versa (Ansoff et al, 2019). In the case of retail, vulnerable fields of enterprise are raw material sourcing, logistics, and the timely supply of the distribution network.

As a concrete application of strategic thinking, problem solving can accommodate three questions of universal applicability known as the Drucker method. The first stage implies identifying and consulting people with an acute sense of awareness of each issue. The second implies challenging the organisation in regard to such scrutiny, which may give rise to a feasibility assessment of its resources, regulations, institutional boundaries, strategic line, and other such issues. The third stage implies highlighting various strategic options to further consider. A reconsideration of the hypothesis under which an inquiry analyses both the context, as well as the opportunities detected is further encouraged. Every issue is examined at its core and translated to its clearest description, leading towards new opportunities benefitting strategic thinking. (Zand, 2010).

Critical skills should be trained not only in connection to the information absorbed as data, but also in connection to the knowledge one possesses of the different elements of an environment. The discernment of human reactions represents one of the ways in which strategic thinking is

adapted to variables arising from the external environment. The limited knowledge we possess of the individuals affected by our actions becomes an inflow towards strategic thinking which becomes directed towards finding the most effective pathway and process to obtain the desired outcome. Such dynamics are particularly visible in communication. Strategic thinking allows leaders to anticipate the audience's response and helps them adjust their narrative to the receivers' expectations and barriers. Storytelling as a tool for motivating employees and communicating to other stakeholders such as investors is grounded on such pattern, as the same information is readjusted to obtain a bespoke construction that appeals to the addressee (Cutolo et al, 2021).

2.2.4.2 Simulation

In managing our intuition, we should breed a scientific mindset to accommodate various scenarios. Allowing opinions can broaden the field of opportunity, opening new perspectives to challenges. (Hudson, 2004). Mechanisms engaged by administration are set in motion through decision making which involves an estimation of possible strategies that might ensure a fulfilment of goals to be further evaluated according to the possible consequences each one attracts (Simon, 1997).

The anatomy of a strategy distinguishes a timing-based completion, therefore excluding the prospect of an immediate fulfilment. Built of assertions which by nature draw on incomplete and speculative information, a strategy is charged with a self-explorative purpose, constantly responding to potential risk scenarios that may arise throughout its unfolding. Such transformation will inevitably question the strategy's premises, demanding therefore a flexible construction that adapts to constantly changing parameters (Ansoff et al, 2019).

The human mind lacks the capacity to detect all valid behaviours that may cater to the implementation of a decision. Furthermore, prognosis should consider the simultaneous occurrence of contradictory principles that can be equally applied to a given situation (Campitelli & Gobet, 2010). Scenario-based reflection represents a fundamental pipeline for identifying, and thus mitigating, the impact of exceptions from acknowledged, discerned, and, consequently, exploited precedents. In estimating possible outcomes, knowledge always generated a fragmented unfolding of scenarios. The rationale of a scenario is to detect trends and incertitude.

Forecasts and estimations should revolve around knowledge we are certain of and should consider variables of which we are not aware. Mapping efforts only ensure a feeble picture of a context, given the difficulties to trace variables that might affect or even reverse initial predictions. Opinions reconfirm their importance by elevating interpretations that guarantee a multidimensional character to a scenario (Schoemaker, 1995). Speculative inputs of value stand at the core of any prognosis which should consider the simultaneous occurrence of contradictory principles that can be equally applied to a given situation (Simon, 1997).

An essential point of debate focuses on the circumstances that influence our perception of occurrences as correlated or independent from one another. Aversion to risk can be avoided by amassing assignments into one, so that projects would appear as coordinated (Thaler, 2015). Personal experiences can provide insights when submitted to Self-Organizational Assessments or to simulation exercises (Kovoor-Misra, 2020). Self-assessment tools provided by Wootton (2010) indicate that strategic thinking can be cultivated by identifying strategic knowledge which leaders are recommended to absorb, by training strategic ability, and by understanding the variables to be included when engaging in strategic decisions, depending on context.

2.2.4.3. The influence of corporate culture

Drucker highlighted the crucial role of the work environment in relation to strategic thinking and effectiveness within the work environment (Drucker, 2006). A maximised achievement of goals is conditioned by how organisational culture succeeds in being promoted as a commonly shared vision that all members adhere to, as the dynamic of thought is strongly linked to interactions with others. (Bonn, 2005). Corporate culture becomes vital for an organisation to maintain its market relevance; it is crucial to how it handles information flow when it surpasses an individual's capacity to effectively process and employ information. Leadership converts organisational culture into a filter for strategic thinking (Kazmi & Naaranoja, 2015).

Encompassing areas of audit, competitiveness, advancement or contraction and ethics, market culture is demonstrated as the most influential factor in the organisational culture for training and for organically developing strategic thinking (Arayesh et al, 2017).

Peculiarities differentiating each organisation convolute attempts to theorise decision making. Such an approach can be developed on studying the inner dynamics of a firm and can be further extended to explain its industry or volume of activity (SMEs or corporations). Influences on

organisational behaviours include the pressure of operating with given resources to ensure a targeted output. A parallel occurrence to decision making comes from internal regulations that set-in motion what Cyert and March (1992) describe as “non-strategic behaviour” (Thaler, 2015).

Innovation is the fruit of corporate culture rather than the result of research and development (Martín-de Castro et al, 2013). Though preconceptions tend to regard innovation as providing the core of radical changes, its emergence has some rather slow dynamics. It is developed on the grounds of creative thinking which is successfully conducted following a proper knowledge of one’s goals. Its roots in corporate culture make innovation dependent on teamwork, therefore creative thinking is favoured by effective leadership. Innovation should be regarded as a potentially trainable behaviour. Innovation can also be the proactive response to a crisis (Vaitheeswaran, 2008).

2.2.4.4 Limitations to the effectiveness of learning programs dedicated to the development of strategic thinking

Strategic thinking is difficult or impossible to be taught and cultivated (Goldman, 2015). Deeply anchored as an inner construct in empirically acquired knowledge, strategic thinking is favoured by constantly surveying insights. All newly received information is processed and interpreted in patterns that have been established under the influence of the most frequently replicated previous experiences. Discerning insights attained through observation employs a neurological component related to details which dominate one’s perspective. Neurological constructs may differ from one individual to another, such as using logical deductions issued by critical, and thus intimate and non-replicable previous experience. Such individual peculiarities reinforce responses to various occurrences, allowing a certain anticipation within the deployment of events (Whipps, 2014). While patterned scopes are only to be used for repeated deployments, exceptions should be confronted through tailored approaches (Maciariello, 2006).

Further limits to organisational training include what James March refers to as superstitious learning, a rational that links succeeding events by a cause – effect logic, collectively developed mindsets or holding on to strategies that have proved themselves inefficient (Argyris et Schön, 1978).

2.3 Strategic thinking in crisis management

2.3.1 PECULIARITIES RAISED BY THE COVID-19 PANDEMIC IN CRISIS MANAGEMENT

The study of crisis leadership is challenged by a dispersed range of research interests that hinders efforts in identifying any consensus in literature (Wu et al, 2021).

COVID-19 imposed near and short time solutions as an immediate response to crisis management. However, the pressure placed on the leaders' strategic thinking to discern the threat and possible unfolding of a crisis which has never been experienced before is demonstrated in the revision of their approach to business continuity management through a change of parameters, to assess strategic risk and synchronise it to operational resilience (Graham and Hoe-yeong ,2022).

As a disruptive context, the pandemic signalled the urgency of recentralising management so that discontinuities within the supply chain would be reduced as much as possible (Schelepet et al, 2021) Recentralisation reduced the relevance of leadership at a store level, which, if not addressed by store managers themselves, might have threatened the retail staffs' own commitment to the organisation. Such risk would have produced a fracture in the liaison the organisation has developed with its end consumers. Furthermore, recentralisation should not be perceived as a reclaiming of leadership from the company's senior management. On the contrary, the emergency elevated the senior management's focus mostly -if not exclusively- on to the functional aspect of administration, such as implementing the new regulations issued by the Government and ensuring that the supply chain responds to the extreme fluctuations in demand. As a paradox, such context raised a higher responsibility of leadership coming from shop managers. Though their authority may have been affected through recentralisation, the entire organisation depended on how they managed to maintain their team on duty. Motivation faced a revised scale from that of Maslow's pyramid from upper incentives to basic necessities such as health and safety. Relatedness within the ERG framework played a vital role.

Crisis contexts affect decision making. Studies conducted by Bachkirov (2015) on decision making under the influence of extreme emotions indicate that fear shifts judgement towards a deal-oriented

processing. Therefore, under the general panic discourse, leaders are more likely to formulate goals and choose directions of actions by assessing the potential of loss mitigation. Stress is also demonstrated to decrease strategic thinking and assess options according to predictions of the responses of others (Leder et al, 2015). In the leaders' case, such tendency can be identified in a passive approach focused on possible directives from superiors without enabling their prerogative to decision making.

Uncertainty is also likely to shift perspective towards immediate or very short-term results, suspending the prospect of an extended time orientation for assessing outcomes. Smit et al (2017) propose the concept of "Strategic Net Present Value (NPV) for assessing options within decision making. The responsibility leaders hold towards their team imposes the necessity to anticipate how uncertainty also affects the team members' general state. On such grounds, strategic thinking converges towards the ability to develop a Theory of Mind (ToM) which allows them to understand the individual factors which determine a certain behaviour amongst their peers and to predict such response (Rusch et al, 2020)

Discontinuity as a form of uncertainty directs strategic thinking towards exploratory, reframing, and decision scenarios (Wayland, 2019) Exploratory scenarios introduce new construct paradigms to increase the understanding of an issue. Reframing scenarios place the issue in an expanded perspective. Decision scenarios add new actions paradigm within decision making.

2.3.2 STRATEGIC LEADERSHIP STYLES IMPOSED BY CRISIS MANAGEMENT

Leadership styles are fundamental in understanding an individual's capacity to acknowledge and integrate variables emerging in a crisis context. As to be reasserted in my sampling strategy, different hierarchical levels which set distinctive reporting responsibilities demand different views on task delegation or guidance. Each role is favoured by a distinctive leadership style without which strategic thinking could not be properly fathomed. Compared to a general context, where, in leadership, strategic thinking faces objective restrictions such as statutes and feasibility parameters, the COVID-19 pandemic was unprecedented. However, the directions and decision

scale within which leaders can articulate their strategic thinking is not limited to objective parameters. Our era highlights the growing pressure to change the paradigm in which the business environment sets its responsibilities from reporting to shareholders to one where it is accountable to stakeholders. Grounded on the earliest theorisation of leadership as a practice, leadership styles are eloquent for understanding how individuals relate to the prospect of integrating into their strategic thinking both the objective parameters of feasibility, as well as the stakeholders affected by their decision making. Nevertheless, strategic thinking must also adapt to the power invested in a leader by the board or any superior role or hierarchical element within the organisational structure. The imperative for approaching crisis management through the most effective leadership style is set by dynamics related to policies, revised synergies within the value chain, levels of authority, and, ultimately, the time frame all to be considered within the decision- making process.

2.3.2.1 Transformational and transactional leadership: a brief overview

According to Bass (1985), transformational leaders manage to converge their teams' efforts towards organisational goals by inspiring them towards a higher understanding of the importance of their input, while also directing their own contribution towards their own development needs. Bass formulated his theory of transformational leadership upon the mutations registered in human behaviour as a reaction to change in the environment. Such an approach represents the core argument recommending (Bass,1985) theory as framework for analysing how leaders readjust their strategic thinking under the pressure of crisis. Furthermore, a crisis can be regarded as the main prospect in which common goals organically juxtapose individual goals. According to Bass (1985), transformational leaders exhibit four key directions of action: Intellectual Stimulation through the assignment of tasks challenging critical thinking (1), Idealised influence which takes the form of mentorship for more complex future responsibilities (2), Inspirational motivation which reaches both clarity in communication, as well as encouragement towards continuously updating one's potential (3), and Individualised Consideration which implies the acknowledgment of every member's merits. The four components extend the argument for approaching the Transformational Leadership theory as a possible framework for the thesis. A crisis itself represents an exceptionally bountiful context for Intellectual Stimulation. The higher

responsibilities arising from managing an unknown context in a crisis may inspire scepticism towards the prospect of entrusting others with tasks during a crisis. Idealised influence can be connected to both the example set naturally under the higher responsibilities a leader is invested with through their own role which becomes the institutional setting for mediating the new norms within the organisational command chain. Individualised Consideration arises from a leader's prioritising the focus on the team members' relatedness as a pathway for maintaining group cohesion. Also connected to preserving every team member's relatedness, the Inspirational Motivation can also accommodate the premise for leaders to turn the crisis into a context for developing their team's competencies.

Crisis and emergencies are however accounted for as the contexts demanding that leaders consider the transactional style shaped around the reward-punishment binary. Implemented through supervision and monitoring, it prioritises performance and execution of tasks. However, the responsibilities to align the public health policies (social distance, etc) to the organisation's own norms and to accustom team members with the new paradigm for work called for the task-oriented character of transactional leadership during the Covid crisis.

The following subsections are dedicated additional arguments supporting the transformational leadership style as the key theoretical framework for the present research. The arguments will be analysed according to the response demanded by the stages within the pandemic's unfolding.

2.3.2.2 The influence of pragmatism and resource preservation

Characterised by high uncertainty, disruptive times pressure safeguarding stability, a revised goal which signals the apparent salutary input of transactional leadership. Under the transactional model, performance should be reached in the most cost-efficient manner. Enforcement-oriented, the transactional leadership operates on a bi-dimensional axis of rewards and sanctions.

Transactional leadership can be found in any organisation endorsing commission-based work where the employees' revenues depend on reaching a certain level in sales

(Nanjundeswaraswamy, 2014).

An organisation's peculiarities lead to a natural alignment towards two major leadership approaches: the incremental mode, which is characterised by a more rigid course that doesn't favour change and the entrepreneurial pattern with its highly responsive modus operandi, critical

within disruptive times. While the former allows predictability, the latter is much more spontaneous and harder to anticipate. A swift change from one approach to the other will eventually generate hard bearing effects, while the prospect of having both modes coexist inside the same organisation would attract unnecessary challenges to its trajectory, slowing down its natural velocity. However, strategic planning can be survival-motivated, prioritising a linear evolution over exploring hypothetical opportunities (Ansoff et al, 2019). Unlike strategic management that targets prospective opportunities, thus employing an entrepreneurial perspective, operating leadership fertilises the organisation's existing potential using the incremental mode as framework. The incremental model relies on a limited number of alternatives and advancing in small steps, which itself can be limiting. In synthesis, the benefits highlighted by each of the two styles signals leadership as a practice which could be adapted to the conventions circulating within each industry and to the challenges traditionally faced by each role in an organisation; much more, may be synchronised to various time frames to achieve goals.

2.3.2.3 The influence of change and readjustment

Both rewards as well as sanctions may end up losing their relevance for employees with the prospect of having their organisation readjusting its priorities in order to mitigate new dimensions of risks beyond those familiar from assessment frameworks. Consequently, transactional leadership becomes unfeasible within disruptive times, both from the perspective of an objective content of measurable goals, as well as through its persuasive potential to echo within incentives (Alkharabsheh et al, 2014).

In times of change and upheaval and crisis, innovation is particularly bred from necessity or crisis or self-preservation and is directed towards safeguarding relevance and towards risk mitigation. Organisations can also build up innovation in their societal background by responding to changes in demographics, technology, information, tastes, and mentalities. Change can profit an organisation both through its manifestations as well as all along its progression (Drucker, 2006). As highlighted in the industry analysis provided by Retail Economics (2021), COVID-19 accelerated the changes of paradigm which were either limitedly implemented

(blockchain synergies), tested (on-sharing) or still contemplated (ESG accountability). The COVID-19 pandemic can be regarded as rather the impulse than the catalyst to change.

The defensive urgency imposed within the immediate impact of a disruptive event calls for high promptitude which is rather connected to the quota-system sustained by transactional leadership. Transactional leadership is recognised to respond to quantifiable quotas that should be delivered as short time goals. However, though operating on objective parameters, compared to the persuasive approaches adapted to the other end on the value flow, supply chain management is also more favoured by transformational, rather than transactional leadership. (Chen et al, 2021) The benefits transformational leadership could bring to the supply chain management within the retail industry could be related to the implementation of a new sourcing and distribution paradigm, which could pave the way for sustainability. Purpose as a symbiosis between relatedness and growth elevates prosocial motivation which can further generate a new profile of organisational commitment. Communicating performance through the narrative of common goals, as advanced through transformational leadership, could expand the suppliers' portfolio, reduce the company's carbon footprint, and introduce resource circularity as a strategy for waste management. However, such goals are rather recommended within the flexible-progression quadrant of crisis recovery (Denyer, 2021). Such effort consensus between group members and coordinators elevates the servant leadership (Xu et al, 2022). Sketching an imagery for the common goals beyond KPIs is notably visible within the 'Feeding the Nation' initiative in which the organisation took part, whereas the sense of purpose which employees may strive towards has particularly echoed in the 'keyworker' praise circulating on a societal level.

Transformational leaders are also fundamental to rebuilding organisational capacity after crises (Kovoor-Misra, 2020). For delivering such transformation, strategic thinking is applied in three key areas: content, people, process. Content demands identifying the areas which must be transformed such as the case of remote working. The people element calls not only for identifying the roles that will deliver the change, such as cybersecurity engineers for the digital infrastructure to connect devices from outside the organisation in the case of remote work, but also for evaluating the overall emotional state of staff during each phases of the transformation- to use empathy to formulate the best communication strategies. The process element refers to the

instrumentalities delivering the transformation such as the digital infrastructure for remote work (Anderson and Anderson, 2002).

Innovation either embodies or triggers change not only in its concrete element, such as perfected technologies, but also in a new approach to their exploitation that may maximise efficiency. Paradigm innovation is inherent to any large-scale upgrades. As change demands innovation in leadership, new challenges may arise for the organisation, both on a business model level, but also on an individual level. Change is also favoured by how disruptive events in unforeseen and inestimable variables call for the contingency framework which minimizes a leader's role by reducing any registered efficiency to happenstance (Avery, 2004:30). Innovation involves the capitalisation of change as an opportunity and can be grounded on both internal sources, as well as on factors observed outside the organisation. Putting objectives in motion requires connecting the organisation with its environment while aligning its internal components -members, departments, management- to the newly conceived direction. Internal resources were aligned through remote working, whereas paradigms such as omnichannel marketing delivered the readjustment of capabilities to the external threat of reduced operations under physical space restrictions. Once such architecture is fulfilled, the company's activity is submitted to operating policies that regulate its day-to-day performance. (Ansoff et al, 2019)

Reservation regarding change is inherent in human nature and may highlight the need for an incremental mode as the organic approach to leadership. Resistance to change risks organisations entering into 'social inertia' (Ansoff, 1977). Strategic change is bred by the proper organisational pillars, such as in a corporate culture which evidences a receptive mindset.

Transformational leadership embodies privileged strategic thinking through the insights acquired in critical dialogue launched within participative decision making (Sloan, 2019).

Disruptive events emerge outside an organisation, whereas self-defence strategies depend on its internal assets which encompass resources and competencies. Instrumental leadership adheres to the purpose of connecting both environments within an organisation. Creating bridges to the external environment allows organisations to rebalance their vulnerable areas and thus neutralise the impact of disruptive events while strengthening their own powers. Instrumental leadership represents another salutary style imposed by the studied context (Antonakis, 2004).

Leadership styles determine how strategic thinking is either fostered amongst the teams or transmitted as a directive to be further implemented. Both the transformational, as well the transactional styles are confirmed as salutary in stimulating strategic thinking amongst team members. Though in compact work groups, the Laissez-faire approach may prove beneficial, it is excluded by the imperative of norms adapting public health policies. (Gross, 2016)

Empathy should be regarded as essential to the effectiveness of strategic thinking, which cannot produce the targeted accuracy without recreating another person's perspective (Wootton, 2010). In order to upgrade their team's response, leaders must readjust strategic thinking to the traits employees are most receptive to. The approaches employees judged as most effective in their leaders' behaviour converge towards individual attendance, guidance, and motivation (Carinal-Go et al, 2021).

Recent opinions (Urbano, 2018; Benedetti, 2019) claim that transformational leadership is more applicable to start-ups than to large organisations. Indeed, charismatic leadership is less visible and consequently, impactful, given the distance produced by multiple hierarchical levels and decentralised structures. However, matrix and divisional structures which are most frequently encountered in the retail industry revise power poles into formations (department and groups) which may operate through various levels of autonomy to a composition and dynamic that is similar to those of SMBs. Organisational resilience depends on group cohesion, which is favoured by transformational leadership.

2.3.2.4. The imperative of adaptability in leaderships styles

Employee expectations within a crisis context converge towards prompt action and empathic communication, which signals the necessity of considering a compromise between the transactional and the transformational style (Haddon et al, 2015). Gause's Principle of Competitive Exclusion which states that ecosystems don't confirm the coexistence of two species of an identical living provide an eloquent imagery paramount importance in flexibility and adaptability in leadership. Challenges faced by an individual within the organisation can be regarded as variables affecting an environment. Their occurrence, frequency, and manifestation influence both the number of opportunities, as well as the number of competitors, while

competitive advantage stands at the core of each strategy. An action plan should be developed on the understanding of all peculiarities arising inside a competitive environment. Such insight can be further used to predict risks, once anticipating the participants' competitive behaviours and the exchanges they engage in (Henderson, 1989).

The transactional and transformational styles have been identified in the Full Range Leadership Theory framework, which was developed by Bass (1985) on a revision of Kurt Lewin's authoritarian and participative models. The demarcation between the two styles had initially been envisioned in connection to the delivery span for organisational goals. Emergency measures with a temporary enforcement and applicability call for a different style than norms and strategic directions designed to be installed on a permanent or indefinite basis.

Operating during the pandemic forced a new dimension to the "planner-doer" duality which on a default setting explains both the logic and the action of norms coordinating an economic activity (Thaler, 2015). The thesis of a dual dimension to strategic planning (Ansoff et al, 2019) has never been more visible in the retail industry than during the global pandemic. The functional capabilities were challenged by delays within the supply flow and with the pressure of unforeseen factors such as panic buying. If in a regular setting, the company benefitted from a regular operational flow sustained by its members to the end-consumer level, maintaining the same functional parameters during the pandemic implied a higher focus on how the ethos is preserved, and how the usual levels of commitment to the organisation are not jeopardised as extreme health concerns over a seemingly untreatable disease could cancel any incentive used by leaders in their motivation (Ansoff et al, 2019).

As change is implemented, clearing of uncertainties, and opening new perspectives, stabilising any kind of reform requires a new 'refreezing' phase (Becherer, et al., 2008). The transformational and transactional styles of leadership are separated also by their attitude towards change. The transactional leaders disregard changes not based on conservative beliefs, but by a highly pragmatic approach to work that strives towards the most cost-effective and therefore, familiar solutions (Bass, 1985). Surprisingly, such a strategy can be regarded as beneficial within a disruptive context where the pressure of neutralising threats does not allow analysis and reflection. Prioritising familiar solutions redirects focus over relevant precedents and how the knowledge they provide can be adapted to new factors.

Dartey-Baah (2015) proposes the resilient leadership profile as a mix between the transactional and the transformational styles. Resilient leadership is therefore characterised by strategic thinking and performance orientation as understood through adaptability, receptivity to change, openness to learning, emotional intelligence, and a collective approach to organisational goals.

2.3.3 THE MANIFESTATION OF STRATEGIC THINKING IN TRANSFORMATION

Organisations are exposed to three different types of change: developmental, which aims to improve already existing settings; transitional, which is conducted for replacement needs, and transformational, which is imposed by mere survival in contexts which cannot be accurately predicted.

Transformation demands simultaneously addressing the strategic terrains of instrumentalities and behaviours. Instrumentalities imply norms, paradigms, and systems. Behaviours, in contrast, are highly vulnerable to emotions. If neglected as variables in strategic thinking, emotion affects the effectiveness of the leaders' attempt at building the necessary culture for the transformation. Nevertheless, transformations differ from other types of change as their entire implementation remains vulnerable to unpredictable occurrences (Anderson and Anderson, 2002).

2.3.3.1. Organisational culture

In their original theory Bass and Avolio (1993) signal the leaders' role in setting up the organisation's culture which inevitably becomes a factor that further affects the effectiveness of their actions. The COVID-19 pandemic is characterised by an exhaustive set of public health statutes which the organisation had to adapt in its internal regulatory structure, while also mediating its relationship with its customers, since essential stores were the only physical settings open to the public. The complex norms and procedures were imposed in the retailer, which, according to Bass and Avolio's (1993) theory, functions within a culture of rules. Installing the new regulatory framework and aligning the default, pre-COVID organisational culture demanded transformational leadership.

On a general basis, corporate culture must be aligned to its strategy. According to the size and status of the organisation under review, the achievement of goals depended on the corporate culture, to which leadership must be aligned. Furthermore, the crisis context of the COVID-19 pandemic makes the general strategy irrelevant, and affects the gearing up tasks, until a new strategy is formulated (Kaul, 2019). One might rightfully argue whether such a relationship remains relevant as the organisation has to comply to new sets of rules -which suspend norms existing in the organisation's culture. The relevance of culture in such a context does not reside in the actual content of rules, but in the capacity of promoting any new norms. It refers to the workforce's receptivity and willingness to engage in efforts to comply with and adhere to the new norms.

Anticipating and overcoming a highly challenging context demands developing a reaction before a disturbance is installed, but somehow signalled. A strategic response must match the magnitude of the new circumstances, regardless of whether emergencies call for an abrupt and disruptive reconfiguration of its concept, portfolio, or communication. Both corporate culture as well as its internal coordination must enforce this new outline by overcoming any kind of rigidity manifested towards change. Resistance to change is mostly reflected in the rejection of newly approved priorities and the setback of their implementation (Ansoff et al, 2019).

Under the contingency framework, decisions made are dependent on the internal and external situation in a company (Tanveer, 2018). Within crisis management, resilience is reflected in the organisation's capacity to prepare, respond, adapt, and learn. Strategic thinking can be used to formulate a model of cultural resilience which can be directed to grow the social capital.

Transformational leadership becomes vital to redesigning the organisational culture (Koronis and Ponis, 2018).

2.3.3.2. Group cohesion

Transformational leaders use strategic thinking to evaluate both the context, as well as the individuals and the work groups in order to identify the most effective approach to use in communication. Assertiveness is best demanded in motivating followers in contexts of crisis which may be perceived as overwhelming. Bargaining is demanded in contexts of participative leadership in which the team must acknowledge why suggested arguments stand out as the most

effective strategies to approach given tasks. Coalition must be considered when communicating to demotivated groups which fail to cooperate effectively, where leaders must become the unifying element (Krishnan, 2004).

Guidance represents the general expectation developed by teams in regard to their leader whereas turbulence affects their trust in the leaders' ability to effectively deliver their role (Wootton, 2010). Contrary to the rationale behind transactional leadership, in a disruptive context, compared to a challenging momentum occurred with familiar market parameters, stability is more likely to be safeguarded through group cohesion rather than the competitive individualism driven through reward-sanction stimuli (Sung & Savaspaakdee, 2021).

Crisis management imposes leaders be cautious about how their decisions influence tasks, as well as relationships with peers. While erroneous task-related directives only impact the execution of a task, ineffective relationship – related behaviours can threaten key variables for the employees' commitment such as their job satisfaction or sense of purpose (Brandebo, 2020).

The increased dynamics generated by a crisis context bring the challenge of a massive flow of new data that may lose its relevance before being properly processed. The accelerated data update demands increased attention which can be realistically attained exclusively when decision making is fostered by a participative environment. Such an environment implies cooperation beyond areas of expertise and aligns competencies with the common vision communicated within leadership (Gianos, 2013).

Transformational leaders succeed in elevating their team's engagement, which impacts their performance, development, and cooperation (Caniëls, 2018). Addressing issues related to esteem prevents or neutralises threats to individual resilience, which in a collective setting is profoundly dependent on relatedness and by the ability of transformational leaders to communicate common goals. To team members, such needs get to be fulfilled also by experiencing the context that allows them to be inspired by their leaders and imitate them. Appealing to elevated needs such as esteem, appreciation, sense of utility and intellectual stimulation, transformational leadership operates on intrinsic work motivation, according to (Avolio, et al., 1991). Transformational leadership promotes a vision as an ideal which crystallises common goals. Performance is to be reached by personal development cultivated in the 'lead by example' spirit (Benedetti, 2019). The inspiration provided through transformational leadership synchronises the team members' mindset to whatever values propelled through organisation culture. Transformational Leaders

succeed in having team members prioritise the group's interest to their own (Nanjundeswaraswamy, 2014) (Sadeghi, 2012).

Conflict management is vital in disruptive times which elevate crisis towards new degrees of probability adding new stress factors to individual resilience as a sine qua non condition for group cohesion. As a leadership goal, group cohesion employs both hard as well as soft skills. While the former is visible in the synchronised insights delivered through every member's expertise, the latter transpires from empathy which is articulated through communication styles which are adapted to every psychological profile. Aiming towards group cohesion, transformational leadership delivers an inclusive environment which in the context of friction of any degree is achieved through integration (Porter and Daniel, 2007). Compliance, as an alternative response towards conflict management defines how transformational leaders empower their followers in order to raise the quality of their input and increase the premise for effectiveness within the pursuit of goals (Lyubykh, 2007) (Muchiri, 2019).

According to Rahim (2002), conflict management may generate five distinctive responses. The first two- integration and obligingness- are regarded as constructive approaches in alternative to three other attitudes - domination, compromise and avoidance which are best to be excluded as an option. Transformational leaders encourage integration and compliance, according to (Hendel, 2005), as a probable extension of their proactive engagement. The exchange-oriented focus of transactional leaders has them opting for compromise. Avoidance of compromise reflects the weak implication of the laissez-faire model (Tanveer, 2018).

While communal strategic thinking targets competitive advantage, conflict and disparate thinking comes at a potential cost associated with such a management profile. Nevertheless, conflict leads to a re-evaluation of mindset on an individual level, triggering the acknowledgement of new references that lead to more diversified and representational systems (Han and Stieha, 2020). In normal circumstances, conflict in business milieus would be seen as disruptive, often in a positive sense where employees were striving to bring about change or difference. Disruptive practices in the eye of the Covid-19 storm were not confrontational or conflict-g geared, but rather aimed at coping with the new reality through innovation and diversity of practice, without distress.

Inter-peer cooperation is vital for maintaining individual performance to its default levels. Cohesion and relatedness mediated by transformational leadership reduce distress which can affect individual resilience in the absence of an accommodating buffer phase within the transition process (Daniel, 2019).

2.3.3.3. Member input

Leadership that shows no receptivity towards members' participation is less favourable to overcome turbulences following the limited knowledge that can be fructified as strategy (Ansoff, 2007). In a default context, the application of empathy in leadership highlights a set of attitudes and behaviours which stands out as pivotal to effective task delivery through team motivation. Emotional stability is fundamental for crisis management, extraversion contributes to the role of evangelising the organisational culture, openness supports a proactive team commitment, agreeableness allows becoming an interface for the company and consciousness is essential for maintaining ethics (Paleczek et al, 2018). In a disruptive time, psychological capital takes the form of individual resilience.

Constantly mutating environments demand that perspectives and conclusions should be evaluated regardless of the hierarchical position they emerge from. Diversity in perspectives and cognitive patterns is essential as it broadens the potential of detecting opportunities (Evans & Salaiz, 2019). A diversified range of perspectives contributes to a wider awareness and understanding of the context challenging the organisation; also, diversity of assets among senior management in terms of abilities, education, and expertise rather than that defined by biological attributes or by social backgrounds benefits the company (Abraham, 2005). The more exhaustive the array of inputs, the higher the potential for progress through problem solving and identification of new opportunities. Leadership skills are now demanded of every team member and not only of those in charge of their coordination. A reasonable point of debate arises whether leadership is now employed as a medium, thus ceasing to mark a hierarchical position (Kazmi & Naaranoja, 2015).

Transformational leaders call for every team member's contribution, extracting new insights on issues challenging the organisation (Pasamar, 2019). Such receptivity towards new perspectives produces creativity, which is regarded by Bass as a dominant trait of transformational leadership (Becherer, 2008). Knowledge hiding represents a defensive behaviour leaders must anticipate and address in a timely manner. In order to safeguard their jobs, employees may retain valuable information related to the outcomes of a decision, should it not produce an optimal performance. The Transformational Leadership style and the Conservation of Resources can be integrated to prevent knowledge hiding by identifying the patterns of this behaviour and the effective interventions and guidance to neutralise their risk (Scuoto, 2022). Furthermore, if unaddressed, knowledge hiding can be perpetuated as a defensive response for every context in which a decision or its implementation highlights results which are other than optimal. Transformational leadership is demonstrated to be notably effective for neutralising role conflict as a variable influencing knowledge hiding (Nguyen, 2022).

The consolidation of the digitalisation paradigm which was bi-directionally ongoing from both the distribution as well as the consumption end has accelerated the establishment of shared leadership which forces a horizontal hierarchical structure. However, shared leadership as driven by digitalisation is considered to be yet in its infancy with no confirmed evidence over stable frameworks through which it can be implemented in retail. Nevertheless, transformational leadership is vital for the solid, mid, and even long-term sustainability of this paradigm, whether it's for B2B liaisons or B2C attendance (Van der Berg, 2022).

The increased responsibilities the organisation held in connection to its external stakeholders exposed it to an increased vulnerability to megaphoning behaviours especially coming from the frontline staff. Any kind of interaction with customers risked amplifying irrational behaviours such as panic shopping which the organisation assimilated as one of the key pressure factors of the crisis. Lee and Chon (2020) demonstrate how transformational leadership can positively impact megaphoning behaviours. The concrete influence of transformational leadership is evidenced in both communal and exchange relationships with direct implications on intra-group communication, as well as on the hierarchical transmission of norms.

2.4 Chapter Summary

Strategic thinking represents an intimate process preceding strategic planning. As it may integrate the exact same processes and the exact same argument, strategic thinking differs from creative thinking which implies applying the same knowledge within different configurations. Strategic thinking should not be confused with design thinking which is oriented towards identifying applicability for every knowledge configuration.

Strategic thinking is mentioned as a key characteristic of strategic leadership, which differs from general leadership in connection to the hierarchical levels. Emerging from roles invested in the authority of goal formulation, strategic thinking focuses on internal resources, thus employing on an individual level introspection and self-efficacy. If applied to leadership, strategic thinking views internal resources as not only the potential recognised in each member, but also as the outcome identified in combining individuals with their dynamic and partially predictable responsiveness within the same task. Consequently, fathoming internal resources represents the key challenge of strategic thinking in leadership. If leaders don't prioritise group cohesion and members' empowerment, any such estimations are threatened by how the pressure of a crisis content affects individual resilience and responsiveness.

Strategic thinking is built upon cognition and knowledge and may also integrate the person's personality and ethics. All these elements represent intimate manifestations which differ from individual to individual, making strategic thinking impossible to be trained. Strategic thinking may be, however, perfected when focusing on one's analytical skills. In an organisational context, an individual's ability to acknowledge the relevant knowledge for dealing with a context and interpret it as insights can be trained through diagnosis and simulation. Whether engaging individual or group potential, strategic thinking views the interaction of internal resources, competencies, and capabilities in relation to external circumstances which may highlight both opportunities and threats before which the issuer aligns their response according to their ability to measure the likeliness, as well as the impact of any such occurrence. Regardless of one's own capacities in anticipating such outcomes in a non-disruptive setting, accuracy in estimation is inevitably affected in unforeseen circumstances.

Crisis context affects the relevance of any reasoning which confirmed effectiveness in previous experience. The various stages under which a crisis unfolds demands either a passive, preservation – oriented approach or a defensive response affirmed through readjustment and transformation. Change, however, depends on the leaders 'capacity of acknowledging new variables and integrate them into strategic thinking. The capacity or openness to integrate new cognitive configurations in decision making imposes a deeper analysis of the particular profiles identified in the leadership literature through their receptivity to change. Therefore, the transformational (Bass, 1985) leadership style represents the core theoretical concept for this profile upon which more recent concepts such as Instrumental Leadership (Antonakis, 2004) have been developed. Transformational leadership is also characterised by how responsibility is extended in individual responses, including that of the entire work group.

Consequently, they must demonstrate the knowledge of relevant traits characterising their team, such as must guide them towards converging their own individual response with the desire of the entire team.

Providing a definition of strategic thinking and its clear application in leadership, the reviewed literature facilitated insightful angles for resolving the research aim of investigating how leaders use their life experience as an eventual precedent for navigating within a crisis. The reviewed literature provides the theoretical background to be applied in delivering the second and the third research objectives, highlighting the skills acquired across the leaders 'professional life and evaluates how such abilities have shaped their leadership. The literature also identifies the characteristics of the leaders 'strategic mindset and their application in resolving a crisis. The reviewed literature does not address how relevant individuals find the precedent when an assessed crisis occurs in the exact organisational setting in which they have developed their analytical skills. Areas for further research may therefore include whether individuals focus on the novelty or the familiarity element when assessing a crisis.

CHAPTER 3. METHODS AND METHODOLOGY

3.1 Research design and strategy

Studying strategic thinking in leadership as applicable in the UK retail industry during the COVID crisis of the beginning of 2020 draws upon an aggregate of unique occurrences. The crisis itself is described as exceptional. The retail sector's position is privileged by contrast with other industries, as it is allowed to operate within the general parameters. However, unlike other industries, the retail sector is challenged by additional pressure factors such as irrational consumer behaviours. All issues stated satisfy Garcia's and Gluesing's (2013) argument that qualitative research can facilitate both theory development and the validation of new research methods.

The focus topic of my research concerns the role of strategic thinking during a time of crisis and how decisions can affect a business. The premise for designing a relevant methodology would demand tracing the cognitive processes within strategic thinking and their adjustment to crisis management.

The goal of producing transferable findings can be fulfilled in the scholastic terrains of crisis management, strategic planning, leadership, guerrilla management or simply in the FMCG retail industry's response to the COVID crisis.

Though dedicated to an academic purpose, the present research has been structured to appear comprehensive to a wider audience. The novelistic reading attributed by Van Maanen to an impressionist account may enhance the chances of such a reception (Hammar, 1991).

3.1.1 RESEARCH PHILOSOPHY

The research aim demanded launching an enquiry into how experiences might have moulded perspectives when filtering information to ground decisions. The reviewed literature highlights six main strategies in their methodology: quantitative research, qualitative research, scenario planning, observation, case study, and neuroscience. However, the research scope explored within the present research is focused on one particular organisation operating within one

specific industry. Both organisations, as well as the industries accommodating them represent human-created environments, whereas the functions, synergies, regulatory frameworks, and expectations of the end consumer which influence their competitiveness are social constructs. Beyond the microenvironment, organisations highlight complementary social constructs as incubators for specific knowledge and determined by ethos, interior regulation, L&D, and above all, the specificity of job attribution under the affirmed strategic goals which are themselves influenced by the uniqueness of challenges. Therefore, both the reality (the retail industry) and knowledge (norms and challenges within an organisation) are social constructs, leading towards the pertinence of a Postmodernist philosophy. However, cognition is grounded on a subjective discernment of realities and acquisition of knowledge, thus calling for the Interpretivist research philosophy which is reasserted within the challenge of transitioning from a general to a specific context. Reasoning itself unfolds through repetition, indicating the pertinence of phenomenology which can also be used to understand the *modus operandi* exhibited by leaders in their everyday challenges. Phenomenology is argued by Souba (2014) to be the pathway to creating leaders as it is anchored in first-person confession case studies in contrast to teaching leadership as a discipline which draws upon case studies in a third-person approach. In leadership, phenomenology connects actions to results in real time. From such a perspective, phenomenology can only be detected in connection to the stabilisation phase experienced at the moment of the data collection. Phenomenology allows tracing the acquisition of knowledge from a holistic point of view, highlighting both contexts and tasks, as well as relational processes that facilitate new insights. Amassing an interior and exterior perspective, phenomenology allows the simultaneous study of both the individual (the leader) and the collective (the work group or the organisation). Through the lens of phenomenology, strategic thinking can be traced in its intentional, systemic, cultural, and behavioural dimensions (Küpers, 2007) Phenomenology supports the transtemporal approach demanded by the study of leadership, as well as its placement within hierarchical structures, as it can also highlight an inter-practice between reporting and influencing (Küpers, 2013) Covering influence as well as practice from a situational, integral, and relational point of view, phenomenology is particularly useful to understanding how leaders evolve from mentorship to coordination responsibilities (Fisher and Robbins, 2015) Furthermore, as Souba (2014) states, phenomenology allows the composing of a

portrait of the human being behind the leader and identifies the traits which allowed such evolution.

The research aim therefore demands the identification of deviations from a series of patterns developed under two key social constructs: the microenvironment and the organisational setting. Such deviations emerge themselves under the subjective interpretation of disturbances registered within the macroenvironment and the expected response to be attained from the organisational setting. The subjective interpretation is grounded on cumulative knowledge. Within strategic thinking, reality may take the form of estimations of various time spans -whether short, medium, or long term- with a different weight for different factors. Cumulative knowledge is present both as a foundation of the methodology, but also within the object of research. However, the first step is to identify the sources or the dimensions of the cumulative knowledge: 1. The personal experience 2. External information (public health policies and media reports) 3. The organisational culture 4. Directives passed across the hierarchical structures. Ratcliffe (2002) signals environmental scanning as a preparation phase for what he qualifies as a productive strategic conversation. The environmental scanning is delivered through a two pillared approach within my methodology: field notes and storytelling both fulfil this construction.

3.1.2 METHODOLOGY

3.1.2.1 The conceptual apparatus

The research aim can be constituted in three coordinates: one's life experience, one's strategic thinking and one's response to a crisis. The literature subsumes one's life experience into cumulative knowledge which also includes a discernment of the surrounding environment, both in its macro factors, as well as in its most immediate setting- that of one's role. Strategic thinking can be connected to the processes through which the cumulative knowledge is discerned in order for an individual to reach the goals they've set. Therefore, the coding strategy must be developed around two core coordinates: the cumulative knowledge and the cognition. However, both coordinates require further development into adjacent concepts. The literature review therefore demanded that I research the cognitive processes of strategic thinking, the knowledge discerned within them, the factors according to which they adjust, and the variations raised by the context.

3.1.2.1.1 The cognitive process of strategic thinking

Strategic thinking distinguishes itself from mere contemplation through its goal-oriented character. Cognitive processes are set in motion to deliver a targeted outcome. The general study of strategic thinking demands recreating its unfolding within which goal formulation stands as the foremost issue to investigate. However, goal formulation itself depends on a collection of data related to the external environment which is further analysed in accordance with the organisation's resources, competencies, and capabilities. In connection to goal formulation, strategic thinking targets identifying the limits to which the organisation can capitalise upon opportunities of the external environment and neutralise its threats. Goal formulation provides the rationale for strategic thinking, which must also be approached in connection to processes and vectors. Processes should not be regarded as a finite stage, but as a challenge to timely and effectively readjusted reasoning to new circumstances.

As highlighted across the literature review, studying strategic thinking implies tracing the sequence of cognitive processes, recreating its deployment and the knowledge affecting its deductions and reasoning. Cognitive processes and knowledge launch a synergy of inter-dependent components. To illustrate such an argument, I will focus on a brief reconstruction of the relationship between cognitive processes and knowledge. Cognitive processes are influenced by the awareness of risks which draw upon temperament but also on the knowledge attained through personal experience. Furthermore, cognitive processes may also be developed within the values prioritised by an individual when performing their role: either their tasks or their relationship with peers. However, the manner in which individuals position themselves in connection to tasks and peers is influenced by the code of practice connected to their job attributions, an external source of knowledge which they have assimilated and continue to affirm across their diligence.

3.1.2.1.2 Knowledge

Knowledge derives from both insights collected by individuals across their own personal experience, but also from the immediate and extended environments which influence how they perform their roles. The institutional settings within which they perform their tasks are essential

to acknowledge boundaries, since beyond general norms such as public health policies and the organisational code of practice, each department and each role imposes specific norms.

3.1.2.1.3 The macro-environment

Had my thesis not been based on the COVID-19 pandemic, the conceptual apparatus highlighted by the literature would have determined that I build my research design upon the deviations observed in the general deployment of strategic thinking under the impact of a crisis.

The unique nature of the COVID-19 pandemic, however, required a readjustment of the scope of my research from the general principles and strategies highlighted within crisis management.

Acknowledged by public health policies as an essential sector, the retail industry did not face the COVID-19 pandemic at the same order of magnitude. It did, however, experience different disruptive factors. The literature review also highlights the fundamental importance of the precedent which arose as the latent knowledge we regard under the idea of ‘intuition’.

The COVID-19 pandemic limits the approach of the precedent. The retail industry has not faced a similar pressure of outcomes during the COVID-19 pandemic as it may have faced as a threat during the 2008 Recession or during various large-scale food contamination crises. Under the COVID-19 pandemic the previous experience of crisis becomes irrelevant. As a core concept of the research, crisis management had to be approached from a general to a specific perspective.

The research methods should have ensured an elliptical approach that captures both the areas that highlight the general reasoning, as well as the areas that imposed such deviation.

3.1.2.2 Key directions for the translating of the conceptual apparatus in a research strategy

The COVID pandemic stands as a context that can accommodate a paradigm shift.

Understanding strategic thinking also implied reaching the cognitive patterns which had been abandoned and the framework replacing it. Much of this information was able to be assessed by the more unconventional methodologies employed in this study. The effects of the pandemic were wide-ranging and the measures to cope with it were in many ways unique and untried.

Pinpointing one method would be difficult.

The cognitive process could only be investigated by directly approaching decision makers and querying their reasoning. The individualised deployment of strategic thinking demands its study through qualitative research methods. However, cognition also exhibits an intimate dimension of which the individual may not be aware. Such peculiarity demands descending from qualitative methods to strategies and instruments through which participants could access and share reasoning patterns of which they are not necessarily aware. Therefore, the research strategy encouraged them towards a free conversation which could be delivered through a narrative inquiry.

Knowledge encompasses both an individual dimension as well as an external or objective component. The individual dimension draws upon personal experiences which can also be revealed through a research into the person's background and through direct querying. The objective knowledge, however, refers to the public health policies which highlight the necessity of integrating secondary data in the methodology, as well as to the organisational culture, which can be accessed through document analysis (code of practice, interior regulations) and through observation. Integrating public health policies within the research was demanded by the particular position in which the retail industry was placed by the emergency regulatory framework. It is the public health policies which endowed the retail industry with a privileged position, that of maintaining its operations, while also limiting its activity through stipulations such as the maximum number of people allowed in a store. Circumstances to which the cognitive patterns are adjusted include changes in public health policies, in the liaisons with external stakeholders, and in eventual mutations of how the workforce responds to changes in the organisational culture. The liaisons with external stakeholders can be found in secondary data, notably in media reports on logistic disruptions and consumer behaviour, but also in internal documents on the exact extent to which such phenomena affect operations. The mutations in how the workforce responds to changes in the organisational culture can be studied through observation.

Therefore, the research aim imposed a multi-method approach that synchronised secondary data, field notes, and interviews. Insights attained through the three methods are further triangulated to identify dependency relationships.

3.1.3 RESEARCH DESIGN

The research design integrates key concepts highlighted within literature to the peculiarities arising from the COVID-19 context, as experienced by the retail sector on a primary level and by society overall on a secondary level. Elements to which the research design had to be adapted include the organisational setting, notably its structure, functions, culture, and eventual dependencies arising from synergies with its stakeholders. However, data collection was also adapted to the specificity of every role- its authority, and its reporting responsibilities. The practical applications to which I aspired was obtaining findings that could become the foundation of new leadership tools that could be applied beyond this study. The study stands out as both organisational as well as interorganisational, as it aims to place strategic thinking in synergy with how decisions can be integrated or may affect a business model, but also with how a company's micro and macroenvironment, particularly in a national crisis, influence cognition in its key people.

The approached methodology employs a triangulation between the primary data obtained from storytelling interviews and field notes with and a set of secondary data accounting for public written statements from the industry, underpinned by the literature. The interdisciplinary approaches propagated by Guercini (2014) highlights community study and phenomenology as appropriate for field notes and biography and detective journalism as interview strategies.

3.1.3.1 SECONDARY DATA

Secondary data collection implied connecting the public communication issued by the studied organisation to public health policies and official statement of high-profile Government representatives (the Prime Minister, the Health Secretary, et al). Initial impressions stood out as concerns related to the virus began to be expressed on an overall society level even before the official Government lockdown measures had been enacted (Emerson et al, 1995). The selection of notes further followed the deployment of Government measures with various stages of consumer behaviour, from stockpiling to the shift to online orders, to compliance. The first significant data emerged from supply forecasts, whereas the key decision – makers 'reaction to the frontline staff shortage stood out as the first unexpected occurrences to be inscribed.

3.1.3.2 PRIMARY DATA

The challenge of studying variations from an individual's general reasoning to the discernment of a context establishes the research strategy through which I would address decision makers. Directly querying over these variations raises a series of limitations which may compromise data validity and reliability. The first such limitation comes from the unconscious dimension upon which humans readjust their cognition. The second such limitation tendency is in intellectualising answers when reflection of one's choices is demanded, whereas if the same reflective process would emerge in a different context, it may provide different causalities. Therefore, my challenge in data collection was to identify the most appropriate strategy through which I could determine an open participation which had been passed through as few filters as possibly. Narrative inquiry stood out as the most effective technique to conduct the qualitative research.

Narrative analysis is defined as a sequence of events that have occurred in an individual's life that are gathered for research purposes through the method of storytelling in order to understand and explain social patterns (Thomas, 2012).

Stories can be regarded as a universal language and allow researchers to investigate elements of the human psyche, discover the meaning of human existence and appraise our own individual purpose within it (Brooker 2004). Using narrative inquiry means that the researcher is able to gain valuable and close insights into the personal experiences of an individual within situations and their perspectives on events. This may mean within a particular time frame or could range over an extended period of time or sequence of events.

The scope of narrative research is to identify the sense the interviewee makes of various events that they have experienced and of their response to such stimuli. If not affirmed as goals, one's own motivations are unlikely to be disclosed or reflected in their behaviour. Attempts to infer such stimuli only lead to speculation. As they cannot be identified by observation or case study, an accurate perspective on motivation requires purposed inquiry.

Importing concepts of various disciplines, narrative inquiry fluctuates between theoretical and practical knowledge. In strategic thinking, such input converges towards management, leadership, market forecast, consumer behaviour, game theory and financial analysis. Beyond the stricto sensu interpretation of a content, the stylistic analysis of narratives can decrypt deeper

meanings for the interviewee within the persistence of details, analogies or even metaphors. Nevertheless, the time dedicated to covering an event can bring the same input.

Storytelling transfers tacit knowledge drives self-assessment, and consequently challenges a personal vision of identity. Concurrently, in strategic thinking knowledge can transpire either in relation to experience, by configuring actions to the handling of familiar occurrences or as an expression of self-efficacy. According to Kevill et al (2015), life story interview can also fulfil the narrative of an organisation, therefore the retailer's performance throughout the lockdown period illustrates strategic thinking in the leadership of its decision makers and can provide a case study on business models in retail.

Findings from the narrative inquiry had also been confronted with the data collected through observation. Though the COVID-19 virus has been present in the public discourse since December 2019, it had not been a part of the formal communication or the informal conversations since the beginning of March. Changes of attitude and concerns could become the object of field notes starting from March. Data collection continued across the First Wave, though within the limitations imposed by Zoom meetings.

A personal participation within the execution of decisions issued through strategic thinking provides an omniscient point of view for the present fieldnotes (Emerson, 1995). Since the immediate proximity to decision makers allows a contextualization, as Van Maanen points out, fieldwork favours theorization efforts by offering the premise to understand others, notably, to decode strategic thinking. Further, also according to Van Maanen (Hammar, 1991), fieldwork in strategic thinking in retail generally entails amassing the observations conducted within an organizational ecosystem. However, the observation acquires sense once explained by confessional tales (Hammar, 1991) which describe the execution of decisions issued by leaders who complement the research in storytelling interviews.

3.2 Sample selection

The research aims called for the study leaders, allowing me full freedom over the hierarchical levels from which I would select my interviewees. The COVID-19 context-imposed change was on an external level, beyond the organisation's hierarchical levels. The core argument for a sample

selection across hierarchical levels is based upon the influence of authority variations which 1. Limits a leader's participation in decision making 2. Highlights a mediation role since each person has to ensure the transmission of rules to their own subordinates. Such confluence between a limited authority before a leader's own superiors and their responsibilities before their own team highlights a unique impact on strategic thinking. The effectiveness to which change is implemented across hierarchical levels depends on how leaders integrate the awareness of a limited authority, the discernment of how the new rules would directly affect their workgroup's responsibilities, and the empathy which would dictate how information is transmitted.

A sample of 20 was chosen as being large enough to be inclusive and represent a range of experiences but small enough to be manageable for a qualitative project. The sample selection has been calculated in connection to the approximate number of 40 individuals composing the organisation's senior management who can be regarded as the target population (Saunders et al, 2018, p.295). The 20 leaders are representative of the areas of the business where strategic thinking would be apparent in decision making processes, particularly in a crisis. By synthesising different roles and responsibilities through narratives collected from various members of the organisation, the image of change in all its dimensions can be completed, thus highlighting fractures, and providing a critical survey of leadership though the impact of all decisions and how Covid-19 impacted the business model as well as the lives and decision-making skills of all the retailer's staff concerned. The extended job attributions and the members' reaction to their new assignments had been prioritised when elaborating notes on the interviewee Observations came from the intermediary position between implementation and execution.

Participants have been selected to cover the implementation of strategy through correlated roles which are horizontally distributed within the organisation's hierarchy, as well as according to key activities and liaisons within the supply chain. Roles fulfilled by the interviewees cover competencies assigned to deliver the organisation's proactive response to the impact of a disruptive environment. Participants with a direct contribution to the implementation of strategy include Nick (Head of B2B Strategy), Josee (Change and Implementation Manager), Jim (Strategy Manager), Sara (Head of Future Brands), and Katya (Category Manager). Participants whose roles can be placed along the supply chain include Jack (Operations Manager B2B), Erin (Client Director), Randall (Operations Manager), Ardeen (Export Manager), Tommie (Fulfilment Manager), Antony (Supply Chain and Logistics Lead), Peter and Natalia (both Buying Managers). Liaisons with

suppliers falls into the competencies of Russ (Head of Sales and Wholesale Buying), Cedric (Supplier Support), Stefania (Buying Manager), Francene (Account Manager), and Terri (Senior Account Manager). Participants in immediate contact with the end consumer include Rocky (Convenience Store Manager). Melanie is the only interviewee who at the moment of the research had already left the organisation.

Table 1. Participants list

Participant number	Pseudonym	Title	Gender and age interval	Referred by participant
1	Jack Hartley	Operations Manager	Male / 30+	0-not interviewed
2	Russ Law	Head of Sales and Wholesale Buying	Male / 30+	1
3	Cedric Lowe	Supplier Communication Manager	Male / 50+	2
4	Melanie Moss	Commercial Manager	Female /30+	3
5	Rocky Padilla	Head of Convenience Stores	Male / 40+	4
6	Erin Estrada	Client Director	Female /30+	5
7	Randall Binder	Operations Manager	Male / 50+	6
8	Stefania Saporta	Senior Buying Manager	Female /30+	7
9	Francene Yamada	Account Manager	Female /30+	8
10	Josee Gillogley	Change and Implementation Manager	Male / 40+	9

11	Ardeen Krouse	Exports Manager	Female /30+	10
12	Tommie Valachovic	Fulfilment Operations Manager	Male / 40+	11
13	Peter Espinosa	Buying Manager	Male / 40+	12
14	Natalia Colman	Category Manager	Female /40+	13
15	Antony Jones	Supply Chain and Logistics Lead	Male / 50+	14
16	Terri Babbage	Senior Account Manager	Male / 30+	15
17	Jim Fata	Strategy Manager	Male / 30+	16
18	Nick Hudson	Head of Strategy	Male / 40+	17
19	Sara	Head of Future Brands	Female /40+	18
20	Katya Francis	Category Manager	Female /40+	19

3.3 Data collection

The diagram below explains how the data analysis has been approached and coded. The literature review highlighted a conceptual apparatus to be applied as the universal codes against which the collected data had been juxtaposed. As the participants recommended one another, before the interview conducted, a preliminary research was conducted in regards to the respondents' role attributions which shall constitute individual characteristics. Such particular circumstances had been continuously confronted with the conceptual apparatus descending from the literature review as well as with the specific data which found relevant.

The first step after collecting the data was to write the transcripts of the interview. On the transcripts it was highlighted and extracted the data found relevant, while synonyms and phrases with similar meanings for insightful phrases or expressions were separated. After each read, the context in which the extracted data has been mentioned to verify whether they can be assimilated

to the identified codes was revisited. Whether the synonyms can be attributed the same sense has been an additional concern. The main themes which also confirmed codes emerged by juxtaposing to data extracted from other interviewees. The focus was on identifying generic information more likely to generate commonalities. New codes would emerge only if the specific data extracted from each interviewee highlights commonalities (like the case of the military background). Insightful traits or accounts which didn't converge towards commonalities were to be addressed in the Discussion chapter.

Figure 5. Data analysis approach

(Microsoft Excel, 2023)

As signalled by Emerson (1995) et al, initial impressions were produced upon the raised general awareness of the virus which preceded the enactment of the official Government lockdown measures. Scrutiny of all possible directives to complement obvious data worth noting as significant has been constantly required for the study. Variations of such emerging patterns of decision making underwent the same assessment, and notes played their part (Emerson,1995).

The duration of the data collection was 6 months from the pilot interview to completion starting on 1st March 2021. Due to Covid-19 challenges and limitations, the initial planning for this phase of the research was heavily impacted and most of the interviews have been postponed and rescheduled multiple times. For convenience, face-to-face interviewing (in the form of Microsoft Team video calls) has been favoured in the unmatched data quality (Schober, 2018) elevated by paralinguistic and nonverbal communication.

Data collection through field notes had been, however, heavily affected by the transition towards remote working which removed the opportunity of a physical setting favouring observation. To a limited extent field notes had been maintained over eventual changes of attitude exhibited by my colleagues throughout our virtual group meetings. Nevertheless, in order to attain an exhaustive perspective over how the pandemic has impacted the organisation across hierarchical structures, I have also collected field notes from retail units I could visit within the limits of public health policies.

The data collection strategy implied inviting participants to recommend leaders within the organisation whom they might find relevant to the research. The choice of the first interviewee (Jack) was based on a recommendation from another leader which the researcher had direct professional experience with. The researcher had no opposition to the participant suggestions of additional interviewees. All interviews have been conducted via Microsoft Teams, participants being previously informed over the duration (40 - 60 minutes) of their intervention. A debrief and a consent form had been priorly sent to them to introduce them to both the research aim, as well as the deployment of the interview. Participants were requested to confirm their consent both at the beginning, as well as the end of the interview.

3.3.1 SECONDARY DATA

The main source of secondary data was the UK Government's own channels. The public health statutory framework included both safety measures which could affect the organisation's operations, as well as eventual custom restrictions for imports and exports which could have impacted the supply chain. An evolution of the virus as reported by World Data allowed anticipating eventual mutations in the number and rhythm of infestations and deaths. Such data could have influenced both public health policies as well as issues related to consumer behaviour.

A perspective on the organisation as a system demanded that I also maintain focus on the official position of industry bodies that cover key external stakeholders such as transporters and representatives agriculture. Nevertheless, benchmarking imposed the need to follow all official statements issued by competitors.

3.3.2 FIELDNOTES

My research aim set the expectations according to which I assessed the facts which I would further record as field notes (Wolfinger, 2002): the time difference between the first concerns informally expressed within the organisation in connection to the virus and the official issuance of leadership decisions (1), the difference in the internal communication between the general decisions and those adopted within a moment of crisis (2), the speed with which they were implemented (4), the stakeholders involved (5), any additional insight transpiring from the overall process (6). The perceived audience also influenced this selection (Squire, 2008).

Notes included not only a descriptive dimension of facts, but also an interpretative component focused on any distinctive variations of the process through which decisions were issued and implemented on the overall organisation. Such meta-commentary was particularly useful in the line-by-line review (Emerson, 1995) which allowed for extending the initial themes and connecting my findings with theories.

Jotted notes had been elaborated on spontaneously whenever aligned to information that would determine a reassessment of strategy, such as in the case of Government announcements. Issued almost immediately with each key momentum, direct observation was reassessed after every day of work, thus, once having left the field. Such review allowed a better integration of the momentum within the dynamics of the day and, further, within the general overview. Interface was focused mostly on codes that may emerge (including communication terms) and how quickly they were adopted by the team. A personal journal followed a critical view on disparities that may have occurred between three major identities: my position as a member of the organisation, the deontological objectivity as a researcher, and my daily challenges as a target consumer of the exact

organisation that I belonged to as a professional and that I was scrutinising as a researcher (Neuman, 2011).

3.3.3 STORYTELLING INTERVIEWS

The methodology chosen for the study was that of the unstructured interview, as it provided the most insightful pathway towards findings that are not pre-determined. The unstructured formulation of questions was juxtaposed with the creative interviewing proposed by Douglas (1985) since the research was interested not in the respondents' actions, but in the processes behind them. According to Ratcliffe (2002), in unstructured interviews the agenda becomes the privilege of the interviewee rather than interviewer, which was an integral part of the purpose of the study. In essence, unstructured interviewing is favoured both for individualisation, as well as for adaptability (Ratcliffe, 2002).

It is important to note that unstructured interviews are not necessarily passive on the part of the interviewer. Much of this information would not have been forthcoming in a more formal and directed interview situation. Furthermore, the interviews also counted on the prerogative to ask questions or whatever guidance they found helpful to sketch their intervention. Across the interviews, I encouraged the interviewees towards controlling the narrative, reassuring them that every detail they wished to provide was welcome and valuable.

The seven-questions approach (Simons, 2010) becomes relevant in terms of the interviewee's approach to knowledge of the future and how they would take advantage of this insight, but also their perception of limitations and reaction to a restrictive context. According to Simons (2010) execution demands identifying the primary customer (1), acknowledging the values they prioritise (2), formulating performance goals (3), setting strategic boundaries (4), assessing the limits to which one can create an environment to generate innovation (5), reflecting upon how productive inter-peer collaboration may be (6), and detecting the strategic uncertainties challenging one (7). The interviewees' perception of extended limitations could be reintroduced through an indirect inquiry.

The open-ended interview is not prescriptive in its questioning. In fact, the aim was to have very little formal questioning, and to grow responses organically through the discussion.

Narrative research should further, according to Kevill et al (2015) accommodate the 'stick of twist' alternative interview methods. Therefore, the hypothetical unfolding of each question imposes different key points to be considered for a possible succession of further questions. Whatever the direction revealed within the respondent's participation, a set of guiding directions will be held as an axis towards which narration will be led on any given opportunity such as a break between ideas. In the present study, the unfolding of each interview would be organic, and minimal questioning and intervention would give the opportunity for free expression and unfolding of ideas and personal stories. Such a proactive approach reduces the risk of ambiguous information which can be further distorted through a biased interpretation, but also facilitates an extensive description of facts by introducing additional angles or anchors which can lead to the unveiling of more triggers within cognitive mechanisms.

3.4 DATA ANALYSIS

Data analysis was also extended towards accommodating angles from other disciplines. The sense of affiliation is credited as an identity-determinant variable. How a person envisions themselves in connection to their group and organisation may hold sway in strategic thinking, should it import upon decision making the perception of responsibility for one's collective. The sense of affiliation calls towards community study. As previously mentioned, one of the key concerns of my research was detecting variations in the leaders' cognitive patterns under the influence of crises as external stimuli. However, the mere question of variations demands detecting the person's default cognitive pattern. Repetitive manifestations are best studied by phenomenology which also proved a bountiful terrain in examining peer influence. As a research method for social sciences, biography resolves questions regarding the actual relevance of structured personal experiences such as social and family background as variables for strategic thinking. Furthermore, biography allows individualisation and thus, detecting findings outside of research assumptions.

As highlighted by Pauchant (2005) biographies encompass a three-method design themselves, as they place leadership into a micro, meso and macro approach. Attainable through interpretative biography, the micro perspective considers the individual in connection to traits, influences, and other insights that may arise from their own career path. The meso perspective employs an institutional analysis which explores their input and influence over their work group or organisation. Grounded on historical inquiry, the macro dimension allows understanding of how societal, or industry change affects an individual's choice regarding their career. Self-narratives are included amongst biographical methods, which, when applied in leadership, highlight two key perspectives: breadth and depth. Breadth refers to the dimensions incorporated in a leader's life, such as the organisational function they serve, the limits to their authority, their responsibilities, the company culture, seniority within the company, experience in a leadership position, and their team. The depth, however, is particularly related to the individual circumstances such as their own career trajectory, personal experiences, and any defining aspects to their cognition and behaviour (Cunha et al, 2017).

3.4.1 METHODOLOGICAL ISSUES

The interviews were manually transcribed based on the video recordings and the coding was executed in NVivo. The data collected is very rich in details and unique by its nature, hence the significant number of codes obtained after the indexing process. The first methodological challenge in data analysis implied connecting findings from all three methods employed. The secondary data collection produced both numeric, as well as nominal data. Numeric data arises from statistics concerning both the industry (sales figures, predictions, delays, etc), as well as the overall society (number of contaminations and deaths). Nominal data can be extracted from policies and official statements. Deggs and Hernandez (2018) emphasised purposeful reflection on the context provided by the secondary data, and an assessment of efficiency and strategic thinking, all synchronised within causalities; a further concern was objectivity and selection of data for the research log, all validated through triangulation. Nevertheless, data analysis raises a key challenge in aligning findings extracted from all accounts. On such grounds, I have focused on an issue raised by Auvinen (2012) who pointed out how scholarly efforts usually focus on the

leader and neglect leadership. The abstraction from a real person must be developed in the direction of elevating accounts towards an organizational storytelling. In such spirit, I will focus on milestone stages such as becoming a leader, building resilience in an institutional setting and resistance and career transition points which can also go beyond the organisation.

All registered data has been placed within a regulatory context that encompassed both the statutory background imposed upon the overall industry, but also the internal directives through which these norms had been translated on an organisational level. Such an approach allowed for counteracting of the tickle-up marginalisation (Pacheco-Vega, 2019) which may be installed through the receivers of leadership decisions who hold on to the preconceptions that strategic thinking is their superiors' duty and responsibility and not their own.

Hybridization integrates findings of quantitative research as argument for variables to be inserted or not. Therefore, secondary data provided the first set of variables within which to formulate eventual questions which could appear pertinent in connection to the interviewees' accounts. Even if the necessity of introducing such questions did not arise, the variables extracted from the secondary data facilitated the classification of data related to the interviewee's position towards the pandemic.

Fieldwork in strategic thinking in retail generally entails amassing the observations conducted within an organisational ecosystem. The realistic approach of observation reached regarding the mutations registered in the new organisational norms, such as the new internal regulations and job assignments. However, observation also accommodated an interpretative perspective that measured objectivization in terms of the headquarter staff's receptivity and promptness in undergoing change. The study stands out as both organisational as well as interorganisational. The organisational dimension focuses on how decisions can be integrated or affect a business model. The inter organisational dimension, however, covers the synergies developed around strategic thinking in connection to the company's micro and macroenvironment, particularly in a national crisis.

The intersection between the realistic and the interpretative approach on observation elevated both the general topic for the thematic narrative, but also the incentive for strategic thinking. Fieldnotes are employed to provide the details (Hammar, 1991) for fleshing out these vectors.

Field notes complemented narration, as jotting also allowed capturing attitudes that might detect spontaneity, impulsiveness, pressure, calm, predetermination and connect such reactions to the roles and contributions of each party involved in decision making (Emerson, 1995). Field notes also allowed following the strategic conversation transpiring from the members' daily interactions, which influence their cognition without them becoming aware of (Ratcliffe, 2002).

The research aim converges towards the identification of a cognitive pattern among respondents. Observation was directed towards the stimuli which activated and maintained these patterns. However, such observations should integrate confessional tales (Hammar, 1991) describing the execution of decisions issued by leaders, whether by the interviewees themselves or their hierarchical superiors. However, establishing the mechanisms of strategic thinking demanded that each real-time field note be revised within the end-point approach by attaching possible retrospective interpretations. According to Wolfinger (2002), assessment is conducted according to the researcher's own expectations and knowledge in the form of note taking. This results in selection, which will have an immense impact on the final findings, as data is collected according to its importance to the understanding of a phenomenon. Observation notes are a first reflection when reviewed in front of a writing machine. Wolfinger (2002) suggests that assessment should be directed towards the order in which data is noted.

The cognitive mechanisms supporting strategic thinking entail two of the narrative analysis approaches suggested by Squire (2008). Therefore, the data analysis should encompass semantics -of which I would extract the content- and pragmatics, through which I will get an overview of the context. As pointed out by Cunliffe (2008) crossing over from field notes to storytelling interview as forms of narrative research requires a transition from expectations on the rigour of allowing findings to be appropriated. Lieblich (2003) points out the difficulties in systemising narrative findings, which stands out as the researcher's task, as such data rejects the premise of an absolute truth or the argument of only one valid form of textual interpretation.

The concept of historical present (Perrino, 2011) facilitated access to the variations in the cognitive patterns I was interested in. The historical present can highlight two chronotypes, notably the time from recollections filtered through today's detachment and the there-and-then perspective which is more likely to be eloquent for the person's default cognitive processes. In contrast, the now-and-

here perspective allows detection of how the experience of going through the pandemic has shaped the usual thinking pattern.

3.4.2 PRINCIPLES USED IN INTERPRETATION

Respondents were informed at the beginning of the interview that they had complete liberty on both the topics they wished to address, as well as on the sequence in which they could be inserted. At times when the respondents considered their depiction of a moment as complete and were uncertain of the direction or topic, they were reassured of their prerogative of full control over the confessional with the short and informal sentence ‘it’s up to you’, so they would not feel any pressure or influence. No additional data could be extracted from an eventual interpretation of a chosen order of events in recollection, as all respondents opted for a chronological sequence. The research aim obliged me to exclusively focus on processes and to exclude outcomes within deduction and correlations. According to the same principles, goals have not been approached under their content, but under their influence as incentive, and any attempt at ordering stakes in terms of possible importance was rejected as basic for speculation. Individual circumstances such as a mixed heritage or an international upbringing, as well as significant periods of time spent living and working in other countries will not be used for arguments within deduction of interaction terms and interaction effects but scrutinised to explore whether they form common patterns. The profoundly individual character of primary data obtained through narrative inquiry obliged correlating recollections to variables such as goals, context, risks, etc. Their attributed influence and considered impact, as transpiring from the participants’ statements are further placed in their distinctive context such as the life stage the recollection is connected to, the respondents’ familiarity to the background factors considered within that particular episode, or whether decision making has been conducted in a regular context or in one of crisis. In such a longitudinal approach, the focus on process is directed towards identifying variations within cognition under a different scaling of perhaps the same coordinates. The longitudinal perspective on every respondent’s account showed no contradiction between arguments anchored in recollections and no logical fractures. Polarities, if introduced (toxic vs inspiration leaders) are coherent.

No contrasts between accounts and the tone used in the narrative have been noticed. Changes of tone could be observed in recollections that produce grief, joy, or nostalgia. Analysis and previsions are introduced in a contemplative tone, indicating the respondents' efforts to make sense of the context upon which they are challenged to bring a prognosis. Situations in which the respondent is facing furlough after a lifelong career in the organisation are related with heartfelt emotion.

Discontinuities or disruptions have been rather connected to the respondents' desire to add more details to introduce new depictions related to the subject (momentum, person, etc) in order to reiterate their argument. No hesitation could be noted.

No repetitive insertion of events could be noted, whereas a second mention of a previously covered topic (ex: grief, parenthood, education) is limited to attempts to explain or deliver a context for the momentum described.

“I don't wanna be stuck up in a workshop for four weeks doing a refit when I've got this daughter at home, but I wanted to see so that at that point there was an opportunity for me to go into the Space team. This is about 2004 so...”

None of the respondent used their own person or their corresponding contribution as leading direction in depicting moments that they considered important for decision making or crisis management. Such accounts were described having a main focus on the magnitude or exceptional deployment of external factors causing that particular context, as well as on the consensus and complementarities within teamwork. If applying correspondences proposed by Lieblich (2003) between narration and literary criticism, responses fall into the comedy genre, as the narrator is concerned with the skills used to counteract disruption, connected to particular interventions in teamwork.

Political references are neutral, respondents refraining themselves from criticising the Government. Mentions of national restrictions are strictly given to provide a context.

McAdams' scheme of deconstructing the memories of personal events is found in the overall composition of each of the respondents' contribution. Every individual intervention includes reproduction of advice given to them (the message component), contemplation on events described

as lessons (the symbolic dimensions), catalysts for affinities and experiences that have reconfirmed a chosen path, and moments which the respondent assimilate as patterns.

3.4.3 INTEGRATING THE RESEARCHER'S INITIAL ASSUMPTIONS

Ratcliffe (2002) mentions the absence of a priori classification as a core feature of an unstructured interview. However, for methodological reasons, categories should not be overlooked as they may attract answers which converge towards the confirmation or invalidation of assumptions, whereas spontaneous occurring data can place findings in a more comprehensive setting.

Narration intervenes with the recreation of contextualised strategies in the most exhaustive approach to demonstrate cognitive patterns (Emerson, 1995). However, beyond the themes I have initially selected, accounts highlight some additional ones. Confessional tales have been framed within the parallel proposed by Lieblich (2003) between the initial impressions I have noted within my research and those to be developed during the process. Exceptions encountered as a listener will be linked to my own position, as inhabited in confessional tales to the actual content of the narrative.

Emerson (1995) provides guidelines for notes: the salience theory or comprehensive note taking theory provides that it is highly descriptive of the person about to be mentioned, their role, the supposed intention and meaning of their words or statements, the rationale behind their actions whether present or future. The observer should also embark on speculation as to the outcome of these actions but be concerned with the consequences of various alternative scenarios.

3.4.4 CONNECTING TO THE INTERVIEWEE'S SUBJECTIVITY

Of all considered research methods, non-structured interviews allow the best adjustment to the respondents' own rhythm and involvement. Nevertheless, a spontaneous development of the interview may be assimilated to an informal conversation and thus, inspire a high participation of the respondents.

Through its subjective (Kevill et al, 2015) input, life story interviewing benefits the research by granting access to one's personal perspective in the language of analogies, memories, recurrent themes, and any other elements that allow conceptualisation, thus tracking the cognitive processes behind strategic thinking.

A notable novelty element in this research is the opportunity given to the respondents to structure their own interview. The highly introspective exploration targeted through storytelling demands a focus on form, notably on the logic behind the sequence of events and the narrator's own position before the evoked cognitive process (Lieblich, 2003).

McAdams provides a scheme of deconstructing personal event memories into five essential guidelines: messages to have marked the narrator to the extent in which they manage an explicit or approximate reproduction, the symbolic dimension attributed by the narrator when contemplating upon an experience which they refer to as a lesson, momentums that the narrator remembers as incentives for affinities, mindsets or other milestones, events that consolidate or reaffirm a previously embraced path, interest or beliefs and events that the narrator perceives as replicating previous experiences and therefore establishing a pattern.

As Ratcliffe (2002) points out, the respondent's hidden assumptions must not be neglected as answers are articulated to either fulfil them or avoid them. Beyond established parameters which may confirm a Red Amber Green (RAG) level reporting for a crisis, essential concepts which can be appropriated as variables for cognitive mechanisms may accommodate subjective interpretations. Richard Thaler mentions overconfidence to illustrate biases influencing mindset. The research should not neglect incentives making respondents confident. Furthermore, the COVID pandemic context should indicate whether the potential profits increase generated by panic shopping stood as a reason for overconfidence.

In the terrain of paraverbal communication, omissions or futile mentions may be as eloquent, as highlighted by Lieblich (2003).

3.4.5 REVIEWS

Patterns become visible once transcripts are studied several times with patience, equidistance, and empathy, as recommended by Lieblich (2003). They may strike the reader as recurrent topics, such as when they transpire from various confessions or in conjunction with the context. The place

within the narrative and the logical deductions which appear in relation to the immediate vicinity of accounts will only add a more exhaustive understanding of the topic. Contradictions of the identified themes are submitted to the same survey.

Selection will have an immense impact on the final findings, and data is collected according to its import to the understanding of a phenomenon. Comprehensive note-taking pushes towards order and a timeline while the salience theory allows for deviant cases which fall outside of the observer's expectations. Criticism of tacit knowledge fuels the illusion of certainty when eliminating data in the research log. Though upon selection, these elements may appear too mundane to be preserved, they may be further confirmed as providing the guiding contrasts that highlight key deviant cases - an important component of the new.

Once a topic of interest had been identified, the next step demanded reviewing its dynamics and mutations throughout the narrative, granting a special focus to the repetitive insertion of events and the shifts in details which are recalled within each mention (Lieblich, 2003). Code memos proved fundamental for identifying algorithms. Integrative memos highlighted the hypothetical and logical connections. Assessing possible such synergies should not exclude pairings of data that do not seem complementary. Differences, whether incompatibilities and oppositions should be given the same consideration as variations that may invalidate patterns and should themselves be submitted to assessment and contextualisation. The mere goal of identifying a pattern requires accuracy and not approximations; therefore, integrative memos were revised as soon as sub codes began to stand out (Deggs & Hernandez, 2018).

The line-by-line review proposed by Emerson (1995) proved vital in an unpredictable cognitive terrain. Emerson (1995) describes an ethnographer's conclusions as encompassing a review of both findings, as well as themes, reaffirming the thesis in an extended or reassessed version that could highlight a common terrain with any existing theories. An additional direction may stand in a meta-commentary. Timelines are very much in the narrative vein and encapsulate an impulse towards order and storytelling and progressive chronology.

Butina (2015) suggests a follow-up session that completes the initial interview with possible clarifications of the perspectives exhibited throughout the answers. Only one of the respondents agreed to such a session.

3.4.6 CLASSIFICATION

The theoretical basis of narrative inquiry is found in the three dimensions identified by Dewey in accounts: situational, temporal, and relational. The situational component is found especially in the respondents' self-positioning to the COVID-19 crisis, but also in accounts related to projects or experiences they might regard as milestones in their career. The temporal component is highlighted in the respondents' choice of momentums that could stand as eloquent for their becoming, the time span they have chosen (whether from their childhood years or from their first professional experience), and the span during which they consider inserting new milestones. The relational component arises from liaisons they regard as fundamental to their evolution, whether positive or negative.

Previous applications of storytelling interviews in leadership highlight accounts converging organically towards six key areas. Trust represents the cardinal aspect through which leaders recollect their own path, equally focussing on their efforts in gaining their own superior's confidence as well as on the virtues their own teams must demonstrate in order to attain credibility before them. The six main areas according to which leaders reflect upon their path include motivation (in connection to both incentives as well as self-encouragement techniques), inspiration (from credos to professional references), defusing conflict (prevention and mediation strategies), influencing superiors (from mentorship to toxic relationships), discovering a focus (from identifying opportunities to goal formulation) and constructing trust (across hierarchical levels) (Auvinen et al, 2013).

According to James Walsh, as cited by Pellegrino & Carbo (2001), influences on strategic thinking echo various personal attributes, group affiliation, roles within an organisation and reactions to industry dynamics. Any study of strategic thinking requires tracking and deciphering the cognitive simplification deductions employed in assimilating data into stimuli and incentives. Decoding strategic thinking would be rather favoured by a holistic than a categorial approach, as the research aim is focused on an individual's own cognitive process and not on a phenomenon which may be replicated by various people. Consequently, categories arise from the participants' own input.

The analysis process of non-structured interviews guarantees individualisation, allowing the insertion of new concepts such as those related to upbringing, career reconversion or extra-

professional commitments that have shaped one's mindset and enhanced leadership skills. An additional aspect requiring clarification concerns the spontaneous unfolding of questions which adjust the operating concepts to information provided by the interviewee.

Storytelling will inevitably advance narrative on different levels (Squire 2008), starting with the co-constructed depictions of events as naturally assembled through the course of the conversation. Furthermore, each event may connect different independent stories which the narrator could have drawn upon to make decisions. The narrator can also link various influences on their decision to analogies of biographical details which, though outside of professional duties, still transmit empirically acquired knowledge. Strictly attainable through details, stage-based contextualisation is the sine qua non requirement in detecting a pattern, which had been targeted as a thesis for the thematic narration. Themes composing the narration highlighted their own conceptualisation, further supporting the identified patterns and grounding potential algorithms. Kevill et al, 2015 argue that there is no consensus over the methodology that should be used in life story interviewing for business related disciplines. The suggested use of chapters can favour research by providing a direction to the narrative. Reaching an exhaustive character analysis targeted through the scrutiny of strategic thinking demands integration of aspects such as influences, selection processes, efficiency estimations, accounted feasibility, predicted peer support and risk assessment. However, the chapter-based approach may be confirming a higher efficiency in letting the interviewee lead their approach on each chapter and having the researcher occasionally intervene. Chapter demarcations can be established by the narrators themselves. My first challenge was to assess the key momentum to switch between the focused and the analytical coding.

Recommended for recording a mimetic, conscious behaviour, focused coding stood out as suitable for the later stages of data collection in a context in which the entire organisation was accustomed to its new norms. However, spontaneous reactions to the first impact of the crisis demanded analytical coding which also allowed extracting algorithms from the decision makers' response (Emerson, 1995). Cohesiveness within storytelling is confirmed when momentums can be connected without disparities. When tracking strategic thinking, cohesiveness should display progressive and derived causalities between external incentive and a monitored flow of reactions which are articulated in such a manner that limits the risk of hyperactivating stockpiling as an uncontrollable variable. Lieblich (2003) point out how the plot's dynamics elevates further points

of scrutiny in the demarcation the interviewee chooses for separating each stage of their experience and the expressions they use in describing their path. The structure (Lieblich, 2003) in which the interviewee chooses to align causalities should be considered as much as the impulse to arrange events along a timeline. (Goldman, 2012). In connection to the context, the deployment stages identified by (Garcia, 2013), notably the imposed transformation, the transition generated, and its concrete implementation, could also be identified.

Beyond everyday leadership challenges, my true focus was identifying changes which may emerge in crisis situations where empirical research reveals gender, class, and profession as more accurate attributes in behavioural predictions (Mitchell, 2003). Surveying the possibility of extracting algorithms between stimuli and reactions employed analytically coding fieldnotes (Emerson, 1995) which crystallised categories and launched various valid logical connections between them. Analytically coding is favoured above focussed coding as its task is to detect a cognitive pattern in spontaneous reactions in contrast to mimetic, conscious behaviours for which the latter approach would have been more suitable. The pandemic became an external vector in society and in the story of the company. External vectors fulfil the role of analytic points, where the strategies responding to augmented market demands provided the descriptive excerpts. Orienting information came from the stockpiling behaviour as influenced by the official Governmental announcements and the background noise distinguished in the legitimate media coverage of the pandemic at home and in other parts of Europe, in the continuous assessment of World meter statistics and even through the exposure to conspiracy theories. The descriptive excerpts were the product of dependent, independent, or uncontrollable variables which opened new terrains for commentary (Emerson, 1995). The key directions arising from data classification which will provide the basis for the coding strategy include:

3.4.6.1 RELATIONAL KNOWLEDGE

Accepting multiple angles on reality, postmodernism also adheres to the thesis of a relative truth, filtered out of social interactions. Social interactions expand the spectrum of vectors that can act upon strategic thinking, both towards retrospection, by employing various references ranging

from mentorships to confrontations, as well as towards projection, by the inevitable speculations over the outcome of one's actions.

Kevill et al (2015) also advise that narrative research should be detached from any existing knowledge over strategic thinking and focus on the relational dimension grounding decision making. Such an approach leads outside the organisational environment towards the multitude of social relationships which can impact one's life. Relational knowledge can occur in strategic thinking either as a translation instrument, as empiric familiarity or as any other analogy to be discovered as finding.

Cross-sectional interviews conducted by Peet (2012) with two different generations of leaders indicate how core competencies have been transmitted through mentorship. My focus as a researcher was to separate the influence that my interviewees acknowledge and praise when evoking referential figures in their professional life from the values they strive to inspire amongst their own teams.

The focus on relational knowledge is particularly useful for pointing out interconnectivity and responsiveness in times of crisis.

3.4.6.2 LEADESHIP STYLES

The literature highlighted leadership styles as one's personal approach to goals and the human components engaged in their acquisition. The core dimension of leadership styles is found in one's approach towards command, including a vision of authority, motivation, and the concrete application of skills and competencies identified within the fore-mentioned human component. Their vision of authority can be influenced by their own perception of responsibilities and accountability, as well as by their ethics. The incentives used in motivation reflect their own values.

The concrete application of skills and competencies is vulnerable to the pipelines through which leaders themselves have acquired their knowledge (exploitative and explorative learning). The learning and development processes which one has been submitted to are fundamental to one's concrete capacity for holistic application to detect a peer's competencies and direct such identified potential towards areas of expertise from outside their roles.

In order to understand how one's life experience is assimilated into their leadership style, Lieblich (2003) recommends applying Adler's theory on the impact of memories on human personality. Extending such a framework to the leadership style can highlight mentors, early academic interests, reference readings as salient points in one's professional evolution.

3.4.6.3 COGNITION

Attempts of detecting a *modus operandi* should, nevertheless, consider Richardson's view on replications and the variations in which they may manifest (Richardson, 2018). However, a pure affirmation of a *modus operandi* is excluded, as Richardson argues, since causal relations that could drive strategic thinking are context-sensitive and the COVID crisis will not confirm the usual macroenvironment audit.

The contrast argued by Thaler between the *homo economicus* abstract profile illustrating economic theory and the *homo sapiens* we live amongst demands separating cognitive processes which either replicate or go against the textbook dictates of economic behaviour. (Thaler R.H., 2000).

The open discussion interview, deceptively simple in its approach and execution, nevertheless should produce salient secondary data about behavioural economics as manifest in response to the pandemic by the company and other retailers as well as by the key personnel involved. Much of this data was rooted in their personal lives but informed by their institutional behaviour.

3.4.6.4 VISION OF SELF

A leader's vision of themselves is fundamental for establishing their leadership identity, which draws upon the negotiation and the reinterpretation of meanings, experiences, and relationships. As researcher, I could also pay attention to how my interviewees have constructed, deconstructed, and reconstructed their leader identity across their account, and what the momentums are for their view of themselves through another lens such as for example that of peer or subordinate (Frimann and Hersted, 2016).

This vocabulary to which the research is becoming acquainted as receiver of the communication flow launched within storytelling will sketch and fill in essential data regarding the interviewee's vision of their own identity and personality (Butina, 2015). According to McAdams, the imagery

we hold of what we perceive as our own identity unfolds like a story. Our vision of our own identity contains a synthesis of the cultural context which we're an issue of; any introspection being filtered through the norms and codes of our upbringing. McAdams speaks of an inner conflict between the image we hold of ourselves, and our identity as sketched under the influence of our environment, personal attributes, primary groups, and culture. Whether as subject or as rhetoric, storytelling revolves around intentionality, which articulates beliefs and desires within the context of goals. McAdams defines autobiographical narration as employing memory as a language of a goal-directed self-portrayal. The general criticism of an etiolated veracity pointed out by McAdams is not valid within the re-creation of the retailer's performance during the pandemic, as accuracy is guaranteed both by an immediate past as well as by documented facts such as financial records or press releases.

How individuals see themselves represents a keynote for making sense of their own past. Clandinin and Caine (2013) argue that people build their self-identity in accordance with key stories which they consider as playing a defining role in their developmental path and which they would also use as a lens when reflecting on how past experiences have shaped them into who they are today. A key angle in self-identity facilitated through narrative inquiry comes from the manner in which respondents recollect past challenges; whether they prioritise the content behind tasks, the actions they had to take or the results they have obtained (Bangerter Et al, 2014) Such a distinction is fundamental in separating planners (individuals who focus on perspective wins) from doers (individuals who prioritise immediate goals (Thaler and Shefrin, 1981) The vision leaders hold of themselves may also be influenced by their professional affiliation, whether to their line of work, their organisation, or their team (Bager, 2015).

3.4.6.5 ATTITUDES TOWARDS GOALS

Pellegrino & Carbo (2001) raise a perspective over strategic thinking as nesting - a starting point for Sun Tzu's convergence between a distant perspective and the obvious data detected when approaching proximity. Consequently, as a researcher, I had to explore how interviewees position themselves in connection to time orientation, whether they favoured short- or long-term results.

Time orientation may also highlight what Thaler describes as the commitment strategy or the decision individuals take to limit their own options in a given situation in order to prevent potential unwanted outcomes. The commitment strategy demands its own survey of the arguments upon which individuals select what alternatives are to be considered and what options abandoned. Such factors might be integral to the reasoning behind strategic thinking, such as the case of one's attitude towards risk.

3.5 Credibility

My main focus was to reach discernment synergies of which the individual is less aware. Consequently, I had to avoid intellectualised answers and consider a methodology in which the studied subjects would provide such data spontaneously. Standardised questions would inevitably frame answers into patterns, standing out as more appropriate for validating theories than for an exploratory research aim. Furthermore, standardised questions would inevitably introduce disruptions, fracturing answers and delivering incomplete data (Ratcliffe, 2002).

My focus on safeguarding objectivity was complemented by the snowballing method used in the sample selection. The approached interviewees recommended new participants whose roles they described as detrimental to the implementation of new norms across various functions of the organisation. Written communications were avoided for the risk of an intellectualised participation which would have altered the reliability of the collected data. Furthermore, as demonstrated, the sincerity and intimacy attained through face-to-face interviews carry respondents to a state in which they are comfortable enough to deliver participation which is less likely to be constructed to fit the 'socially desirable' pattern. Therefore, their genuine attitude will favour the targeted accuracy. More cooperation represents another positive input of face-to-face interviews.

The participants' role confirms the credibility of the qualitative data. The unequivocal character of codes and the concrete application of the participants' roles highlight the dependability of data. The conventions emerged by way of the nature of goods, the provenance of merchandise,

and the statutory frameworks such as quality standards and custom procedures, establishing synergies across the supply chain to ensure the confirmability of data. Transferability is reflected in the logistical disruptions in the supply chain and the de-synchronisation of volumes to the unexpectedly escalated demand (Lincoln and Guba, 1986).

3.6 Reflection on the research process

The study emerges from an experienced and shared reality, to which I have contributed to its implementation and execution phases. Privileged by immersion (Emerson, 1995), as an observer and interviewer, I was ever mindful of the challenges my colleagues and I were facing in unprecedented times, faced with a fragmented selection of relevant measures which demanded an equal or superior effort of assessing data that did not converge within the catalyst context of strategic thinking. Arendt, et al. (2012) argue the importance of the researcher to manage the appropriate integration so that the observed subjects persist in the studied behaviour without sensing any intrusion which may affect accuracy. Such challenge is not relevant to the research as my approach was to have minimal intrusion and regulation. As an employee, and thus a member of the organisation, the issue of integration has only been raised when earning the cooperation of decedents and not of fellow colleagues with executive roles.

A particular concern arose about how my responsibility of sharing the purpose of the research could affect the respondent's participation by introducing a rationalised delivery of answers. All respondents were provided insights on the anonymous collection and management of data. According to Squire (2008), narratives can also be influenced by the context in which storytelling is being conducted and the respondent's own assessment of the audience. Participating in academic research may be perceived as an informal conversation, with a limited reach, compared to one's involvement in press conferences and other such similar addresses. However, even the awareness of such scope and audience can influence the interviewee or the leadership or mentoring positioning before a fellow team member.

As a preliminary phase to the study, Pellegrino, and Carbo (2001) recommend that the researcher should engage in self-reflection in regard to how they shall connect to the participants. My

approach was to create empathy with the interviewees, to have minimal questioning, to share life stories and experiences (also of the pandemic) and to allow them to provide information in an open manner. The success of my approach would be in the nature of the empirical evidence garnered.

A major challenge arose when distancing from what Wolfinger (2002) describes as tacit knowledge, notable the observer's familiarity to details, contexts, institutions, practices, or codes. In a default setting, such access facilitates recognising the role of elements found in the scene that is about to be documented. However, the pandemic calls for detachment, as it pushes both the organisation and its culture into a reconfigured paradigm. Reflective questions proposed by Deggs and Hernandez (2018) were adapted in the context of my membership of the organisation. Therefore, my connection to the research setting was resumed to the a priori expectations bred upon the first signs of a deviated market demand and before the organisation had issued any reaction.

The shared experiences of my colleagues and I at the retailer could have been seen as detrimental to objective evaluation and empirical authenticity; however, my firm belief was that such common ground, particularly in the setting of a set of challenges not experienced in the world before, would provide the insights required and prove my confidence in the method I had chosen. Before engaging in the research, I had conducted the introspection required according to Bispo & Gherardi, (2019). I did not have preconceived ideas about the outcome of the research, but I was confident that it would provide rich data interpretation and achieve its aim of answering the research question: *How leaders readjust their individual patterns of strategic thinking in times of crisis?*

At first glance, this method appears to be self-evident and effortless in its essence, that it consists mainly of coordinating a conversation and obtaining needed information. As a norm, the respondent adopts a passive role during the interview, being limited by the pre-set structure of the conversation.

As much as the formal affiliation to the company could sustain such background, my focus remained, however, that of inspiring and supporting what Ratcliffe (2002) describes as an ambiance of disclosure. However, as respondents started to open, a challenge appeared when maintaining an approving and not a neutral participation that would have determined that

participants reflect upon their thoughts and feelings. Once installed, self-assessment brought the risk of having respondents withdraw or try to correct their initial statements and a rationalised participation would have profoundly hindered, if not compromised, the study. However, a scrutiny of critical self-assessment could qualify as beneficial if the points on which the respondents would like to intervene could be identified.

Though privileged with such insights given by the interviewees on their own initiative, I have avoided explicitly addressing childhood memories both out of ethics but also as I tend not to agree with Adler's thesis on how they are determined by one's view of life. I rather consider human personality as a dynamic development which can foster mindsets that may contradict those that one has exhibited in previous stages of life.

When reflecting on the extent to which the interviewee's perception might be juxtaposed with my own hypothesis, a particular challenge could arise from scaling the benefits and shortcomings generated by a synchronisation of assumptions. (Guercini, 2014) refers to constantly extending methodological approaches validated and accommodated in qualitative research. These new methodologies represent responses to dynamics registered in the business environment, notably around data circulation.

Ratcliffe (2002) favours a mutual exchange of thoughts and feelings, initiated, however, by the interviewer as a strategy of gaining confidence. Such approach became feasible with any opportunity of engaging outside company-related topics such as family life, parenthood experiences, and even nostalgia over various issues.

Throughout the research, I was mindful of the flexibility required of a researcher whom Ratcliffe (2002) describes as a "methodological bricoleur" both in data collection as well as interpretation. The aim was very much to focus on the dynamic nature of the process and as Achterberg and Arendt (2012) state, qualitative research is demanded when validating process and not outcome-related variables; the study considers performance only in the prospect of influencing the cognitive deductions supporting the affirmation of a *modus operandi*.

As a researcher, I had to keep focus on the objective order of events and not that of the interviewee's narration. Such references and the sequencing the interviewee chose for setting the

plot when storytelling is acknowledged to reveal additional data. However, the same consideration would be given if a certain momentum seemed to be prioritised, whether the interviewee chose it as a starting point for their narration or to construct various correspondences or analogies. As Pellegrino & Carbo (2001) point out, if the simplification process has been traced, a researcher's focus should not neglect analogies and their source nor the respondent's perception on outcomes and their evaluation. The challenge which awaited me as the researcher was that of extracting common denominators and dissecting their significance. Such terrain could lead to central themes which would stand as an axis for each stage and would help to determine the underpinnings of the responses to the pandemic.

Lieblich (2003) signals a special attention to be given to disruptions within the narrative, such as unfinished accounts or depictions producing any changes of tone or attitude in the teller. Once installed, self-assessment could bring the risk of having respondents withdraw or try to correct their initial statements, and a rationalised participation would profoundly hinder, if not compromise, the study. However, a scrutiny of critical self-assessment could qualify as beneficial if the points on which the respondents would like to intervene could be identified. As a researcher, I was also interested in polarities such as negative versus positive perspectives or the extent to which narratives accommodate either egocentric depictions or relational stories which draw references to others.

As signalled by Schober (2008), delivering suboptimal performance may come as a particular concern for interviewees, therefore questions should be somehow constructed to extract the natural cognitive flow without bringing the respondent into the context in which they may reflect on whether the analogies they had used within strategic thinking were extraordinary enough. The cognitive processes detected by Richard Thaler demand an insight into the respondents' calculations towards optimisation and the constraints they consider along this assessment. Furthermore, the exceptional context of the COVID pandemic can broaden perspectives over relevant limitations retained within optimisation and dynamics identified from a default condition. The pressure generated by the 'key industry' status submits the organisation to constraints from three directions: the Government, the suppliers, and the consumers.

CHAPTER 4. FINDINGS AND DISCUSSION

4.1 Theoretical background for the data coding strategy

Narrative analysis follows no agreed procedures (Ratcliffe, 2002). However, strategic thinking within retail can employ a thematic analysis, whereas responsiveness to incentives can also be mapped through a structural approach. It is the data collected through narrative research that will determine the most common themes that allow a separation of findings. However, the extracted themes will be submitted to a system of axis encompassing variables such as: environmental factor pressure, previous experience in crisis management, decision audit, and outcomes. These criteria can foster causalities, justifying or cancelling each decision. Furthermore, such a framework also allows detecting variations in the modus operandi before an unforeseeable context emerges. Self-efficacy could also be considered as an additional dimension for the system of axis if scenario-case questions would be introduced. Even when faced with an evolving research methodology as suggested in the literature, I was convinced that my open plan questioning would result in the sort of data envisaged by more prescriptive researchers.

The general structure proposed by Labov and Waletzky (1967), as cited by Squire (2008) unfolded an abstract argument into orientation details which lead to a complicating action. An evaluation follows, descending into a resolution and highlighting a coda. For instance, a decision to reduce the usual working hours would develop as follows: business hours had to be imperatively amended (abstract). It became impossible to operate within the same terms and still have the stores fully supplied in time (orientation). Such measure became obvious as our frontline staff needed at least two additional hours to undertake the reception of the merchandise and put it on the shelves- which were constantly emptied through stockpiling (complicating action). Our concerns moved towards the prospect of not being able to supply our stores, thus throwing them into an operational crisis (evaluation). However, we managed to regain our regular supply flow without overworking our frontline staff (resolution). Now we know we should have previewed eventual disruptions within our supply chain and acted accordingly (coda). Criticism to experience-centred research reaches what Squire (2008) describes as the prescriptive assumptions about the presented events or the contradictions or discontinuities it

may have to accommodate. When mapping the cognitive processes involved in strategic thinking, data analysis will highlight a longitudinal approach. However, variations from the usual cognitive pattern to be identified within the pandemic calls for a cross-sectional approach. When interviewing people living with severe illness, (Anne Bruce, 2016), has documented how data collected has shifted the pre-established methodology framework through unforeseeable findings. Such revision is argued by narrative turns which elevates new concepts and employs emergent designs built upon methods borrowed from quantitative research. Characteristic adaptations breed self-awareness and self-management, goals, affinities, drivers, and mindsets. Nevertheless, my interest as a researcher was focused on surveying any conflictual states that may have emerged in one's identity after handling the pandemic. Identity is defined by McAdams as emancipation from role confusion. Therefore, leadership style as an expression of identity emerges from a confrontation between one's personal ethos and pragmatic job attributions. Scrutinising the retailer's organisational culture is fundamental to understanding storytelling, since, as McAdams pointed out, narratives reflect the environment in which events have been experienced.

4.2 Coding Strategy and Mind Mapping

In this short subchapter, I will establish briefly what each codes means, and that the reader should expect from each specific section. The diagram below (Fig. 5) represents a visual representation of the codes generated by the data. The codes are classified in themes, whilst the themes are divided into 3 main areas: the Individual, the Organisation, and the Context. Around the Individual area, the data shows 4 main themes, such as Personal Attributes, Professional Attributes, Career and Strategic Thinking. Although the latter can be included in either of the first two, I have decided to analyse it separately given its central role in this research. The Organisation area consists into 3 themes, including aspects of the Industry, Leadership, and an array of Influencing Factors towards leaders and strategic thinking. The third area reflects the economic and social Context, which is that of the Covid-19 Pandemic and its impact on the development of organisational and individual resilience.

Figure 6. Coding – Mind Map

(NVivo, 2021)

For increased readability, the large diagram above has been broken down in sections, as it follows:

Figure 6A. Mind map – Individual area

(NVivo, 2021)

Figure 6B. Mind map – Organisation area

(NVivo, 2021)

Figure 6C. Mind map – Context area

(NVivo, 2021)

This classification represents the core of the natural flow of discussion with each participant during the interviews. The first and largest area resulted from the data collected is the **Individual** related area, which focuses on the leader as an individual. Every interviewee started their life story with a detailed **Career** overview, most of them beginning with the college or university period. This common theme covers 4 main aspects or codes: the *Career Path* or journey, which highlights their most important and relevant roles, the companies they worked in and the influencing people they met; *Turning Points*, which brings to the light strong moments that led to life changing decisions; *Management consulting* as a career choice with high implication on strategic thinking especially, followed by a child code of Management Consulting that goes into deeper details aiming to answer the question *Why Management Consulting* could be a good career choice; the last code of career these is *Military Career*, which again, similar to Management Consulting, brings to the surface interesting links to strategic thinking. These last two codes have been collapsed together as former career experiences and how these influenced leaders' present careers.

Another large theme in Individual area is **Personal Attributes**. The first code captures information around my participants' *Background and lifestyle*, such as *Inspiring Family*, places

their lived in, routines or habits. The code goes hand in hand with the next one, which is *Hobbies and Passions*. Another code of this theme is *Personal Development*, which describes elements of the journeys my participants went through for their own development, but most of all it highlights their willingness to develop their skills or abilities, and to grow both personally and professionally. Somehow in strong connectivity with the *Personal Development* is the *Personal Values* code. I have collected here all the narrative regarding their life philosophies, personal ethics, principles and values their guided their life around. The data also gave me to opportunity to capture some *Personality* types related stories and some moments of *Self Reflection*.

The next theme has been built around their **Professional Attributes**, which reflects several skills, characteristics and qualities strongly related to their professional life. The first code of this theme is *Soft skills* and blends all these characteristics and attributes mentioned which are part of the professional development and success of a leader within the organisation, such *Communication* that refers to different aspects such as communication skills, ways of effective communication and its impact on leadership or *Networking* that comes as part of the theme and collects the narratives around the importance of networking inside and outside the organisation plus the necessary skillset.

Another code of this category is *Hard skills* which highlights some of the important skills a leader must have and to develop for a successful career from my participants' point of view and experiences. A central role in this theme is occupied by the *Loyalty for the Organisation*, as an important characteristic of the leaders that grew professionally within the same organisation for many years. Since not just organisations must be resilient in order to stay successful during these unprecedented times, leaders as individuals need to develop it for themselves, hence *Resilience* is the last code of the theme, but one of the crucial ones in my research.

The central theme of this area is **Strategic Thinking**. As I mentioned at the beginning of this section, I have decided to give this theme a separate place in the area, although it could have been included in the previous three themes, reason being that the concept itself is the very core of my research. The first code is *Ambiguity vs. Structure*, which explores leaders' preferences over either ambiguous tasks and projects or more structured, guided activities. *Building a Strategy* follows the previous codes and explores ways around creating strategies. Another code resulted from the data collected is *Decision Making*. This code is a fundamental aspect in leadership, and

it appears frequently in the data I have collected. *Influencing* code refers to both influencing other and be influenced. Another code related to this theme is *Mindset*, which presents various aspects of leaders' thinking and how this helped or impacted them along their careers. The last code of this section is *Strategic Thinking Characteristics* which wraps up, conclude and recap nicely all the aspects related to strategic thinking leaders that came up during the data collection.

The second area or section of the data is the **Organisation** which is divided in three main themes. The first one is **Industry**, and it contains four codes. *Customer behaviour* highlights its transformations suffered during the Pandemic and how leaders' decisions impacted customers and ultimately, *Retail Industry*. *Retail Culture* speaks more generally about the industry under my research whilst the last code of this theme, *Retail Going forward* offers an overview on leaders' thoughts and prognostics regarding retail industry in the light of disruption, changes and transformations that are going on around the country and the World.

The second theme of the area is **Influencing Factors**, which includes several codes. One of the codes is *Challenges* and it offers rich data around some of the leaders' difficult experiences throughout their careers with direct connection to the organisation's culture. This code has a child code, *Criticism*. Apart of their difficult experiences, they shared with me Negative and Positive Experiences which have influenced them from a leadership perspective and had a massive impact on their development and success. The last code of this theme is *Books, theories and frameworks* and includes all the stories and comments around the books they've read, the theories and framework they applied or got inspired by, which relates in one way or another to the organisation they've been working, or they work in.

The last and central theme of Organisation area is **Leadership**, which is divided in six main codes. The first, *Becoming a leader* reveals interesting stories and advice from my participants experiences and the organisations that nurture them to become successful leaders. Another code is *Female leaders*. This highlights some of the distinctive characteristics of the strong female leaders which made an impact on their followers at the beginning of their careers and throughout the journey. As an extension of the previous code, *Followership* dives deeper into the relationship between the established leaders and the becoming ones, underlining the impact on their development, and thinking.

Whilst Followership focuses more on the becoming leaders' perspective, *Inspiring leaders* code brings to the surface narratives around the established leaders and how they inspired their followers. Strongly related to the previous code, *Mentoring and coaching* highlights the direct impact on leaders' development and progression throughout mentorship programmes and coaching facilitated by the organisations. The last code, in total opposition to the ones mentioned is *Toxic leaders*. This last code of Leadership's theme discusses the impact of toxic leaders, such as selfish, authoritarian, poor communicators or ignorant, on the becoming leaders' development and career.

The final area is *Context*, and it contains one theme, **Covid-19**, which is divided in three codes. The *Pandemic* establishes the reality and context to which my research refers to and it has been conducted in and underlines important characteristics of strategic thinking leaders in decision making during Global disruption. Directly linked to the Pandemic, *Organisational resilience* points to the ultimate goal of strategic leaders during the Global disruption, which is to ensure organisations are resilience enough not just to survive, but to thrive.

However, to offer a more over-arching perspective, I collated the themes and subthemes in a diagram. As some of the codes would relate more to others, I collapsed them together. The last representation is again a breakdown of the three main themes: INDIVIDUAL, ORGANISATION and CONTEXT. Each of them keeps the same codes as elaborated above.

Figure 7. The presentation of the data codes

(Microsoft Excel, 2022)

4.3 Analysis, Interpretation and Findings

4.3.1 INDIVIDUAL AREA

4.3.1.1 THEME 1 – STRATEGIC THINKING as the core theme of the research

The literature highlights knowledge as core asset in both setting as well as favouring strategic thinking. Consequently, the first area which requires the researcher's focus is the management of incomplete data and predictions drawn of unfamiliar settings which place strategic thinking within the binary of structure and ambiguity. Building a strategy implies capitalising on available data and subjective estimations which are themselves a product of one's capacity to discern the precedent. Reflecting the concrete deduction used in cognition, an overview of decision-making highlights arguments and proportions used in scaling risks to the likeliness and extent of targeted benefits. As the ultimate rationale behind leadership is to engage others and integrate common goals into individual projects, influencing represents another key area for study which demands a particular attention on one's own persuasive techniques, which can be further evaluated in a comparative regard to strategies employed for individuals or settings which do not respond to such modus operandi. Mindset is considered both as premise as well as product of strategic thinking, the researcher's focus aiming towards understanding both initial attitudes used as filters in decision making, as well as beliefs shaped by one's own experience in problem solving. Nevertheless, as a conclusion of the theme, data analysis should also survey strategic thinking characteristics affirmed by each member in order to extract a common pattern that allows theorising of the research aim.

4.3.1.1.1 Ambiguity vs. Structure in relationship with the strategic thinking

Impulsiveness appears to be counted as a personal risk which prevents a person from fathoming and understanding exact circumstances and outcomes. The participants appear to be aware of how the pressure of delivering a prompt decision might affect the effective discernment of an issue affecting their ability to separate the background noise. Decision making is therefore

conditioned by clarity which demands detachment from various issues preoccupying the participants' minds as well as the pressure factor.

An issue is approached by identifying with its eventual causalities, implications, influences, points of vulnerability and any other elements conventionally accommodated within scenario planning. An additional angle under which an issue is deconstructed revolves around

components which the decision maker can intervene upon, and elements out of their control.

Reflection over controllable elements inevitably creates a clear vision of the areas one can claim knowledge of, allowing an estimation of the highest level of effectiveness one may deliver through their input.

Participants agree on problem solving as operating within unknown territories. The respondents' advocacy towards flexibility and adaptability reflects an acceptance of ambiguity as a likely setting which cannot be avoided. However, when it comes to an effective pathway for managing uncertainties, Jack believes that the focus should fall on available knowledge, whereas Antony on circumstances which one can influence.

“All, you know. I think probably the first instance, to really, really understand the question, probably process it, you know, it that's to go for a 10-minute walk, then find out all the information, put in some sort of logical steps. Actually, I know, I'm only missing this, and I will find out this, then I go from there, rather than, okay, I still don't know the answer, but I know 90% of it. I know that you often give 90% back, the other person is more than happy, so I guess, it's okay not to know, which is quite hard thing, you know, especially when you're in your early career is always “what's this?” and you're often terrified not to say no, I don't know, but actually a lot of time it's fine.”, mentions Jack, while Anthony:

“And, again, another another lesson was about you... you can only...you can influence what you can influence. You can't influence other stuff. You can't influence things about outside of your control. So, you just deal with what's in your control. You deal with what you can influence and deal with. And trust that other people are gonna do what they say they're going to do and... and well like that. Otherwise, you're going to fail. You go to fail and you're going to reflect yourself again. Affect your health. Because you can't influence what other people...”

Operating in familiar territories implies collecting insights and perspectives to identify key points to address. Erin exemplifies this perspective through the legal requirements of the supply chain which confirm feasibility. Strategic thinking involves surveying alternative solutions which may eliminate or displace blockers, according to Erin. When applied in familiar settings, strategic thinking appeals to insights extracted from the precedent (Wolf, 1996). Such a deductive approach is recalled by Rocky and Katya when stating that detecting the logical structure of processes is a core value of strategic thinking. To Rocky, logic demands disseminating questions in mutually exclusive components up until the point where answers may arise, even for highly specific issues. Facilitating deeper understanding, both Rocky and Katya point out how a focus on logic ensures the ability to communicate complex realities descending from data in a simple manner which made sense to all addressees.

“It’s about asking really good questions and then breaking them down in such a way that is just really simple and logical.”

The ability to communicate ensured participation, engagement, and ensured exchange of knowledge (Pasamar, 2019). However, particular circumstances may not always allow deduction a consequence of incomplete data, which creates ambiguity. Confronted with the prospect of ambiguity, Erin states that she would rather be interested in dissecting such challenge in order to be attain a better understanding of its processes.

“Well...I would say that ambiguity is interesting. However, I’m very much the type of person that wants to address it, dissect it, and see what we can do to put processes or understand the process.”

Jack highlights a similar point of view when advising towards separating question into logical steps and try to identify the extent to which an issue becomes unfamiliar. The reflective process mentioned by Jack recreates the assimilation-accommodation dynamics within Piaget’s Theory of Cognitive Development. However, Jack concentrates on detecting ‘missing points’ in the perspective launched within the configuration created when accommodating new knowledge.

The ‘missing points’ indicate the level of efficacy and effectiveness to be expected when delivering a task.

“I still don't know the answer, but I know 90% of it. I know that you often give 90% back, the other person is more than happy.”

4.3.1.1.2 Building a strategy - through the eyes of a strategic thinking leader

Strategic thinking follows a vector's dynamic from the setting of cognition to the targeted circumstances. The cognition behind strategic decision-making is oriented towards mapping directions to address (levers) and identifying the key indicators for their accomplishment (Benevolo et al, 2021). As highlighted in Jack's statements, criteria used for assessment can employ different and, apparently, antagonistic outlooks which may coexist and be affirmed when explained through distinctive purposes.

“The biggest thing I care about is things going wrong; ... for me would probably be all around keeping everyone's morale up, spirits high, because everyone always focuses on the 1% negative rather than the 99% positive.”

Such paradox can be correlated to the different matrices in which anticipation and retrospection can be framed. Unlike anticipation, where feasibility is dependent on both attained progresses, as well as uncertainty, which may cancel any key achievement, retrospection implies judging a momentum as completed. Anticipation implies investment, whereas retrospection reflects detachment. Nick explains his strategic thinking patterns as descending from experience (Goldman, 2015).

“It has been about trying some things and failing and learning and then being on a journey. Why I think the way that I think I was... I think it's probably through experience. Um, how? My line managers have challenged me in various ways through my career. Seeing others reflecting a lot and thinking a lot about you know the different scenarios in different outcomes before actually putting it into play, so I can't say turn say that this person in

my careers who are model. Then that's exactly how I wanted to work. So, it's all been through personal experience.”

The precedent is correlated to feasibility, effectiveness, and risk mitigation, thus appealing to experience ensures promptitude in decision- making and implementation. However, Nick signals the importance of accommodating every learning acquired through experience by reconfirming its validity through multiple mental scenarios (Wolf, 1996) (Schoemaker, 1995). Cedric appears to combine the two perspectives. For him, strategy is grounded in a continuous survey of opportunities within the external or the internal environment, detecting the criteria through which they should be prioritised, as well as the stakeholders that can facilitate their fruition (Vaitheeswaran, 2018). Problem solving follows a similar methodology, though oriented towards the pathways which can allow lowering risks. The internal resource audit phase prioritised communicating the new objectives and identifying the stakeholders that reveal the competencies which allow delegation of tasks for each goal. The relation Cedric has developed with space as an internal resource highlights a personal approach of the Lean Six Sigma philosophy. Patterns identified empirically through past experiences has individuals develop strategic thinking within the margins of the particular causalities.

“When you think about strategy, it's almost like you need to understand what the opportunities are so you know a lot of the work I do is about... is looking at the system understanding how the system works, having a relative level of detail, but utilising the big brand, but really looking at where the opportunities are and then working through a process that says like how do we prioritise them? Who are stakeholders? Who are the people that are going to help me get these changes for a positive? I... and make things better for my customer. The supplier in this case and ultimately our customer.”

Therefore, all logical deductions function as vectors between certain points. Correspondingly, efficiency is assessed in relation to outcomes produced within given costs. Transcending levels of scale (from store configuration to shelf display) when assessing space, Cedric reveals strategic thinking as a survey of potential additional perspectives which can signal new pipelines, other than costs, that can foster efficiency. As reflected in Cedric’s focus on verifying how

merchandise display complements customer experience, the critical lens used for self-assessment recreates the addressees' perspective. His focus on enhancing external opportunities while reassessing areas of efficiency within internal resources qualifies Cedric as an instrumental leader (Antonakis, 2004).

“The most important thing in our business is our is our colleagues, our staff as number one, but the second most important thing is space. And if we use it well, we can drive opportunity and commercial gain in the business by making sure that space is correctly allocated and then the flow through the Format team is really ideal.”

Stefania states the importance of figures when formulating strategy, as correlating data with buying patterns allowed her to extract algorithms which she further used to develop a model that increased the average order values for her previous order. When grounding strategic thinking, data interpretation changes the paradigm over an organisation's external environment. By prioritising independent insights, the conventional approach to the macro environment indicates that organisations are reactive to external factors. However, data analysis can be assimilated to an audit of internal capabilities that can allow the identification of configurations in which a particular external context becomes reactive to the organisation. Consumer behaviour is absorbed within the social macro factors. However, while a focus on the external environment only points out trends and the VALS (values and lifestyles) framework, a focus on collected data concentrates these patterns to the organisation's own offer. When further placed against additional variables, the algorithms can allow forecasts within a short time span, as Stefania signals. The shorter the forecast time span, the higher the clarity to risk mitigation in strategic thinking.

4.3.1.1.3 Decision making, an important factor in developing strategic mindset

Reflections on facts and flair as possible sources for leadership are present in every participant's intervention. Data and intuition are regarded as complementary, rather than opposing factors, highlighting a democratic strategic style (Meij, et al., 2016): general consensus indicates the necessity to attain a symbiosis between the two. Intuition is seen as rather audacious, admirable, and justifiable in exceptional contexts where data is unavailable or incomplete. Even while

admiring leaders who can make decisions without data, Katya acknowledged that such a pattern is not always applicable (Maciariello, 2006). Jack links effective decision-making to contemplation, viewing expectations of spontaneity as counterproductive. Accommodating the prospect of not being familiar with new challenges is mentioned among the most insightful conclusions over one's path.

"I think along that I've also learned that decision making to me personally, it's to not try not to be so instant, you know. It's OK to say no, right, or it's OK to say, "give me 5 minutes, give me a day" and I think that was a quite big learning curve for me, you know, become more comfortable not knowing stuff."

When inquired as to whether they equate the pursuit of an alternative modus operandi to instinct, Melanie insists on a distinction between the required due diligence and overthinking. By invalidating the proven effectiveness of established methods, disruptive times impose new paths which demand an alert application. Pressure calls for the urgency of very short-term goals which converge towards risk mitigation and loss prevention (Antoniou & Ansoff, 2004). Disruptive events are perceived as difficult to fathom in regard to two coordinates: the scale and the areas of impact. While manifestation may qualify as an unpredictable element within the equation of risk, the impact of a threat becomes easy to estimate due to the practical knowledge attained through direct experience with the organisation (Whipps, 2014). Due diligence is anchored in concrete, palpable (logistics) or perceivable (quality standards) elements, whereas overthinking functions like a continuous survey of scenarios, thus operating on hypothesis and speculation. Such distinction points out intuition as not related to the external factor but to the internal areas with which one is already familiar.

4.3.1.1.4 Influencing skills as a fundamental part of strategic thinking

The arguments brought by all respondents who prioritised clarity and communication as the main traits required for leadership revolved around explaining one's vision in a manner which can resonate with every team member's own personality and the degree of autonomy they could

manage. Strategic thinking is shared as the logic behind the cognitive framework. Identified processes are recommended to be explained in order to obtain a more effective understanding of the strategy, but also for a higher group adhesion to the presented goal. (Korlén et al, 2020) A leader's strategic thinking may become the matrix for every group member's modus operandi, since alignment strategies are grounded on contextual knowledge earned within a specific setting. In order to obtain cohesion with the leader's vision, strategic thinking must be translated into concept with which all members are familiarised. Explaining logical connections lays the foundation for an effective division of the project into tasks (Gibbins-Klein, 2017).

However, influence becomes a bidirectional process. When asked about inspirational figures which have shaped her leadership style, Natalia points out that such contemplation should not be limited to superiors with a disregard for the people one comes into contact with (Gu, 2015).

“It's not necessarily about your bosses, it's about other people.”

Antony also regards the acquisition of knowledge as a common journey which is based on exchange.

“No one knew what, so none at ever faced into anything like that before. Everyone was learning, so I think one of the good things was that everyone was learning together. Yes, everyone was learning together, and everyone was affected together.”

The pressure of coordinating a team may be perceived as an estrangement from self-management. When focused on reshaping behaviours, coaching strategies integrate multiple cognitive frameworks which converge towards internal self-regulation (Wang et al, 2021). As team cooperation is essential to performance, such balance may be prioritised to the leader's own comfort, both in objective issues such as time management, as well as in subjective matters, such as resilience (Drucker, 1968).

“And then when I got promoted to actually leave the team, I kind of felt like I was being back in my element a little bit.”

4.3.1.1.5 Mindset, and how it can impact strategic thinking

The interventions of all participants converge towards a set of traits which can be regarded as mutually inclusive: receptivity towards the unknown, adaptability, and a dissatisfaction with the prospect of developing a comfort zone (Becherer, et al., 2008). Respondents (Jack, Russ, Erin, Stefania, Randall) regard the unknown as a fertile terrain for growth. According to Jack and Russ, exploring the unknown as a pipeline to the acquisition of knowledge leads to better self-efficacy and facilitates risk prevention. The continuous search for a more stimulating work environment has been brought as an argument for career reconversion and illustrates such a mindset. An additional trait transpiring from all interventions manifests as prioritising long-term benefits over instant delivery.

Unknown territories may be detected in settings with which leaders are unfamiliar but also in unforeseen circumstances (such as the COVID 19) which they cannot properly fathom (Wolf, 1996). When it comes to the first scenario, Cedric believes in engaging in tasks outside of one's competencies for the purpose of expanding one's perspective.

“Maybe even just try and do a bit more of someone else's job and just get that experience and understanding, because if you're seen to be a word...An achiever in the business.”

Contemplating the benefits of a leadership position, Sara evokes the opportunity to become acquainted with terrains outside of her competencies, which, placed in the context of the value chain, revealed the activities standing in the vicinity of her own attribution. In its broadest architecture, the value chain connects prototype design to post-purchase consumer attendance, which places strategic thinking on a vector between goal formulation and goal accomplishment. However, the broader the identified complementarities, the wider the premises become to expand the vector into configurations which allow mapping when employing design thinking (Boland, 2007). Exploring and entering a multidisciplinary scrutiny of issues with which one is confronted while performing their tasks represents one of the pillars of transformational leadership (Pasamar, 2019). Sara's perspective confirms transformational leaders as applying to themselves the same principles they use in team guidance (Benedetti, 2019). Nevertheless, Cedric points out

details of an additional terrain of growth which may be frequently disregarded, as it is perceived with the confidence arising from of one's expertise.

“So, I did a session as a Store Planning Coordinator, so I was looking at the whole outside stores and making sure they were following the basic guidelines and how they should be where they were being created, and then I went more into macro space which is looking at the individual allocations of space for individual sectors around the store.”

“I was famous for the time is going through and looking at the whole of table sauces, for instance, we had something like 18 different types of Heinz ketchup, so different sizes and so on, and I thought this just it can't be right. It was a little bit of the tail wagging the dog, shall we say another one was tea, so we looked at Tea in the exploration of tea and the space. It took up and just realised you add... it didn't need that space based on its...”

4.3.1.1.6 Strategic thinking characteristics and how they can be recognised

The equation of strategic thinking is resumed to goals and instrumentation. Though feasible, envisioning success as a 100% goal competition only sets the premise for decline. Consequently, goal formulation should not sacrifice long term stability for short term gains (Antoniou & Ansoff, 2004). Goal formulation may address multiple directions of action. Multitasking reduces the concentration allocated to each activity had it been conducted singularly, according to Francene. A point of reflection arises from the extent to which strategic thinking can be sustained in the process of implementation and whether it can support two simultaneous directions, as cognition must remain alert in a state of automatism. As reflected in Francene's statement, a second degree of strategic thinking comes with the challenge of achieving and sustaining a balance between two confrontational interests.

“I kind of realised that ... What I struggled with was being the middleman too much.”

The foremost direction adopted in strategic thinking is to delegate. Strategic thinking is grounded on flexibility as uncertainties cannot be addressed through data and demonstrated methodologies. All participants signal the necessity to adapt.

“I think I learned that I prefer to either get stuff done me or have a team that Kind of I can organise the time of...”

4.3.1.2 THEME 2 – Importance of the CAREER in shaping strategic thinking

A person’s career path is pivotal to both their competencies, as well as their leadership style, as each industry and role highlights a distinctive exposure to goals formulation, ethics, pressure factors, and knowledge acquisition opportunities. As goals articulate motivation which compiles intrinsic aspirations and the influence of external stimuli, the researcher’s focus was directed towards disseminating the rationale behind career turning points to further analyse eventual mutations from arguments dominating the interviewees’ professional path. Management consultancy and a military background have been detected as alternative career paths from having evolved in the retail industry.

4.3.1.2.1 Career path, the essential journey to a strategic mindset

Except for participants who had crossed over from consultancy and those with a military background, the majority of respondents built their career path through other organisations within retail (Cedric, Antony), or other industries (Terri, Sara, Katya). Russ and Randall are the only respondents who have never worked for other employers except the organisation.

According to the respondents, the experience acquired in a large organisation could qualify for multiple (6-7) roles in multiple (6-7) companies. The same perspective is expressed in regard to performance in consultancy. Early career pathways include entering the organisation from a store level (Jack, Cedric), grad schemes (Francene, Ocado), or trainee programs (Randall). Most respondents mention retail as their first choice of industry, though accounts highlight a pattern for decision making which is driven by certitudes strictly in regard to what options to exclude, not to pursue. The initial career choice is driven by either personal aspirations related to roles and purpose, as visible in Stefania’s search for something stimulating, or by individual assets such as Ardeen’s opportunity to use her language a native speaker of French. Terri explains his

choice of graduate scheme as arising from a preconception about career paths, signalling that early-stage experience highlights adaptability as deriving from compliance with precepts, rather than a quest for innovation.

“I applied for lots of graduate schemes because I thought that was kind of what you did, but that really no one really told me to do it. I just kind of. That's what I thought was the outcome I should be.”

“I guess if I start with my career journey, so when I was probably 14-15, 15-16, probably younger, I used to go around the street cleaning / washing cars to win some more pocket money and I think that it was drilled into me by my parents.”

On a broader perspective, within the same organisation, promotion highlights one's career path as a sequence of complementary roles. Reflecting on his path, Tommie mentions always reinventing himself, whereas Randall considers having been introduced to all functions within an organisation. Randall recollects acquiring a better understanding of the business model when evolving towards a head office role which allowed zooming out of the store's micro-operations and networks to attain a vision of the entirety of synergies connecting the organisation.

“My career was a sequence of me doing all these things and reinventing myself, and every time I got a promotion, I would automatically be looking at the next level in the next level and I would be trying to get myself to a place where I could rub shoulders with them. And. I'm not academic. I haven't got a particularly good vocabulary. I, I wouldn't say I'm the smartest person in the world. And when you start rubbing shoulders with people on next level, they typically are smarter. They've got more experience, so you have to kind... I had to reinvent myself every time as each time to be able to be accepted and then to.”

“I've worked in almost every business area within Sainsbury's with the possible exception of HR and finance, and I think even for finance have done some projects for them in the past so. It was great in in the IT gave me access to lots of lots and lots of different people, different skills, different opportunities. And different banks of knowledge.”

Randall recollects acquiring a better understanding of the business model when evolving towards a head office role which allowed zooming out of the store's micro-operations and networks to attain a vision of the entire synergies connecting the organisation.

“That head office position opened up my eyes because when... when I was in store all you really see is the store or your immediate stores on your area or region or zone. Where is working in head office gave me an insight into all these other interesting areas, so even back then.”

A zoomed-out perspective captures opportunities in both internal resources, as well as macro factors, identifying with higher accuracy the organisation's market positioning, allowing benchmarking, and implementing micro segmentation from societal developments. As an exercise of self-reflection Randall visualises reminiscence as focused on momentums rather than a review of one's entire path.

“Looking at your questions, I suddenly start to sort of progress back in time over my career and you start to sort of think about all these things and ...and take them as a whole. Where is normally when you reminisce, usually about a point in time you think back to an occurrence or an action. A particular point in time, as opposed to the journey.”

“And then I think along that journey probably got until now about four or five different roles and I think each one and each line manager I had along the way, some great, some not so good, but each of them you know, you can take learnings and learnings and move then on to the next person and probably, the biggest thing I learned is how to manage managers, if that makes sense, along the way.”

4.3.1.2.2 Turning points in the career

The fundamental importance of career turning points in the development of one's strategic thinking arises from the pressure of connecting self-efficacy with insights arising from outside the environment which allowed one to acquire intuitive familiarity. As milestones for one's professional becoming, career turning points can be identified both in connection to employers, but also to industries. Career turning points represent pivotal challenges in self-efficacy, as they

push one towards an audit of eventual transferable skills which may not necessarily derive from the competencies they've acquired in an institutional settings such as a qualification or a role, but also from empirical knowledge which could have been attained through informal circumstances such as hobbies or extracurricular activities (e.g., sports). Implying an element of delimitation within one's professional path, career turning points may determine that one questions the intuitive familiarity and thus invalidates the relevance of past experiences used to build precedents on. Career turning points represent therefore a context of reconfiguration of one's own references with inevitable impact on one's reasoning, given the influence of knowledge on cognitive patterns.

“Um, a big one would be when I got back from Ghana, and I didn't know what to do next. Trying to figure that out as a fairly new graduate was difficult and I almost fell into Sainsbury's just, just by chance. Which was great because I think sometimes you need to try things to understand whether you enjoy them or not. A big turning point.”

The respondents' career reconversions are generally driven by the search for more stimulating environments (Sara, Katya, Erin). However, when it comes to the reasons for which they left a previous employer, respondents link their decision to organisational culture and the perception of no more opportunities for growth. Personal reasons invoked by respondent to explain career reconversions include an exhausting lifestyle and parenthood (Antony, Sara) as a milestone that made them re-evaluate their priorities.

“So being a mum actually becoming a mum actually changed my priorities a bit. Had an impact on my aspirations and actually made me want it even more.”

The unknown also motivated Russ' crossover from retail (Tesco & Sainsbury) and strategy consultancy (PWC) to wholesale. As transpiring from their recollection, there was an acknowledgment that an area in the supply chain which their own previous experience derived from inspired the ambition to attain a complete vision of the actual terrain they perform in. Arguments used in recalling their interest in wholesale allow identification of the reasoning

employed in assimilation of random factors as incentives which may further become goals of strategic thinking.

“...had never been in sales, had never been in wholesale and very much wanted to kind of figure out what this world was all about, so, the remix was trying to figure it out.”

For Sara, intrinsic motivation manifested itself through the desire to achieve success in a different background.

“But as you do, after spending a long time at a business, I was always wanting to know that I could be successful somewhere else, you know, that I wasn't just being able to progress because I'd grown up in a business and I had added people would always support me, cheered me on from the side-lines, but I needed to know that I could do it somewhere else.”

Having attained an exhaustive knowledge of the value chain, familiarity with the content reduced both challenges as well as intensity as well as task complexity (Locke & Latham, 2002).

Furthermore, by placing peer support and praise within the brief retrospective enumeration used to describe the conclusion of accomplishment, Sara confirms feedback as an issue of instrumentality and not as a goal, a prospect which would have connected efforts to validation and not to the factual achievement of the targeted state (Antonakis & House, 2014).

“So, I sat on the leadership team. Which was great because that gave me a real breadth of business understanding and really challenged me to be a leader above and beyond my function, right? Because here I was having to understand and be able to contribute to things that were about manufacturing. Be able to contribute to things which are about people and organisational design. Being able to really think about, you know, how do we drive the future of this business, making sure it's future proof in terms of what mergers and acquisitions that we then need to make will see. My background was marketing and sales are really being able to understand what our innovation pipeline would need to look like?”

Consequently, strategic thinking is not limited to detecting routes to accomplishing objectives, but also towards surveying circumstances which act as sufficiently intense stimuli that create new goals. The lifestyle drawn by a particular role represents a key incentive towards a career reconversion, as Melanie highlights when reflecting on the reasons for crossing over from consultancy to retail. Strategic thinking is therefore dependent upon the extent to which benefits can neutralise shortcomings and the time span within which such balance can remain sustainable.

“...the culture they were building up wasn't really a culture that I was particularly enjoyed other than the fact that I learned lots and could progress very quickly.”

Erin and Ardeen argue for ethos and culture as the main criteria that convinced them to join the company after years of experiencing diversified projects within various industries and organisations. Ethos reaches an individual's psychological capital (Li, 2018) indicating concrete application of how their higher professional aspirations can be fulfilled through trainable conduct: the concept of an informal learning process through which one adapts one's personal modus operandi to a company's ethos. Informal knowledge is assimilated subconsciously after being exposed to a given environment (Okoro, 2012). Since it directly influences one's work effectiveness (Drucker, 2006), organisational culture can stand out as a valid argument for which a person could consider changing employers. In connection to organisational culture and ethos, their arguments converge towards autonomy (Drucker, 2006) and the prerogative of making decisions for themselves both in connection to their biorhythm and time management (Sheats, 1968). In connection to the tasks, they're assigned and the instrumentalities they can use to deliver them, flexibility leads to creative thinking which stands out as a paradigm for developing their potential (Pasamar, 2019).

“I think there's a strong culture of flexibility, making sure you know that people make decisions for themselves. I think what is really important is treating people as scheduled, you know...”

Antony mentions culture as the first thing he noted upon entering the organisation. However, his argument is connected not to the organisation itself but to the sector in which he was previously active, indicating the influence of culture to acknowledge one's own purpose (Kazmi &

Naaranoja, 2015). Culture resonates with a person's psychological capital (Liu, 2018), indicating the terrains within which they can explore and capitalise their potential, such as in Antony's case where it revealed a different approach to how he could perform his role and his competencies (Vaitheeswaran, 2008). The rigidity of organisational structures can hinder employee expression, limit the effectiveness of their work, and prevent them from fulfilling their potential, under the limitations raised by transactional leadership (Bass and Avolio, 1993).

“It was a completely different industry, completely different to what I've been used to. The company culturally wasn't a lot different to, wasn't miles away from (a competitor) and ...and most expenses, but the industrial logistics industry was miles away from where I bought had been used in from a retail point of view. Totally different, obviously heavy every unionised. It was culturally it was different. Logistics was different to retail. And I find found that quite difficult in the beginning. Difficult to adjust, so probably I'll probably spend the first few months question whether I made right decision on actually wondering how I got back out of logistics now back outside. Luckily, I didn't get out of logistics.”

Ethos is defined as the principles converging towards the accomplishment of the organisation's mission statement, transpiring from both technicalities and quality standards, but also the values honoured through its purpose and operations, such as sustainability. Organisational culture encompasses the material and intangible values distinguishing the business within its market, such as brand identity, but also the norms establishing roles within its hierarchical structure and the manner in which they communicate and cooperate. Prioritising ethos and culture over financial incentives highlights a similar leadership profile to that of social entrepreneurs. Innovativeness and risk-taking as the two main general traits within entrepreneurship, are complemented within such a profile by proactiveness and a socially oriented manifestation of passion which comprise the exact mindset focussed on ethos and culture (Shahid and Saqib, 2021). While ethos determines that a leader reflect on how their decisions would impact every one of the organisation's stakeholders, culture reminds them of the importance of cooperation.

4.3.1.2.3 Former careers, such as management consulting or military career

Russ, Cedric, Melanie, Rocky, and Peter have entered the organisation after crossing over from consultancy, an extremely dynamic environment in which one must adapt their expertise to technicalities which differ from one project to another. When reflecting on the incentives which had initially attracted them to consultancy, participants argue for novelty and the opportunity to immerse in strategy as a process. In his experience, Rocky attended 35 different industries, all highlighting their own institutional settings, regulatory frameworks, and markets peculiarities. Performing under such exigencies of versatility, Russ describes the experience he earned in consultancy as an opportunity of getting familiar with ambiguity, praising PwC, his former employer for flexibility and providing the challenges which helped him to detect a possible path forward (Wolf K, 1996).

“PwC was probably more just getting really comfortable with ambiguity you know; I was there for half five years. The longer I was there, the more ridiculous the assignment I'd be given to try and go and solve. Yeah, it starts with something pretty tangible, like game, going into administration, tell us what you think the store portfolio could look like and what future operating model is.”

Rocky reveals communication as a terrain in which a professional working in consultancy encounters further dimensions of adaptability, when challenged to explain the peculiarities of an opportunity to investors who are generalists. The acquisition to the appropriate knowledge sets the premises considered in strategic thinking when managing an exhaustive range of clients, as stated by Melanie.

“Your investors are generally generalists. So, you've got to explain it to them and understand the dynamics of the financial situation, market situation, competitive environment so they can make a pretty big decision on do you by the company or not. And that just really round at home.”

“I'm a person that likes to feel knowledgeable about the topic. I don't feel comfortable if I'm just parachuted in and I know nothing about an industry.”

Assessing different expectations within a corporation to those raised along the multiple clients attended through consultancy, Melanie concludes that when applied within a team, the exact same behaviour be perceived so profoundly different that it may hinder the desired alignment for each member's input (Alban-Metcalf, 2013).

“So, this is a big lesson for me. How to really, really, really have a sexy management style to the different people that I'm managing and like that, that situation resolved itself, but it was a big, big learning for me and not an easy one, because like I said like at the beginning, I had worked with hundred different people and had never had such an issue. But I think in a corporation, the expectations are a little bit different as well. So yeah, big learning for me.”

All respondents mention consultancy as an environment which brings the opportunity of an initially fascinating lifestyle which may become in their own way, exhausting. The need for stability within the work life balance determined them to leave the industry.

“I decided about five years in that maybe I didn't want to be a consultant long term because, well laid, the lifestyle is incredibly punishing both from hours, but also the requirement to travel is really high, and while in my 20s early 20s that was amazing, cause, you know, I got to travel the world after a while.”

Josee describes the military as an environment functioning on an extended and intensified set of constraints, in which risks, forecast and timing attain an exceptional dimension. According to Josee, the military trains strategy to improvisation and adaptability, while excluding the prospect of self-limitation.

“In the military like you have, like when you're given a mission, it will be like to have a title. Then you have a task, and you have a uniform unifying purpose. And it's not like just do what I say it's like: do like it's I tell you what to do, not how to do it. So, they say I would like you to go and do this. How you do it is completely like with up to you. And it's like every task has a in order to so whatever the task might be, I want you to construct a fence between your next-door neighbour's house and your house. In order to make a physical barrier that stops like

pedestrians crossing like properties. So, it means... it kind of gives you the purpose of if you can't do offence, what is it you actually have to do in order to achieve your mission? So, any sort of barrier that stops people will do and then you can use your initiative. And the whole military system is geared up to improvising, adapting, overcoming.

You always like when you do stuff in the military in order to simulate stress. You basically don't get sleep as how they kind of do it like physical activity and lack of sleep simulates life. How you have compression, really. So, there's lots of stuff in your training. That's how they really get to you, like a deprived of sleep exhaust you and then you really see your true character and how you make decisions. And lots of that.”

Tommie also confirms the military as a setting which perfects problem solving, challenging strategy by continuously demanding bespoke technical solutions.

“I learnt some technical skills. I had to think about problem solving and I had to calculate things. I had to make things bespoke so we were spending- we would spend- thousands of pounds on things that I would have to take a Stanley knife to it or a sword to it to make things fair. So, you learn about double checking things before you make the cut. You learn to be confident that when you make a decision.”

4.3.1.2.3 THEME 3 – PERSONAL ATTRIBUTES that define a strategic thinking leader

When analysing the leaders 'personas, the researcher's focus is both on the influences assimilated in the interviewees 'cognition, but also how they are placed as variables in deductions. Accounts related to non-professional settings background and lifestyle allow the researcher to extract strategic thinking its raw, non-rational configuration and detect its mutation under additional variables that raise the pressure of accountability, less present in areas of self-management.

4.3.1.3.1 Background and lifestyle as potential factors to developing strategic thinking

The educational background, as well as the early career start highlight an early affirmation of decision making by excluding options which are considered not to be optimal. Nick, Erin, Stefania, and Natalia state that their choice of area of study, as well as that of their career start began with the dilemma of not knowing what path they would like to pursue. Stefania, Erin, Francene, and Josee explain their option through the certitude of prospects they would not desire. Letting oneself be guided towards a career choice by the success rate in the particular field represents a demonstration of both the effect of informal knowledge (beliefs circulating across society) as well as the precedent on strategic thinking (Porter, 1980). For a young person at the age to enrol at university, a stable and high earning career represents a goal requiring strategic thinking. At the same time, age may limit the possibility of self-efficacy (Dartey-Baah, 2015). The education background is eloquent for the formal knowledge, which complements strategic thinking by confirming the eventual dynamics of some variables as facts. The preconception that installs a false deduction on how a certain level of training (a master's degree) is indicative of intelligence descends exactly from the effect of knowledge -in this case, formal - on strategic thinking and goal accomplishment (Simon, 1997).

However, their own professional experience and their rise to their position of authority confirms how leadership is not related to competence and expertise (Alban-Metcalf, 2013), (Caniëls & Gelderman, 2005).

“Interestingly, that when I first started, I didn't really know what I wanted to do, and I think I sort of sometimes got a bit lost in the kind of all everyone's going to be a banker. All you know, you're doing a master's degree and you know you must be really clever and you ...you can go and do things that earn yourself millions of pounds. But I think I was always a bit like I just don't feel very excited by any of this.”

Rocky is the only participant connecting their university choice to the interest in a certain discipline rather than the actual outcome, whether desirable or avoidable.

“I did Economics and Management at university. I did that because I always enjoyed Math. Turns out I enjoyed the management side more than the Economics because it was a bit more

real. It was a bit less theoretical and at the end of that, pretty much everyone on my course went into either Investment Banking or Management Consulting.”

Such pattern highlights risk mitigation as the core behaviour within the untrained decision making in regard to long term effects. Jack is the only respondent who displayed an enterprising character in their childhood years. Entrepreneurial orientations are eloquent for a person’s predilection to risk with a deep effect on their competitiveness (Henderson, 1989), self-control (Thaler, 2015), and ethical thinking.

“I used to go around the street cleaning / washing cars to win some more pocket money and I think that I was drilled into me by my parents. I used to go and be a dinner man, which basically I was playing with the kids and so yeah, arranged whatever they were doing, and I guess, that was really fun and very well paid for what I did.”

Antony mentions owing their knowledge to the organisation’s culture, as they have not attended university.

“I used to go and be a dinner man, which basically I was playing with the kids and so yeah, arranged whatever they were doing, and I guess, that was really fun and very well paid for what I did.”

The sample reveals a proportionate composition between respondents who have an academic training in business and those whose educational background include other disciplines (Mathematics, Biology, Languages, etc) Alternative pathway through which participants cultivated their strategic thinking include military training (Josee and Tommie) and semi-professional sports. Respondents who have experienced living in other countries include Russ (Australia), Erin (Philippines, Ghana), Tommie (Tibet). Erin is the only respondent who comes from abroad, whereas Melanie and Ardeen are born outside the UK as citizens of other countries.

“I finished university, as you know, played cricket for a little bit, which was semi-professional, it wasn't for formal, professional. But I lived between England and Australia for 2 1/2 years, just flying between the summers to play cricket, which is very good fun, very helpful from a formative

experience, because I probably came out of university a little bit immature and you know, I've gone straight from school to university.”, tells Rocky.

4.3.1.3.2 Hobbies and passions of a strategic thinker

Beyond providing a factual context in which an individual could earn a leader status, hobbies and passions highlight the setting in which input is predominately, if not exclusively, driven by intrinsic motivation. Hobbies highlight the ability to construct stakes and goals when they are not derived within parameters such as virtuosity or experience and difficulty levels. The usual coordinates for strategic thinking are replaced with mastery development and a maximised indulgence of the experience itself. Affinities have been mentioned exclusively when the respondent considered them relevant for their path, such as performing in professional sport or opting for retail as a career start with a passion for food (Stefania).

“And then my mum was always saying to me that you know you like good with people like you should be in retail and always thought like what you on about.”

4.3.1.3.3 Personal development as a key factor to strategic thinking

A definition pursued within the data analysis on personal development considers the ability to critically evaluate the knowledge of competencies which can be acquired from every context experienced. Goals therefore mutate towards not neglecting circumstances which might be used for expanding one's skill set. Approaching professional development last within the section of personal attributes may be justified by the necessity of a given individual's career maturity to reflect and properly benefit from such an opportunity.

Notably when contemplating turning points, Katya and Sara point out a realisation of the path they would like to pursue only in contrast to previous roles which provided no intrinsic motivation and revealed no path of further development (Avolio, et al., 1991). Reflecting on his path, Tommie mentions always reinventing himself. Consequently, in career self-management, strategic thinking is directed towards a re-evaluation of individual assets and external opportunities to identify new environments and roles that can provide a longer span for the binomial manifestation of motivation.

Unrelated career switches such as those conducted by Sara, and Katya test one's set of transferable skills. Josee's decision to survey life outside the military or P3's declared curiosity on whether they could start their own business can be assimilated to the same personal goals.

“And at that point I have done about 10 years with the business by now and I was thinking underlines of you know this is just sort of a hit me, I've done 10 years and I've never really thought about what to do. So, I actually left and did a couple other things. I wanted to try and see if I could set my own business up, but the first thing I did was Financial advice, so I went into a company as a financial advisor for about two years, but I soon found out that, really, that was about sales and every meeting I went to realise that every sale was a sale. I... they bought something off me or I bought them. They couldn't afford it or didn't want it, so I assume realised it wasn't mobile. Sales wasn't necessarily.”

4.3.1.3.4 Personal values and their importance to strategic thinking

A scrutiny of personal values is essential for understanding how leaders may use incentives as filter for discerning and advocating organisational goals. From a timing perspective, the awareness of personal values could emerge at any moment within an individual's upbringing and along their immersion in an affinity. However, once acknowledged in a professional setting, personal values establish both an individual's work ethics, as well as their argument when prioritising their goals. Personal values interest research not through the perspective of content but through the critical process that leads to their assimilation, while also considering eventual re-evaluations or changes in their understanding. Purpose represents a cumulus of all personal values.

Purpose transpires from Ardeen, Terri's, Nick, and Sara's intervention, though through a different understanding. To Ardeen, purpose stands in the value one can contribute with. Terri affirms a similar view by mentioning the chance to make an impact or have any kind of responsibility.

“You've left and you haven't really had a chance to make an impact or have any kind of responsibility...”

Nick relates purpose to the rationale behind an action,

“...challenge people towards understanding why they're doing what they're doing.”

whereas Sara regards it as the setting which allowed her to live up to her own values both with, as well as outside work hours.

“Very progressive from a people perspective. Very progressive from a diversity perspective and that gave me another string to my bow in terms of okay what does inclusive cultures look like, what does inclusive leadership look like and really kind of challenge. My thinking in terms of I suppose. But my values were then important to me, you know, in terms of who I was inside of work, but who was outside of work, that was the first time I think working for a business like that where I really started to think about my personal brand. And you know what was important to me?”

What my priorities would be. And how I needed to be fulfilled at work and how I needed work to also be able to have a blend of what I was doing at home, and it was at that point that, you know, I wanted to become a mum. So being a mum actually becoming a mum actually changed my priorities a bit. Had an impact on my aspirations and actually made me want it even more.”

“The motto of Sandhurst is Serve to Lead and you do a lot of leadership studies as you would imagine, joining the army as an army officer and particularly you look into like the simplest bit of serve to lead and what leadership is: what type of leaders, what type of leader you are, and you do a lot of studies there, mainly military leaders.”

The motto draws upon a leader's accountability, their sense of purpose, and the role they carry in uniting groups and collectivises under common values in connection to which they actually develop the service mentioned. The mere idea of service demands deprioritising one's individual

aspiration in favour of common ideals, a challenge expected of leaders in the liaisons they build with subordinates. However, before demanding such a requirement of leaders, the motto signals their moral duty to embody such behaviour first. Exposure to this motto may unconsciously develop the sense of purpose to relation to ethical thinking which increases an individual's reflective and creative skills (Wooton, 2010): these are, for example, vital for military life where one has to continuously contemplate the deepest implications of one's decisions while also originating new pathways for goal accomplishment under new and unexpected configurations of challenges.

The impact on team members is assessed according to how comfortable, stimulating, and satisfactory the assigned task may be perceived in accordance with personality, skills and creativity as these vectors determine the potential to capitalise upon members' knowledge base. As for the impact produced on one's team, the giving-oriented transformation leadership induces the perception of participation, which is itself envisioned as a wider access to decision making. Nevertheless, using the giving-oriented transformation leadership as pattern for strategic thinking succeeds in growing the members attachment to organisational goals which end up being assimilated not as business objectives but ethical values that transcend an institutional framework and which are likely to be claimed as components of one's moral structure (Bonn, 2005). The comprehension of purpose shifts towards one's duties which attain an unexperienced dimension when performing within a disruption. If in a regular circumstance, purpose is rather contemplated in regard to the implications of one's actions beyond organisational settings, disruptive times activate a survival focus which turns leaders towards their team's and their own capacities (Drucker, 1968). Performing in FMCG retail, purpose is reinforced by public praise of participants as heroic keyworkers.

4.3.1.3.5 Temperament, an important component to developing a strategic mindset

Personality has been approached within data collection from two perspective, which would further enhance accuracy as they could allow me to validate my initial interpretation of key insights identified in the responses. Traits claimed by participants within the prospect of self-reflection could be juxtaposed or contrasted with a certain profile they might sketch as preferable for a leader.

Key traits for preference include whether a manager sees human capital as related to the person or the outcome of their work, whether leadership favours a participative approach or not, whether performance assessment favours both inputs as well as output, whether potential is innate or acquired and whether competence is transferable or context dependent. Answers may, however, lead to a coexistence of two profiles. Though many respondents provided views on preferred traits composed of a desirable moral stance and attitude in one's relationship with team members, Randall is the only participant to provide a commentary over the personality recommended for leadership. According to Randall, charisma and stamina provide the appropriate personality that convinces, motivates, and inspires their followers' trust. For Randall, such traits are even more important than intellectual abilities (Collins, 2001).

“They could be, you know, have intellectual upper gazoo, but if they didn't have the personality to go with that intellect, or if they couldn't fake it, then that made them less of a leader and therefore they could have the best strategy in the world. But if they couldn't get that out there, and if they couldn't drag people along with them or they couldn't get people to go with that idea. Tonight, I lost the plot and I think I saw those two or three times with. Big leaders in Sainsbury's who didn't have the personality to go with it. They certainly had the brains. They probably add the ideas, but they just didn't have the personality and that kind of thickness that you need when you're running a company of.”

4.3.1.3.6 Self-reflection, the fundamental element of strategic thinking

As an exercise to recollect and revive the sequence of circumstances and decisions that have led to a given momentum (Gibbins-Klein, 2017), self-reflection represents a bountiful pipeline for understanding one's responsiveness to external stimuli, providing clarity on analytical skills, capacity for critical assessment, rationality, and self-control. Conclusions attained through self-reflection are highly valuable to predict own's own psychological capital with a high impact on eventual future decisions for similar circumstances.

Foregrounding an argumentative construction, self-reflection is manifested as a conclusive element which justifies its place as the end section a series of denominators. Such sequences may

also be supported by the fact that self-reflection is conditioned by a certain experience in a context which would allow a critical evaluation of the particular circumstances. Self-reflection has been approached as process in order to detect if self-evaluation emerges spontaneously or as a parallel deployment to an account inserted by the participants with the purpose of responding to other topics. Nevertheless, a retrospective contemplation may highlight individual triggers and references on which every participant anchors their critical self-assessment and which the researcher could correlate to incentives previously identified amongst personal values.

Scrutinising internal stakeholders, Sarasvup (2020) observes organisational and corporate identities coexisting. Organisational identity can be anchored or diffused within roles, professions, or divisions. Leadership should take into account how a uniform corporate identity is not necessarily attainable. When aiming for role autonomy, strategic thinking may also target the diversity multiple identities which privilege the organisation. Purpose as a cumulus of personal values can be reviewed as experience which expands one's perspectives and readjusts priorities. Nick assimilates leadership to reflect what and why one engages in an activity as opposed to simply executing tasks.

“Surely cause one I'm interested but to challenge the people's thinking about what they are doing and why they are doing this. And if they don't have the answers that then forces them to find the answers down the line, so you know you call it leadership, quality management at the end of the day; I do feel that people have to question what they're doing and why they are doing this, rather than just following the grain.”

The rationale behind one's actions represents the foremost strategy for reconnecting to one's purpose. Accountability, which is mentioned by Rocky as a key guideline for strategic thinking, stands as a direct reflection of purpose, connecting one's personal input to consequences that directly concern one, with implications which range from legal effects to a loss of credibility as a leader. However, the pressure of daily tasks may blur self-reflection as relatedness is shifted from one's purpose to one's most immediate environment. When becoming too accustomed to the mindsets of one's own team, Erin signals the necessity of surveying insights outside one's work group. Such knowledge becomes particularly valuable in the case of details which enhance

the clarity demanded in strategic thinking (Gibbins-Klein, 2017). However, queries conducted outside of one's work group should be oriented, according to Erin, towards a critical perspective on one's potential, and whether it is privileged with the opportunity to deliver an input in the appropriate environment.

"I looked around the business I talked to so many people. And awesome, very specific things. Like where do you think I would fit? Where do you think my skills would shine within the business and we homed in on?"

Rocky points out that strategic thinking also implies self-reflection over points of balance where one can find support when their endurance is challenged. Such focus is vital in a disruptive environment, indicating the limits of self-resilience and areas to be addressed for their improvement.

4.3.1.4 THEME 4 – PROFESSIONAL ATTRIBUTES

Professional attributes have been analysed in correlation to an organisation's resources, competencies, and capabilities, as it is within the institutional setting that both leadership as well as strategic thinking are affirmed. Resources account for an organisation's material and human capital. Competencies describe the knowledge employed for accomplishing the organisation's purpose. Capabilities represent the pathways through which an organisation engages stakeholders to deliver its competencies. Loyalty to the organisation accounts for an individual's receptivity to fulfil the agency behind leadership and to dedicate their hard skills as background to their competencies. Encompassed within an individual's expertise, hard skills have been approached within research as both the person's own knowledge capital as well as contribution to the organisation's competencies. As a product of strategic thinking, communication describes the motivational patterns observed and interpreted by leaders in their team's psychological profile to be further capitalised as a new configuration under which organisational goals are transmitted in order to produce the desired level of loyalty from each individual. Soft skills have been approached as the leaders' ability to identify the fore-mentioned

psychological profile through empathy. Networking represents a proactive strategy of extending a person's or an organisation's capabilities.

4.3.1.4.1 Soft skills, such as communication and networking, necessary to become a strategic thinking leader

Respondents of both gender mention parenthood as a milestone which changed their approach on leadership, teaching them the importance of empathy, as Sara mentions.

“Yeah, it was when I started to understand a lot more in terms of looking and understanding things from other people's shoes. I had a lot more patience. I've been a lot more tolerant. You know my dimension and my outlook really became a lot broader being a mum. So again, that impacted some of the choices that I made in terms of my career.”

When further mentioning empathy in various circumstances of team coordination, they connect it to adaptability. Their recollections associate empathy with the strategy of adjusting their leadership style to any emotional feature which can trigger a barrier in the individual. Therefore, their approach to empathy launches the prospect of confusion with psychological capital (Li, 2018). Such understanding of empathy can be noted also in participants who did not make references to parenthood. Furthermore, parenthood is the only given influence that respondents regard as a potential catalyst for empathy. Mentions of empathy emerge along the interviews in key contexts of either crisis or increased responsibilities, as well as in depictions of teamwork within the COVID-19 pandemic. All mentions converge towards an approach to empathy as a strategy to prevent blockages generated by pressure or to extract the maximum of the detected potential. The cognitive correlations behind the rationalised use of empathy replicate risk mitigation.

Human capital is regarded under optimal parameters of pressure and the exact input it can deliver under various levels of stress. An unforeseen crisis such as performing under extreme dynamics registered in the variables one is working with on a regular basis may trigger an unexpected response both for the co-ordinated individuals, as well as for their leader. An understanding of empathy as the ability to fathom one's feelings is highlighted by most respondents when accounting the benefits of remote working. Individual circumstances such as regaining time

efficiency, as commuting ceases to be an inherent impediment, are never mentioned in connection to themselves, but either through mentions of their direct team or of peers who are not hierarchically related. Such pattern of argumentation reflects a key feature of transformational leadership, notably preoccupation with the team's wellbeing- to prevent circumstances that may hinder their performance.

Arguments brought by respondents when mentioning inspirational leaders who impacted their career most often include the ability to communicate, to support, and to earn one's trust. Melanie, Sara, and Francine agree on clarity as the top goal when setting one's communication strategy (Gibbins-Klein, 2017). Furthermore, clarity should be expressed not only when formulating a message, but also when cultivating a vision (Sara), as well as in establishing one's priorities.

"Inspired by leaders with a clear vision who can communicate that clear vision and motivate people."

"I think the most that I learned from her is just how to be much more concise."

Antony raises an argument on how communication becomes an act of consideration by keeping people in the picture and providing them the premises for growth.

"Communicate even what you don't know. Just communicate, keep...keep people in the picture. Let people grow as leaders, let them make decisions that end."

According to Cedric, empathy provides the clarity to strategize how to communicate with each member in order to encourage autonomy in an effective direction. Within team building, strategic thinking is articulated through adaptive leadership according to the members' distinctive personalities (Denyer, 2020). Strategic thinking redesigns leadership as intrapreneurship, approaching performance and cohesion enhancement as objectives (Carlsson, 2021). As a management approach, intrapreneurship is necessary to communicate organisational objectives along various hierarchical levels. However, horizontal communication emerging between departments requires effectively addressing people of different expertise sets. In

developing the proper narrative, strategic thinking is oriented towards editing, which involves introducing new concepts of a similar meaning to function with the existing ones as a gradual and organic adjustment to change (Drucker, 2006). Cognition becomes vital, as despite being performed on the same concepts, editing is employed by different leaders to address distinctive groups or individuals. Consequently, senior management must focus on surveying concepts that retain their meaning regardless of interpretation. Disruptive events demand a re-concentration of efforts towards the organisation which can only be fulfilled if each component within its structure prevents dispersion for resources, irrelevance for competencies, and blockages to its capabilities (Antoniou & Ansoff, 2004). The organisational resilience is resumed to the stability of its smallest arrangements which can be insured through communication. However, social distancing as a dimension of the disruption may pose a threat to communication by diluting the bond built on proximity and the informal cooperation brought by it. Terri signals a different paradigm to immediacy created under remote working, as communication is more likely to emerge with someone performing the exact same role, though in another country, than with a person found in the physical vicinity.

“I spoke to the person doing my job in France more than the person next to me.”

Randall is the only participant mentioning the benefit of networking, arguing that opportunities arise from conversations. As disruptive events tend to turn organisations' goals towards safeguarding their own resources, networking may become the background for knowledge exchange. Such dynamics are notably visible when addressing mutual goals. In a regular context, an industry initiatives chain is directed towards lobbying as a pathway to earn higher influence before policymakers. Disruptive times shift mutual goals from readjusting their interest in the regular environment in which partners perform to attaining higher responsiveness and to dispersing the eventual impact of a threat (Antoniou & Ansoff, 2004). Connecting partners of complementary missions, strategic alliances such as Feeding the Nation readjusted the supply chain to fix blockages which had been caused by stockpiling as an extreme market reaction, in a timeous manner.

4.3.1.4.2 Hard skills, the indispensable part of performing in a high responsibility role

The attitude towards not being sufficiently knowledgeable is assimilated in the early career to the impostor syndrome which is pointed in the context of increased responsibilities, unexpected promotions, or the first projects participants (Katya, Jack) perceive as defining to their path. Jack regards unfamiliarity to new challenges as specific to early career stages, as experience facilitates the ability to delegate, while concealing eventual knowledge gaps.

“He saw potential in me and promoted me prematurely, which again, it’s like: oh, my god, what am I doing here? I don’t belong here! I am not good as him, I am not good as her. But again, it’s about buying you time and understanding you’re definitely got your strengths, they’ve definitely got their strengths, but with all have weaknesses, right? We could all help each other up something, so yeah, that was cool.”

“I think you know, that further on you get, the bigger you realised that people more senior don't know a lot of stuff, but that they are just great talking and giving you load of higher all the time, right?”

Such a view is also present in Terri who argues that the higher the hierarchical level, the more generalised the attributions, as management duties are developed around the safeguarding of a properly functioning system. The same perspective transpires in different wording from Jack’s perspective when indicating that the higher the position, the fewer the people who have an exhaustive view on everything (Vaitheeswaran, 2018). Katya links this assumption to the mythology circulating around leaders, a preconception which follows team members in their first coordination of responsibilities and which Jack describes as an unnecessary pressure one places on oneself.

“Then manager comes along and says why this happened. You need to this and this. You know, multiple different bits of the business. When I first started, I was definitely: Oh my God! I need to write everything down; I need to give an answer! So, you know, probably tell a few white lies, oh my God, panic, panic, panic; where is now you know, when you understand it more, A:

understand it, but B: you know, nothing is life and death. You don't have to respond straight away. Absorb it! Think about 10 minutes, then process it, then respond."

However, maintaining a smooth flow of operations does not subsume supervision into a passive role, as managers employ strategic thinking in delegating the right people to various tasks and motivating them towards delivering their best potential. Amassing teams of complementary expertise represents the best prevention strategy for time-sensitive contexts of decision-making, as not only does each member provide their input in the optimal span, but the experience of working in a group provides them with sufficient knowledge of how to deliver their insight in a common language (Brown, 1991). Learning how to communicate with people with different areas of expertise is mentioned as a challenge by both P4, as well as Tommie, whose description is 'people who are more educated'. Such concern was expressed in two distinctive settings: either related to one's own regular attributions or in projects in which one's expertise must be applied on unknown territories. This latter context is proper to consultancy, a field in which numerous participants gained their professional experience. According to interviewees who have performed in the field, commissions arrive from all manner of possible industries and cover matters which may fall within highly specialised areas of expertise. Consequently, consultancy does not demand an exhaustive or encyclopaedic knowledge which covers all areas connected to projects, but rather the capacity to extract causalities and connect the observed synergies with insights attained from interpreting data.

Knowledge is found at the root of the expert power, which attracts a following on the grounds of facts. Revealing oneself as having limitations de-prioritises influence gained and sustained through the expert power, which derives not from the leader's guidance, but from the data collected, that they can deliver and consequently, the reassurance and certitudes grounded on demonstrated insights. Transparency on the part of leaders related to limitations attracts trust and relatedness as grounds for the leader-follower relation, raising cooperation. Antony points out that transparency over limitations empowers followers and allows them to grow as leaders. A similar view on transforming the acquisition of knowledge into a common journey in which followers are given, as Antony suggests, the liberty to decide for themselves is found in Peter's belief that leaders should know about asking the right questions.

“I think the greatest thing it gave me is just a professional standard which we talked about, but also the ability to not feel that uncomfortable about knowing the least content in a room. That's okay and I don't worry about that. Now it's about knowing the right questions to ask and being inquisitive and working- working through and working with others to get things to happen. I don't need to be an expert in anything. I'm so fancy that's probably one of the things I've taken from... from consulting. Then I still carry that now.”

Such detachment becomes a bountiful asset when readjusting to a disruptive environment with unfamiliar and unfathomable manifestations, and it reduces the relevance of existing knowledge and calls for estimations (Antoniou & Ansoff, 2004). The more provisions -which by their nature are hypothetical and speculative- confronted the wider the number of scenarios that can allow for identifying risks and reducing their likeliness and impact (Zand, 2010). Compared to the transactional style where hierarchical distance is favoured to mentoring, being transparent about one's limits in knowledge after having exhibited transformational leadership can only raise a sense of relatedness, which has an outstanding effect on the followers' commitment. Relatedness brings a personal dimension to purpose which factually describes an individual's attachment to their role and ideally, to the organisation, shifting such commitment to the work group and thus upgrading the contribution of every follower.

4.3.1.4.3 Loyalty for the organisation that creates bonding

Loyalty can be measured in accordance with the relatedness experienced within given circumstances. In a professional setting, relatedness can transpire from organisational and corporate identities (Sarasvup, 2020). Organisational identity can be anchored or diffused within roles, professions, branches, or divisions, whereas the corporate identity transpires from mission statements and ethos.

Sara's contemplation of relatedness was extended from the common values detected within the organisation's culture to her own feelings outside of work hours. Such concerns highlight how expectations related to one's role become longstanding traits within an individual's personality and self-perception.

“My values were then important to me, you know, in terms of who I was inside of work, but who was outside of work, that was the first time I think working for a business like that where I really started to think about my personal brand. And you know what was important to me?”

Relatedness emerges as an intermediary phase to growth (Alderfer, 2014). Sara’s reflection on how she related to her role inside an organisation and outside of working hours translated into growth through her preoccupation over her own brand. Women leaders balance multiple identities that either disappear or are readjusted as they enter new stages within their career (Pediconi, 2021). The fading process is observed as conflicting identities produce the gradual disappearance of some, whereas transformation implies achieving a fruitful equilibrium between them. The default dynamics of strategic thinking in self-management are oriented towards capitalising on potential and minimising the impact of areas that need improvement. However, Sara’s introspection changes the paradigm of self-efficacy (Bandura, 1977) towards how to capitalise an identity that is exposed to the risk of mutating under the influence of roles. In their majority, the respondents referred to the COVID-19 pandemic in terms of the challenges related to coordinating virtual groups and maintaining the team’s morale. Disruptions registered within the supply chain have only been mentioned by members with intersecting attributions. Such contrasts signal professional identity with the role rather than the organisation. Furthermore, when asked for a view on the future impact of COVID-19 on the market, those focussing on changes to working patterns comprised a proportionate ratio to those offering their previsions on mutations brought about by consumer behaviour. Such filter can be synchronised to statements related to career changes which were in all cases correlated not with the organisational climate and the work environment, but to the incentives found within one’s role (Hudson, 2004). The immediate professional identity is essential to understanding the goals-risks axis on which they would set their goals; whether they prioritise the organisation’s interests or that of their own group (Nanjundeswaraswamy, 2014). Such perspective highlights leadership as key to the perception of purpose becoming more connected to one’s personal contribution rather than to the mission statement affirmed by the company, the initial anchor through which a new purpose-oriented recruit joins an organisation.

4.3.1.4.4 Resilience, probably one of the most important aspects of strategic thinking

Regardless of hierarchies and responsibilities, the pandemic forced an organisation's members to readjust their personal balance mechanisms in the light of unfamiliar stress factors, as well as to adapt their self-management mechanisms to dysfunctions which might appear in their communication with peers or superiors. Finding the right balance between the pre-COVID routine and the benefits revealed with the remote work scheme during lockdown had society testing what may emerge as each member's own prerogative. According to Jack, resilience derives from having the appropriate tools to perform the job.

“From a working point of view, I think people will make it work themselves. I think we've all been told for two days a week in [in the office]. I think some people will go in four days a week; some people will go in no days a week. I think that will be the balance and I think the challenge will be when poor performance starts happening, how do you ever really monitor what somebody's output is when you're not sat with them all the time? I think we will find happy grounds. It's more important that you have a team you can trust. I think we've been given even greater flexibility when we are all working so hard.”

“I also think that having the tools to do the job enables you, or enables us to work how we work, to be successful. I think that's probably the huge one of on resilience, having the tools to do the job enables the companies to be resilient through these times.”

However, Jack warns about issues related to identifying the causes of poor performance when remote working will make it difficult to monitor output. Trust becomes vital when implementing and coordinating efforts within different working styles that integrate different scales of remote output. Jack's analogy of virtual and real-life presentation indicates a perception of remote working as a framework which neutralises the pressure of issues which might make each member uncomfortable. Eliminating negative emotions which affect self-efficacy brings more clarity and diminishes the perception of individual 'weaknesses'.

4.3.2 ORGANISATIONAL AREA

4.3.2.1 THEME 1 – INDUSTRY, a defining factor that can shape the mindset of a leader

Consumer behaviour represents the driving force of the retail sector, determining innovation in both product development (as highlighted by the readymade meals which stand out as the solution which may neutralise the threat of substitutes) as well as in the value delivery paradigm. Observations of the retail industry during Covid highlight perceptions over the dimensions of the market share, the scale targeted within growth strategies, and the margins accepted in stagnation and decrease before reports become a subject of concern. In a disruptive setting, an analysis of the retail sector reveals quantitative metrics for goals, performance, and predictions over impact, as well as the stakeholders prioritised in an emergency context. Retail culture interests research in regard to how values, norms, conventions, and ethics converge towards purpose as the sum of an individual's personal values. The future of the retail industry is addressed in this study with regard to the prospect that the current paradigm for performing within the market maintains its relevance. When analysing the interviewees' vision, data interpretation follows both predictions of instrumentalities as well as eventual time spans in which they could be implemented.

4.3.2.1.1 Customer behaviour, an aspect that impacts leaders' ability to deliver results

As the physical implications of the legal restrictions have shaped a new understanding of convenience, consumer behaviour is analysed through the possible mutations generated by the pandemic on purchase patterns.

The participants agree in unanimity that the pandemic will push consumers towards online grocery shopping. A particularly insightful reflection comes from Stefania's analysis of consumer behaviour as observed within recent years. Beyond the pandemic context, Stefania warns about the impact of a high convenience lifestyle on supermarkets which can then be assimilated into a macro threat which makes an organisation's competencies irrelevant.

“But we haven't got lazier as a species that basically things have been put in place to make us more lazy. So, for example, if you can buy a packet of ready cooked chicken and he's on your lunch

break, but it costs 100% more than buying a chicken breast and cooking and taking into the office and packing it and remember taking it from the fridge. The nine times out of 10, if you have got the cash to do it, then you probably choose the kind of second one and less unless you've got that kind of will power not to. So, I think that's been really interesting, because obviously those convenience that really high convenience lifestyle of like breakfast and lunch in city centres has forced us off changing behaviour first reverse and say, well, I'll eat my breakfast at home. Are you my lunch at home? But if I had a Pret that was a 3-minute walk from my house. Wooden I just walked the Pret like I used to walk to the office because prepping my lunch when I'm short on time is difficult.”

When it comes to challenges, the same cognitive pattern focuses on the exact pressure and severity of external forces such as global disruptions and the effective and efficient organisation of internal resources. If the juxtaposition of these two does not provide the grounds for an organisation's resources to neutralise threats, cognition is then focused on developing scenarios of impact and recovery time spans (Schoemaker, 1995), regardless of the considered area of action (management of markets, intermediaries, knowledge, as well as competitive scenarios, or global configuration of value-generating). The highly convenient lifestyle pointed out by Stefania elevates the threat of substitutes (Porter, 2008). The organisation responded towards a growing trend of eating out by developing ready-made meals; however, as reflected within Stefania's analysis, strategic thinking should be oriented towards identifying the exact scale and occurrence of the threat, as such trend may be present within given demographics (professionals who readjust their time efficiency through on-the-go meals) and not in the overall population. Furthermore, scrutinising the exact scale of the threat demands mapping the territorial presence of key substitutes, such as Pret à Manger. Dedicating the same attention to substitutes as to the organisation's capacity for defence reduces the risk of over-evaluating the threat and diverting the customer base in areas where no additional action is needed.

4.3.2.1.2 Retail culture assessed in relation to the research question and its impact of the strategic thinking leader

Culture has been the argument through which the organisation attracted participants who built experience working for competitors. However, culture also became an incentive for participants

from other industries such as Ardeen. Aspiring towards creating, through leadership, an environment in which team members were seated like family, Ardeen praises the organisation as having a culture of flexibility which grants every member the prerogative of deciding for themselves. The enormous diversity of thought is also mentioned by Rocky who regards organisational structure and culture as the framework which can ensure the smooth flow of decision making, and consequently, as members feel more comfortable with systematic implementation of change, they are more willing to co-operate with it (Evans & Salaiz, 2019). Change should be the responsibility of those assigned strategic tasks and not an additional pressure factor on every member.

4.3.2.1.3 Retail industry, home of the leaders interviewed in this thesis

The only area for value creation in which strategic thinking can be employed in an already established environment such as the retail industry is the autonomous revenue growth (Van Straten 2019). Compared to the inter-connected cost reduction, leverage, balance sheet restructuring, the causality between price and earnings and the synergy between buying and building, strategists are notably concerned with autonomous revenue growth for the unknown outcome it may produce. Strategic thinking is therefore mostly driven by uncertainty. The external stakeholders' perspective would, however, explain the connection between buying and building, as customer loyalty descends from a purchase experience complemented by other stimuli rather than costs. Jack finds cost leadership goals 'uninspiring', whereas competitive advantages arise from the whole spectrum of customer experience and not only from the pragmatic benefits within purchase.

“This whole “New winning food” [Sainsbury’s current strategy] thing it is ambitious enough, or it’s just that we’re lowering some chicken breasts and matching Aldi’s prices? If that’s all we’re going after, that’s pretty uninspiring for me. Where is the “we’ve got great customer service,” “we’ve got point of difference,” “we’ve got great food”? They need to figure out what we’re doing with that. To be honest, I am not overly impressed with it.”

Such a perspective can be correlated to both internal as well as to external stakeholders. When applied to internal stakeholders, the term ‘uninspiring ’ may be associated with the lack of challenge as catalyst to strategic thinking. As one implemented through the appropriate scale parameters, cost leadership does not require further interventions, whereas the market positioning in which it places the organisation reduces its growth terrains.

4.3.2.2 THEME 2 – INFLUENCING FACTORS

The reviewed literature signals the role of practical knowledge in adjusting cognition within strategic thinking. Patterns of cognition as highlighted by various circumstances are acknowledged and analysed in accordance with their distinctive traits. Experiences are being perceived according to variables and causalities, which may replicate or not, allowing anticipation and an effective reaction. Consequently, challenges are elevated by situational uniqueness. As strategic thinking may be privileged by such familiarity in discerning a context, the researcher’s interest is to identify whether the positive-negative binary is set in accordance with circumstances, outcomes, or promptitude and effectiveness in delivering a response. Nevertheless, the researcher is interested in how empirically gained knowledge has been complemented by theory.

4.3.2.2.1 Challenges that strengthen a leader’s mindset

As uniqueness forces strategic thinking towards extracting common patterns that may highlight an already experienced deployment, challenges transpire from criticism, which can be perceived as a contestation of one’s capability to understand and react to circumstances they considered themselves familiarised with. Whether faced in an individual setting or as a representative of the organisation, respondents exhibit a high receptivity towards criticism as a pathway for improvement (Eppink, 2003). Such attitude is explained by the fact that strategic thinking continuously returns to precedents and difficulties to conclude over particular circumstances, maintaining the risk of facing the exact experience when confronted with the same context. Erin states that having capitalised on a negative response in a career progression attempt she used the opportunity to attain a better diagnosis of her skillset and what move she should target next. A key

insight attained by Cedric in his experience as Trading Support Manager is that solutions emerge from feedback (Abraham, 2005).

“...a new launch of assistant called Oscar which was about customer complaint costs recovery from suppliers. That's basically what I've been doing since 2016, and as part of that evolution I was the one person dealing with it. We then decided to create a team of Supplier Support, hence why I am now Supplies support supervisor or manager, and then we incorporated Oscan cost recovery.”

Cedric maintained focus on customer complaints, which was seen as the core pipeline for system error detecting (Abraham, 2005). Using passion and perseverance as an axis for entrepreneurial orientation, Mohammadi (2021) signalled the continuous reconfiguration of a bricolage behaviour through risk taking, innovation and proactiveness which were a response to the challenges of resource-scarce environments. While responding to feedback stands out as the definition of proactiveness, confronting discontent as articulated through complaints indicates that risk taking is a form of micro-crisis management. Communicating within a setting of adversity exposes the organisation to reputational risks if addressees perceive the response to complaints dissatisfying either in essence, formulation, or proposed solutions. Restoring client satisfaction calls for going outside of the policies which generated the customers' complaints and manifesting innovativeness.

4.3.2.2.2 Criticism, a constructive factor

Erin states having capitalised on a negative response in career progression attempt by using the opportunity to attain a better diagnosis of her skillset and what move should she target next.

For Francene an issue of dissatisfaction comes with no possibility to extract an insight out of negative feedback.

“You got everybody's negativity and none of the lesson.”

Strategic thinking continuously returns to precedents and difficulties to conclude over particular circumstances guarantees the exact experience when confronted with the same context.

4.3.2.2.3 Negative experiences, as lessons learnt

Participants do not describe less comfortable situations as ‘negative’, but rather as ‘challenging’. Accounts of such circumstances witness that they were used to deliver a clear view of the context and to facilitate problem solving. Further, every account of a less comfortable situation is approached in connection with the lessons it could provide. Referring to a dissatisfying memory as ‘not a highlight’, Melanie recalls not being pursued, though aligned with the authority, and having her vision augmented by data. Recollecting a personal crisis in which she was unfairly overlooked for a promotion, if faced with the opportunity of going back in time to fix the problem, Stefania would have addressed the issue with the only superior she trusted, highlighting the critical importance for leaders to inspire their team while engaging in mutual feedback (Ansoff, 2019).

“Is... There is a bit bad... missed out that at the time when I left, I was working for my very first manager, said someone I really respected. And... I... feel like we could have worked something out together if I'd been more open honest about how I was feeling, but I felt like I had been.”

Nevertheless, negative experiences may also be related to one’s personal life. As a resilience mechanism after losing her mother, Stefania channelled her grief into work.

4.3.2.2.4 Positive experiences that build confidence

Accounts of positive experiences highlight different incentives when placed along career trajectories. In early career stages, positive moments are related to empowerment (Melanie) and participation in strategy formulation (Erin, Katya, Sara)). Career reconversions point out satisfaction in earning their teams’ acceptance as peer or leader. Maturity in leadership connects positive experience to problem solving (Ackoff, 1978). The changes noted in the incentives behind positive experiences recreated the ERG theory. Self-expression may be regarded as indicative of relevance which can be regarded as a basis for existence. Relevance within one’s role can be shifted towards that within one’s group, which leads to relatedness. Growth changes the perspective from the contribution which one can deliver within a group to that which one can add to an organisation, as expressed within the problem – solving.

4.3.2.3 THEME 3 – LEADERSHIP viewed as the focus of the participants

The foremost focus has been directed towards extracting a pattern used in discerning one's own experience as a subordinate when assigned co-ordinating attributes in order to assess how task delegation and team motivation is first perceived when becoming a leader. Also from a chronological perspective, accounts of inspiring figures highlight the first examples of leadership they were exposed to that they could further integrate or replicate in their own style. As the direct beneficiaries of leadership, the researcher was particularly interested in the interviewees' relationship with their team members. Working in teams has been viewed by the respondents through the prism of the challenges of coordinating talents with emphasis on reaching consensus, maximising each members' wellbeing, and ensuring a background in which they can effectively express their individuality. As the ultimate application of transformational leadership, perspectives on coaching and mentoring are vital for understanding how leadership shapes their perception of other people's potential, how they combine their responsibilities with communication techniques to upgrade talents and how to readjust their coordinating approach to a continuously up-skilled team.

Though not envisioned, an approach to leadership in accordance with gender has been introduced by the interviewees. If introduced in the interviewees' accounts, female leadership has been exclusively correlated with stamina, a trait never mentioned in the description of men, highlighting therefore distinctive expectations according to gender, albeit from individuals fulfilling the same responsibilities. Advanced within the interviewees' responses were reflections on toxic leadership, highlighting how one's inner approach on coordinating a team could be crystallised by judging conduct deemed ineffective, having one's personal experience as filter.

4.3.2.3.1 Becoming a leader, as a purpose

Interviewees describe their transition towards leadership through the lens of understanding and further communicating a purpose. This process also entailed surveying the instrumentalities according to which goals can be accessed and using structural intuition to help formulate coherent insights while adapting such a methodology for each industry in which they get to perform. While focusing on the importance of data to explain decision making, none of the

respondents rejects or disregards the role of intuition, albeit without providing a personal interpretation of the concept and any insights on its triggers and manifestation. Eventual correspondences to intuition may transpire from mentions of a leader's capacity to identify patterns (Goldman, 2015). However, such perspectives are rather introduced as an abstract phenomenon, rather than in the form of concrete examples.

A leader's responsibilities can be connected to two main areas: delivering a purpose and employing the appropriate instrumentalities for its accomplishment. The purpose represents the objective rationale justifying the institutional arrangement in which leaders exercise their influence, as in product development. Instrumentalities covers the methods used for allocating resourcing, including team coordination.

The purpose and instrumentalities pursued in leadership can be understood through the rational and non-rational cognitive elements which may also explain the correlation between entrepreneurial passion as catalyst, orientation as decision and behaviour as product (Zollo et al, 2020). The respondents' prioritisation of data signals the predominance of linear thinking, which is reflected in rational cognition. By contrast, nonlinear thinking is fostered within intuition-based processing mechanisms. Linear thinking becomes fruitful to articulate orientation through an effective behaviour, yet it is the nonlinear thinking that gears passion into orientation. By focusing on the ability to recognise patterns, respondents appear to understand intuition as familiarity (Whipps, 2014). Team coordination represents the fertile terrain to demonstrate such a hypothesis. Jim regards leadership as a mix between innate traits and knowledge acquired through exposure to a learning-oriented organisational culture (Pasamar, 2019). Flexible leadership styles which are adapted to every member's distinctive personality are, in Jim's opinion, the product of corporate environment (Hudson, 2004).

“You know, I think that was probably quite a good example for me an. I think you know; I think from being in the workplace you see some really different examples of ...of leadership styles.”

“A bit of both. I think people always say that a good strategic leader or lead in general is someone who is genuine and authentic. And I think there are people in the business who you see come across as really genuine, really enthusiastic there. You know, warm there, liked because of

that an. I do think that it can be. Things can be changed, improved in the corporate environment too, so you know there are changing leadership skills, seminars, and books that you can read. And I think you can probably. You can probably tell the sort of leaders who have spent the time learning versus those, probably that happened. And. You can probably tell who those are able to kind of adapt their style for different audiences, different environments and those who can't to be the in terms of. Is it kind of innate? In yours? It is it learned learning. I think it probably is a bit of both.”

Acquired knowledge is more likely to be driven rationally, whereas innate traits are more likely to manifest themselves instinctively. Contemplating the experience of working with an outstanding number of people through temporary teams amassed for weeklong projects, Melanie argues the factual inability to understand one's peers' styles and adapt their modus operandi to one's own. Under time pressure, strategic thinking is oriented towards minimising inefficiency and prevention of risk, thus self-management is deprioritised in respect of the benefits reached through consensus. Melanie's perspective highlights the impracticability of the Authoritarian style even under time pressure and extreme circumstances- the only contexts in which leadership theory described it rather as tolerable than recommendable (Scheidlinger, 1994).

“I ended up working with a lot of people, which is great experience on. You gotta spend even a day understanding how other people work. You just have to kind of go in and be like okay here the expectations. This is how we're going to work.”

The necessity to adjust to other styles has been reiterated by respondents with experience of travelling and conducting businesses around other cultures. In retrospect, Melanie expresses appreciation of this challenge when assessing the insights gained on the impact of a career start. Both Jim and Melanie point out how effective motivation depends on the leader's capacity to get accustomed to their team, whereas empathy as a ground for establishing communication is highly dependent on the quantity and meaningfulness of human interaction.

4.3.2.3.2 Female leaders that inspire

Randall argues that women are more likely to acquire knowledge due to thought flexibility, in contrast to men who tend to be sabotaged in this aspect by their tunnel vision. Except for

Randall's account, when praising female leaders, gender is exclusively mentioned by women (Melanie, Stefania, Katya, Francene, Ardeen). Men name inspirational figures in a chronological order, according to the moment in which they started working with the mentioned individuals. Participants highlight a gendered association with some of the core features attributed by literature to leadership styles and the integration of knowledge. Two out of four participants evoking female leadership connect it to determination and strength. Determination emerges through the patterns of goal orientation, whereas strength can be regarded as a manifestation of self-efficacy. Goal orientation can be rather connected to numeric (Wootton, 2010) and design thinking (Knight et al, 2020), as it implies the ability to correlate actions to a quantifiable outcome, as well as to the pathways to achieve it. Self-efficacy relies on a clear vision of one's values, convictions, and work ethics (Dartey-Baah, 2015). Female leadership is associated with a protective, mother-like attitude, which to an extent can be connected to a higher accountability towards one's team- a key trait of transformational leadership. Women are also associated with higher abilities of assessing the required knowledge for decision making. According to the participants, such knowledge can be connected to either objective facts (figures) or the intuitive familiar (Sloan, 2019) The contrast suggested between the broader perspective and tunnel vision can be translated as the ability to predict outcomes by integrating more levels of magnitude (Gallup, 2015) through either time orientation (short, medium, long term) or inter-dependencies (within the work group, department, or organisation).

If the traits attributed by each of the participants to female leadership are amassed within a singular profile, the resultant, hypothetical person would combine task-oriented as well as people-oriented leadership (Bajcar et al, 2015).

"Girls are far more, you know, wider of knowledge and more accepting when you're a bloke, you're a bit more tunnel vision."

"That kind of that she was absolutely amazing for me both it too. So bright so driven. Almost too driven, I think, and also like really changed my attitude towards women in the workplace.", says Stefania.

Also, Russ recalls:

“...she was the first female to make director level at Tesco, you know, just a work ethic, seconds, and none, really... If you don't know her, she's actually very, very tough, but if you know where she's like the most protective, almost mother hand, and just absolutely brilliant in terms of being there to kick about ideas in terms of 'should these be the numbers' or 'shouldn't they, 'how would you think about changing our workstyle, etc...”.

While Melanie posits:

“I've always been impressed with very strong female leaders, and I've had the luck to work for several of them.”

4.3.2.3 Followership as importance in becoming a leader

Cooperation is regarded by Jack as the outcome of group cohesion, which Russ argues as sine qua non, considering data and knowledge are useless in the absence of a team (Gu, 2015). As a prior stage to group cohesion, participants believe in consideration (Sara, Lack), growth – oriented feedback (Nick, Stefania), and the importance of acknowledging the merits of everyone in the team (Jack) (Bonn, 2001).

“People are willing to do it because they genuinely care about each other, not just terrified to do it.”

“Actually, it doesn't matter if you've got 90% of the answers, 75% of the answers, 100% the answers... if you've got 0% of the people.”

Team co-operation has also been prioritised by Cedric when recruiting, but within virtual team building within the context of remote working where he prioritised a reaffirmation of common goals followed by insight into his plan for coordinating their achievement. Upon a commitment to team recruitment, strategic thinking capabilities on the part of each individual was determined

key to every project's potential outcomes, as was their profile ability to co-perform with others (Henderson, 1989). Remote working may arise within a context in which a team has already been established, thus has already achieved group cohesion. Consequently, the approach of coordination in remote working is oriented towards safeguarding the existing bond by focussing on the member's wellbeing (Cedric, Stefania, Katya).

"I had a small team now hired to be bold, incredibly different to one another and both of characters I had managed before."

4.3.2.3.4 Inspiring leaders throughout the career of the participants

When enquiring about an inspirational figure that they regard as influential to their own leadership style, the participants launch four distinctive perspectives. The first is knowing what kind of leaders one does not want to become (Stefania, Jim). The second is praising inspirational leaders or role models. The third comes from rejecting the prospect of role models. The fourth reflects on the extent to which exposure to multiple leadership styles allows developing one's own. As highlighted in the following commentary, all perspectives set the terrain for transformational leadership.

One's leadership style represents all the managerial approaches one has been exposed to when performing roles of subordination. Recollections converge on the psycho-emotional response to the approach employed when being delegated tasks, as well as the clarity within each assignment (Gibbins-Klein, 2017). The personal filter discerning the direct impact of leadership styles correlates such impressions as Jack calls 'learnings' to each individual's ethics.

"...stay true to myself."

Clarity as a fundamental requirement within both communication as well as goal formulation dominates responses on the foremost lessons extracted from inspirational leaders (Gibbins-Klein, 2017). As for a moral profile, inspirational leaders are supportive, humble, earn their followers' trust, work on their team's morale, and reflect on how decisions impact people.

Though systematically reappearing along all the participants' responses, empowerment in terms of decision making should emerge cautiously, after providing the appropriate technical and moral support for a follower to fully capitalise on the given autonomy (Urbano, 2018). As Jack confirms, a personal experience in subordinated roles highlights the Authoritarian style as the direction not to be followed when ascending towards a hierarchical position complemented by assistance. However, the discontent expressed when reflecting on the confusion generated by the difficulties in accessing comprehensive feedback excludes the Laissez Faire approach by leaders as frustrating rather than empowering.

“I think that, as a manager you have to take the good things you've learnt along the way and recognise the bad things and try not to them yourself.”

Unorthodox leadership praised by Melanie, Russ, Jack, and Stefania as a particularly bountiful opportunity for growth launches a point of reflection on the insights gain when discerning positively or negatively challenging behaviours. The exposure to unorthodox leadership is contemplated as an insight into what approaches to integrate as well as to what behaviours to avoid in team coordination. The participants' view on unorthodox leadership highlights a hybrid approach between the transformational and the authoritarian leadership style. As a trait of transformational leadership, guidance is characterised by an imperative approach which is inherent in an authoritarian style. The imperative dimension to guidance highlights the authoritarian approach as a transformation. As Russ confirms, such manifestation of guidance can take the form of being forced towards the explorative knowledge attained by understanding all facets of the role. The unorthodox leadership approach combines a directive approach with a participative one. Though agreeing to a partial acknowledgement of the team members' individual input, unorthodox leaders retain the prerogative of controlling decision making. The participative component emerges under certain limitations as the team members' input appears to only be accepted under constant testing of the certainty of their own proposals. Such an approach reminds of the observations of Henkel (2011) as to how decision making in the Go game relies on reasoning more than calculation. Nevertheless, unorthodox leadership is deeply related to thinking outside the box and the enthusiasm for novelty.

“He’s kind of like a massive inspiration to me. That said, it could have frustrations with her as well. I feel like she was quite proud person at times. So, say I think I’ve taken a lot from her in terms of who I’d want to be as a manager, but I’ve also taken stuff that I don’t want to be that I feel like I almost over admired her and I think it was partly because she used to have a bit of an approach, which was you go to and say hello. I would like to do this XYZ way, and she’d say no, no do it this way and then you go and do it that way. The way that she wanted to do it and then she kinda go. You should have done it XYZ, which was like the 1st way that you presented it to her, and I feel like I have to be really careful not to kind of flip flop around like that cause I know what kind of frustration that drives.” (Stefania)

“...my first experience of management on me in that shop was awful and it had, probably, the biggest influence on me before having an office-based job. He [his manager] was just relentless in, you know, you could never...there’s always more to do. And he drilled that into me. He could ring me up anytime, any other day and say like: can you do this? Since I went through that, it was really, really good and it pushed me to do more.” (Jack)

“And to some extent we were very similar, types of personality, to some extents were opposite ends of spectrum. So, he’d left school at 16, started in Tesco supermarkets filling up produce, worked his way through Tesco to get to the store manager and for probably the first month he hated the idea that, you know, an Oxford graduate could come in and within six months gets what it’s taken him 20 years to get. So, [he was] really tough, but, very, very fair and you know, [he] put me onto nights [shifts], put me onto Sundays [shifts], did everything to see if I was just going to say, you know, that “I don’t want to do this!” (Russ)

“She’s also very, very forward thinking and forward looking and never afraid to try something that’s quite different and quite new.”

Authoritarian leadership is generally advanced by respondents as toxic in some degree. Toxic leadership inhibits expression through an authoritarian, egocentric, disinterested, or a dismissive style, disregarding clear and comprehensive guidance, thus dispersing focus, and failing to deliver basic ethics. Although a less comfortable approach, unorthodox leadership aims to

empower followers through self-discovery and self-management by testing their limits to strengthen their focus, confidence, and ethics, while teaching adaptability and responsiveness under pressure. The unorthodox leadership can be associated to the neo charismatic model (Urbano, 2018). When describing one of the most influential figures she has gotten to work with, Stefania cited a modus operandi in which a leader would dismiss an activity planning within task management by indicating another succession of steps just so they could later criticise the approach and suggest the initial proposal. A similar experience is accounted by Russ who describes his first inspirational leader as putting him into the most challenging settings to test his willingness to see all aspects of the job and consequently, to grow.

“But then once I came through that passage of time, he was just absolute brilliant you know, my biggest advocate with his boss. We spent hours each day teaching me about the tricks of the trade and all the things that would ordinarily take years to learn by doing. He just taught me the theory and then let me practise and then, because of that Tesco kind of move even quicker and said after about three months, gonna be a store manager.”

Such leadership style reiterates the importance of confidence one one’s own choices which further derives from the appropriate due diligence within decision making which should also survey the outcome of alternative approaches. Natalia also mentions having worked with leaders who challenged one towards coming to conclusions oneself.

“I’ve had three really amazing bosses at ... who have just been very supportive, you know, give you enough sort of guidance to be able to come to conclusions yourself, and I think that’s what’s being really, really great for learning.”

Consequently, strategic thinking is constructed on the strength of claims in conjunction with a continuous review of feasibility. Furthermore, testing methodologies extended by alternative approaches eliminates the influence of subjective factors such as presumption of superior knowledge associated with hierarchical positions. Melanie invokes unorthodox leaders when mentioning their flair for experimenting with an alternative modus operandi, even in the absence of a precedent which may confirm or infirm effectiveness.

Unconventional approaches to problem solving can also be connected to informal behaviours or attitudes (Alban-Metcalfe, 2013). Jim's first display of genuine leadership came from a university professor who gained their students' following after engaging with them in informal contexts such as going to the pub.

"I think he had a very kind of open and honest style. Either he was willing to go for a drink at the pub or go for a coffee with you know with us after a lecture that I think actually helped her build rapport and probably confidence in him too. And you know helped her to build his reputation as a leader, and which I think is important, you know, insomuch as the ability to kind of commands silence when you're speaking in a room, or to ensure that people are submitting the... the work that's required to a higher standard and on time, and that you know people are genuinely interested in it. Yeah..."

Receptivity towards informal settings facilitates relatedness and reaches intrinsic motivation which can further nest the outcomes targeted through transformational leadership (Avolio, et al., 1991). Another manifestation of leadership on the professor's part to make an impression on Jim was not providing highly detailed guidelines but trusting their students' intuition to understand the assignment. Articulated through brief, vague, and flexible indications, strategic thinking is channelled towards stimulating alternative or complementary projections of the same issue which can further contribute to problem solving and expand knowledge by sharing the epistemology in the professor's case or the deductions in an everyday setting. Disruptive environments signal the exact necessity, as they call for participation and mutual exchange of knowledge which can allow risk mitigation (Antoniou & Ansoff, 2004) (Gianos, 2013).

Informality may also take the form of unconventional language and manifestations of temperament which Stefania perceives as 'being oneself'. A similar view is expressed by Natalia in regard to revealing oneself with one's own concerns and being able to become emotional in the situation.

“One particular boss she is so she juggles so much so she's a mum she's got two young kids and she you know that's obviously like a massive commitment in terms of time and emotional energy that that goes in into that. But she... she somehow manages to juggle that. And being just a general generally really present and really good boss. And I think that's something that's kind of really inspiring as well because she's open enough to talk about all the stuff that she's got going on, which makes her a real human being, but she doesn't. - it doesn't actually seem to impact her capacity for work as well, which is just quite impressive, I think. Yeah, to have so much going on and not to affect your leadership style or your capacity of work. That is quite something. Yeah. Sometimes I also think because when... when you get to know somebody more on a personal level and understand the sorts of things that they're having to deal with a like to juggle outside of work. It just I really actually think it's- it just gives people like so much more respect. When you think, wow, that is just so impressive that you're doing all of this and all of that. So, from a leadership perspective, I think that it's actually amazing.”

Genuineness provides the basis for trust and is fundamental in transformational leadership. The respondents highlight trust within a bidirectional deployment: reflected in the leader's persona or manifested towards the followers' performance. Basic business theory points out that unlike managers, whose authority is invested formally, leaders earn their legitimacy through the impact they have on an audience -who become sufficiently inspired to follow them. Such informal investment is grounded on trust. When emerging from the leader towards their followers, trust is expressed through support and motivation, two key attributes dominating the participants' responses.

Nick is the only participant who stated not having ever regarded any figures along his path as role models, arguing he doesn't operate this way. The word use 'role model' does not allow an equivalence with 'inspirational' or 'insightful'. Such a position does not exclude acknowledging a distinction between exposure, experience, esteem, and mentorship. Not operating through role models could be understood as not considering the benefit of having a behaviour which could establish someone's career shaped by another individual, regardless of the qualities transpiring from their own conduct. Not operating through role models does not cancel the presumption of esteem, as it can acknowledge merit while remaining sufficiently self-aware to admit that replicating a person's behaviour could not favour another one's own skillset, personality,

experience, or interests. Nevertheless, not operating through role models does not reject the prospect of a given interaction being insightful, without standing out as inspirational. However, what not operating through role models can be assimilated to is the belief that no universal formula can guarantee effectiveness in any circumstances (Tanveer, 2018). Nick's stance highlights a common trait linked to its exact opposite, as both rejecting role models as well as praising their influence reflects critical thinking.

Though mentioning both negative as well as inspirational figures amongst his leaders, Jack opens a new perspective that may be regarded as within the vicinity but not equivalence to Nick's. Jack argues that exposure to different leadership styles limits the premise of being able to build one's own. In contrast, Melanie believes that working with different people helps one to develop their own style and recognise the values they stand for (Abraham, 2005).

"I ended up working with a lot of people, which is great experience on. How do you manage your own style when you work with people that have different styles and how do you very quickly figure that out as there is no like when you're on a four-week project, you can't? You gotta spend even a day understanding how other people work. You just have to kind of go in and be like okay here the expectations. This is how we're going to work."

Jack's stance does not qualify as scepticism and reserve but reflects the appeal of critical thinking. However, alike in Nick's case, the logical negation supports the exact argument. Exposure to and direct experience of a given leadership style privileges an individual with the opportunity to form a critical opinion on the particular approach, as well as to detect potential cognitive and behavioural patterns (Alban-Metcalf, 2013). Arrangements in which one leadership mode is exclusively directed towards one individual are unrealistic in an organisational setting, whereas they may be found in contexts such the relationship between athletes and their trainer. Consequently, exposure to and direct experience of a leadership style allows one to observe and reflect upon the effectiveness of the given personality traits within such as style of leadership. Nevertheless, exposure or direct experience allows one to detect eventual variation within one's approach and the arguments by which they anchor their shift such as in the follower's personality type, experience, age, et al; but also, by evaluating the legitimacy

of these premises (much more so if they become the grounds for abuse and discrimination). Even if focussed on not replicating witnessed behaviours, exposure and direct experience benefits the goal of developing an individual leadership style by providing insights on the circumstances and levels of adjustment which should be considered within flexibility and adaptability.

4.3.2.3.5 Mentoring and coaching as important aspects in both becoming a leader and leading successfully

The contrast between transactional and transformational leadership (Bass, 1985) can be readapted into a further demarcation between commanding and coaching. While the former is exclusively related to task assignment and may be followed by a discretionary performance assessment, the latter communicates objectives while providing the appropriate guidance which transforms their accomplishment into mutually beneficial experience. Through transformational leadership, task performance becomes a pipeline for growth, which can be deployed in two main phases: motivation, which is built on empathy, and empowerment, which is materialised through work autonomy (Caniëls, 2018). Motivation descends from an acknowledgement of merits which is formulated to conjoin the output to the circumstances characterising the challenge.

“The biggest thing for me is reminding everybody the great job they’re doing how hard it is.”

Melanie states that feedback provided by a mentor provided the most valuable insights.

“...opportunities to be specific and firm enough with feedback, but also incredibly kind. And delivering that feedback. I still use that as... as inspiration how I should write my performance reviews to my teams?”

Formulating feedback challenges strategic thinking by opening a three-dimensional axis between concrete performance, an estimation of the receiver’s potential, and the appropriate approach to stimulate the behaviour which may deliver the targeted outcome. As coordinates of self-efficacy (Bardura, 1977), personal capabilities and task setups sketch strategic thinking as a matrix between the efforts to be employed and the insight gained from of an overview of a particular project.

Stefania reiterated the importance of empathy when developing a leadership style. When performing a given role, Belbin's theory points out an instinctive adjustment of conduct towards attaining a complementarity with other work group members (Batenburg, Walbeek, & Maur, 2013). However, group co-ordination attributions demand equidistance between predicted outcomes pursuant to one's leadership style and the anticipated response that may be affirmed by each of the personalities within the team.

Stefania mentions empowering others as the most rewarding aspect of her management experience. When such outcome is regarded in anticipation and not in retrospect, strategic thinking highlights a multi-stakeholders' development which accommodates as many variables as the number of parties affected. Risk assessment represents a core component of strategic thinking, regardless of the number of parties which have been taken into account within cognition (Henderson, 1989). However, severity and occurrence as components of risk assessment are estimated with less accuracy following the limited knowledge of every stakeholder considered. Furthermore, such variables may also be affected by the priority order set by the issuer when reflecting on each stakeholder. Employee empowerment is recognised as a dimension of humane entrepreneurship to which strategic thinking is oriented in designing collaborative goals (Debicka et al, 2021). Collaboration and ownership can also lead to an increase in engagement and by promoting participation, leaders get to create ecosystems (Gianos, 2013). Regarding ethics, as a core component, strategic thinking is present in training towards the everyday application of law, but also in exercises such as dilemma games. When it comes to equality, strategic thinking may arise as a response to results highlighted when measuring progress.

Autonomy is set by respondents as the final stage of growth, regardless of the pipelines used for its approach (participation- Francene, empowerment towards critical thinking- Natalia, Katya and Erin, extended liberty in decision making- Jim, task assignment within new territories). By mentioning logic as being employed in facilitating the emergence of better employees, Katya signals that an executive role should not exclude discernment and autonomy. Antony connects the entire purpose of leader-follower communication to growth, which like Natalia, he envisions as the prerogative to draw conclusions and make decisions. Francine also stands out as an

advocate of self-expression and participation, regardless of a lower hierarchical position (Pasamar, 2019). However, neither self-expression nor participation should be confused with autonomy, as the comfort to articulate a point of view does not imply the liberty to actually apply it. When reminiscing about her experience as an executive, Erin argues that being involved in the process of strategy without enjoying the prerogative of decision elevates one's ambitions towards expressing ideas on the particular challenge.

“I think when you are a follower there may be times that you are limited to the views of your line manager. Especially if you're in a role like strategy, so as much as you have lots of ideas. It very much is up to your manager what gets through, so sometimes you are limited in what you do, what you work on an, what ideas get passed. And what was the second part of the question? And if a situation like that pushed you into a different knock tune different a different way, like looking for freedom and more returnable. Would that be correct? I think its autonomy is very important and that's what makes you feel empowered in any roles that you work in. And... going from a line manager that might be limiting with your idea is makes you really want to pursue a team where you have characters that don't do that, so, so you're almost looking at the role that also the personalities within the team to allow you to express your opinion, challenge the status quo, bringing power to go off and have that autonomy.”

Jim points out that trust and a sense of autonomy are mutually dependent:

“I think it probably is, is kind of trust and building that sense of autonomy, and I think they can be examples where maybe that doesn't always go well, if if... You know someone. I'll have betrays your trust, but actually an you know it takes to make a bit with the work they are doing or doesn't do the work that required or does it work for standard, but from what I've seen so far, I think generally it...it does work well as long as you give... give the people the reassurance that if they do need more support, you are kind of there.”

As the concrete application of empowerment on a leader's part, autonomy involves detaching from one's rigours and accepting individual approaches which can be applied in task execution. To Jim, attention to detail may bring the risk of being perceived as a lack of trust in one's

competence. As can be seen in Melanie's own experience of growth points, being granted autonomy as a team member creates a higher sense of responsibility, to better deliver.

"I think I've seen some. Some leaders were probably very involved in the detail and kinda verging on the micromanagement side to those that are very relaxed. This is all about letting the kind of direct reports and team get on with it. I think for me the best leaders are those two who will kind of put their faith and trust in their team but actually support them. So, they kind of they... they know what they're doing, and they are kind of steering and working in the right direction."

While Melanie ruminates:

"It certainly made me work harder and make sure that everything I was saying and putting in a page was like 1000 times checked that everything was absolutely correct."

Such a leadership style may raise concerns about the premises that allow growth and the proper comprehension of the project. Strategic thinking evaluates efficacy to effectiveness to efficiency in a reverse relationship to the key insights available when performing a task (Drucker, 2006). The wider the guidelines provided, the fewer variables to be taken in account within strategic thinking. The fewer requirements delivered, the wider the terrains reached by strategic thinking, expanding from task executing to problem solving and risk prevention. Jim's argument indicates that strategic thinking can be fostered with autonomy, which always provides the premise for growth. The higher the autonomy, the larger the variables and incertitude for strategic thinking. An executive task within detailed requirements guarantees efficacy. Problem solving as an expression of autonomy challenges effectiveness. Risk mitigation for a reduced use of resources introduces an additional variable to problem solving within the definition of efficiency (Antoniou & Ansoff, 2004). Growth is ensured when crossing over from an executive role to initiative within problem solving and advances with any additional variable.

Autonomy is achieved by encouraging innovation amongst team members, educating them towards taking ownership for all implications drawn by their decisions, reducing the prescriptive

element within task assignment, promoting participation, and supporting directives through an eventual rationale (Vaitheeswaran, 2018). Competence can be upgraded by facilitating learning and development, as well as by providing mentorship opportunities in which every member's own pace is respected (Pasamar, 2019). Constructive feedback and a communicative approach designed for support and raising self-esteem are also essential. Relatedness is based on a more substantial acquaintance with one's team members, by getting familiar with both their background and life outside of the office context; but also becoming familiar with their skills and interests. Team building is achieved through designed activities, but also through new member induction. Building trust with one's team is expressed by increasing the autonomy granted to a work group by its leader, according to Jim. Autonomy is not only an acknowledgment of the team members' competencies (Bonn, 2001), but also their personality traits such as time management (Drucker, 1968).

“Giving putting their faith in their ability in their faith to kind of do the work that's required to kind of the suitable time frame, meeting deadlines, et cetera. And then I think kind of giving that sense of autonomy as well so. Rather than always.”

4.3.2.3.6 Toxic leaders that create obstacles to successful leader

As in the case of role models, attributes of toxic leadership converge towards two main areas of manifestation: approach in guidance and moral standards. Ineffective or detrimental leadership is correlated by respondents with lack of clarity, coherence, and constancy, as tasks are assigned by commanding, rather than guiding (Gibbins-Klein, 2017). Duties are apportioned with incomplete requirements, while exigencies change unexpectedly. Moral standards are connected also to difficult or unpleasant personality traits and the unwillingness to conceal them. When reminiscing about leadership styles that had a negative impact on her, Stefania recollects the challenge of facing bullying and the mix between tunnel vision and manipulative tactics. Transformational leadership is defined by the flair to get followers outside their area of expertise and expand their skill set by adapting to unknown territory, thus the direct opposite of having tunnel vision (Becherer, et al., 2008). Natalia mentions having come across terrible bosses, approaching the experience of their collaboration as a lesson to detach from the question while

broadening her perspective on the entire context. An exhaustive view on a given situation brings a critical perspective of the context in relation to both the person's ethics, as well as to their leaders' credibility or legitimacy.

"I've had some absolutely terrible bosses in the past, but not necessarily because they were terrible, but just because their style wasn't right for me, yeah..."

4.3.3 CONTEXT AREA

4.3.3.1 THEME – COVID-19

The leaders' attitude towards the pandemic interests the researcher from the perspective of their capacity to formulate a coherent revision of goals which by promptitude and interrelationships succeeded in mitigating risks driven by an extreme context. Interviewees' personal views on the organisation's resilience reflects their capacity to audit the available resources, capabilities, and vulnerable points which, as a subordinate structure will inevitably affect their teams' input. As group co-ordinators, the leaders carry the responsibility of reviewing and adjusting their teams' competencies within the context of pressure from both external threats as well as from internal vulnerabilities threatening the organisation's resilience. Team cohesion as a fundamental requirement for group performance is further conditioned by individual resilience which can be investigated both in the leaders' observations regarding their own teams as well as in their perception of themselves.

4.3.3.1.1 Pandemic

Secondary data shows the FMCG sector to be the least affected by the COVID-19 pandemic, compared to other industries. However, its stability has been challenged by delays created within the supply chain by unpredictable market responses. The manifestation of an accelerated demand imposes the need of a survey regarding whether the crisis has been perceived as an opportunity or high risk. Strategic thinking adapts an organisation's internal resources, competencies, and capabilities in whatever configurations are demanded by a given context, whereas physical boundaries hinder the accurate awareness of these three key coordinates. The absence of physical

immediacy is mentioned by Russ when arguing the term ‘disaster’ used to describe a mutation in a given framework within the organisation’s structure.

“Where is it you know, if your category manager, you’ll incentivised to really focus on maximising the space you’re given and so one of the difficulties that was really true in life pre Covid, with mostly general Merchandise and Clothing team were based up in Coventry or Milton Keynes and the Food team were based in Holborn.”

Preventing fractures within the supply chain necessitated reinforcing synergies connecting the organisation’s divisions and branches. Studies conducted on the supply chain management of other organisations in FMCG retail signal decision making as being re-centralised and reconfigured according to time pressure and the limitations challenging other stakeholders involved on sourcing and distribution (Schleper et al 2021). The pandemic represented a context which raised the issue of informal decision making under the pressure of crisis management. As transpiring from the participants’ answers, the organisation re-centralised decision making only after an overview of challenges faced on a store level (Schleper et al, 2021). Re-centralised decision making was not, however, imposed on all departments. To Rocky, effective decision making is weakened by the complexity of the command chain, whereas the autonomy he enjoyed allows an enhanced focus on tasks.

“I think I was quite lucky because ...because I wasn’t looking after supermarkets, I got left alone. I can totally imagine it was similar in the wholesale world again where a lot of the command and control, treacle and governance and things that slowed you down disappeared. It was because I’ve almost focused over here. And I felt really empowered to do what I want and...”

4.3.3.1.2 Organisational resilience built by the strategic thinking leaders

An organisation’s capacity to evaluate the extent to which a context could be capitalised derives from the comprehension of its macro factor as both an opportunity as well as a treat. Political and

legal factors pose the limitations of the area of operating within a re-evaluation of the business model, while providing new guidelines which could have been regarded as additional premises for the organisation's stability. Though the FMCG is privileged by utility, even an industry which has been promoted as essential remains vulnerable to economic factors which determine that its end consumers readjust their spending. Social factors such as panic buying are observed both from within as well as from outside the industry as circumstances which have indicated the sector's vulnerability. Though technology could have functioned as a pathway for regaining equilibrium, it had further highlighted the supply chain's weakness. Nevertheless, the key status earned by the industry obliged an extension of its ethical commitment which had been further translated in readjustments of the business model, such as the case of special opening hours for key workers and vulnerable groups.

The pandemic tested organisational resilience through limitations on the configuration which accommodates the company's operations, as well as through suspension of all key growth activities, such as product launches.

Melanie regards COVID as the momentum which postponed anchor projects that functioned as incentives for her new role towards a revision of priorities given by a shortage in basic commodities such as toilet paper.

“And that was interesting time because our first hypothesis was that, like all of our Future Brands and kind of our work is going to get deeper organised by the whole business. Because these were older, like fun, interesting challenging brands and who the hell cares about fun and interesting when they can't get toilet paper?”

Accounts (Melanie, Cedric) highlight how in a regular context, the organisation targeted growth through projects that could have accurately exemplified Ansoff's market development or diversification strategies. Redirecting investment efforts towards consolidating the organisation's presence in the market signals the threat-rigidity effect (Staw, et al., 1981). Reflections also centred on the possibilities the organisation relied on to draw from the new context, as well as the exact scale of the resources needed and the threat. The unprecedented context of COVID required entering new territory. However, a stand-by mode imposed by the pandemic challenged

strategic thinking to identify pathways to recapitalise time as a re-emergent resource which might ensure a smooth reclaim of the same rhythm in planning and delivering the pre-COVID objectives.

Nevertheless, as both Cedric and Terri warn, a particular concerning threat arises from the impact of remote working on communication, trust, and the overall organisational climate. Nick points out how the COVID-19 crisis could be understood by changing the outlook from the threat towards the impact and what was learnt from previous crises (Trijp, et al., 2018).

“This is not the first-time business has been impacted in various shapes or forms. So, what have we learned from the past? Um, how do we understand how competition is responding? Gathering information, understanding the data points, and just making a decision at some point, right? Because you can't just stop doing what you're doing just because something is happening. And just get rating through time.”

When analysing the shortage experimented during the First National Lockdown Cedric affirms having reiterated the modus operandi adopted for maximising the effectiveness of space as a resource in retail.

“...my... my primary function was tools and system. The secondary function was making sure that these guys were not mentally incapacitated, and they were able to thrive and that was my key thing. Once we went into lockdown then it was about setting up regular one to ones just on a chat level; personal one to ones, regular information once, once about systems and what we were doing; regular team meetings online etcetera to make sure that things were happening and that they understood what my priorities were.”

An unforeseen context, the COVID-19 pandemic, required a readjusted practical wisdom in all fundamental practices detected by Jakubik (2020), notably envisioning the likeliness, scale of impact and potential solutions as key coordinates within risk assessment, enabling all synergies so that sourcing fulfils the same rhythm as the emerged buying behaviour, energising teams in order to avoid having them fall to pressure within crisis circumstances while engaging new

configurations within human capital of complementary expertise, and executing emergency decisions in an immediate time span.

Even though both the international and the domestic political context, as highlighted in how both the WHO, as well as the UK Government monitored and responded to the COVID-19 pandemic, could have prepared the organisation for an eventual supply chain management emergency, the interviewees' accounts of the stockpiling crisis indicated that the company neglected an incubation period for its supply shortage (Turner & Rindova, 2012).

For Cedric, the stand-by mode represented the appropriate context for a diagnosis of weaknesses, which can highlight a prompter response in the scenario of a wider deployment of unforeseen threats. Beyond a capacity reevaluation, an internal audit may also reconnect members to their purpose and thus elevate organisational resilience.

4.4 Chapter Summary

Findings confirm or invalidate the themes arising from the coding strategy. Background and lifestyle are not envisioned when contemplating the formation of personal goals. Neither are hobbies and passions, while the general attraction for a field might be present in one's career choices without necessarily highlight the intensity connected to an affinity. Personal development is grounded in the purpose of securing one's competence either through transferable skills or the acquisition of knowledge. Personal values resurface as a catalyst for self-reflection and converge within a purpose and set the ground for loyalty towards the organisation and eventual career transitions. Personality is associated with communication skills rather than strategy or risk management. Communication is cited as the core of coaching and mentoring, further echoing individual resilience. Soft skills provide the rationale for adaptive leadership which mutates according to followership. Hard skills represent both the ultimate goal, as well as the tools and pathway for personal development which can sustain career turning points. Within an organisational context, hard skills set the demarcation between generalists and specialists and regulate individual resilience. Loyalty to the organisation is based on relatedness both as a catalyst, as well as the goal approached when communicating the organisation's culture to one's followership. Not mentioning networking reiterates the fact that leaders extract

configurations for strategic thinking from their team rather than external influences. The career path represents a sequence of turning points. Management consulting and a military career come as alternative educational or professional backgrounds to an experience in retail. Management consulting highlights the importance of flexibility, a catalyst for intrinsic motivation, which is transformed into a key criterium for assessing organisational and industry culture. A military career trains a strategic mind set through extreme challenges which have both stakes and boundaries as rigid variables. The retail industry and its opportunity to advance beyond a disruptive context is dependent on customer behaviour which is itself an unpredictable factor that demands a culture of flexibility.

CHAPTER 5. CONCLUSIONS, CONTRIBUTIONS AND RECOMMENDATIONS

5.1 Conclusions

As anticipated in the most optimistic scenario, the participants offered exhaustive insights which could have allowed separating their cognition and modus operandi in a default setting from those exhibited during the pandemic. Such a comparative overview provided the prerequisite to identify the areas and processes through which they readjusted their patterns of strategic thinking in times of crisis, thus answering the research aim. An insightful aspect that can confirm the formation and evolution of strategic thinking patterns comes from the chronological narration of one's life, as participants tended to analyse and justify without external intervention, because they have made certain decision at the beginning of their professional lives, such as the case of their training or their first jobs. Accounts by participants which granted me access to their hobbies and affinities allowed me to understand variations within strategic thinking in aspects which aren't challenged by pressure factors. Beyond one's own distinctive discernment of values and stakes, decisions related to family life signalled the manifestation of psycho-emotional factors within cognition, while the place of ethics in decision making is particularly visible in how they connect to the concept of purpose.

The majority of respondents, in their default strategic thinking patterns, rely mostly on informal knowledge and self-efficacy (Okoro, 2012). Insights coming from interviewees with a background in consultancy were highly insightful in confirming the human mind's tendency to resolve the challenges raised by every issue's individuality by extracting schemes of knowledge from past decisions and reflecting upon the new problem's peculiarities before engaging in decision making (Calabrese and Costa, 2015). Self-knowledge and one's analytical skills are prioritised to knowledge when passing from one consultancy commission to another (Gibbins-Klein, 2017). The supporting knowledge required by each consultancy project is mentioned in the research background which is referred to as a default preliminary decision. The person's knowledge of the overall microenvironment is prioritised to that of sector or industry.

Consequently, holistic knowledge is favoured above a focused one.

Procedures and codes of practice diffuse and reduce the connection between strategic thinking and strategic planning. Feasibility tests and any other tools that identify and prevent the manifestation of barriers reduce strategic planning to diligence as set by the organisation and the roles within an institutional dimension. Strategic planning is therefore directed to test how the directions issued by strategic thinking fit within the procedural requirements. Therefore, respondents confirm that leaders rather focus on analysis rather than on intuition (Sloan, 2019). Bonn's (2005) thesis is that, in a default setting, strategic thinking is grounded in intuition, mindset, and previous strategy is partially and rather specifically confirmed. Respondents hardly provided any accounts which may reflect intuition. A knowledge of the macro environment and the capacity to promptly deduct its mutations on a given issue can be considered as a manifestation which is understood or explained as intuition. As a synthesis of data collected from the participants, strategic thinking is rather grounded in knowledge which is prioritised when according to the effectiveness rate for proposals.

The mere prospect of engaging in decision making without a prior evaluation of the available knowledge is accounted as a risk, thus excluding intuition as an eventual basis for reasoning. Even the assessment of unknown territories is resumed to a scrutiny of the available knowledge and to issues one can actually control. Knowledge is regarded as the foundation of feasibility. The focus on concrete knowledge indicates a preference for deduction as a pathway for obtaining insights. However, the imperative of completing areas of which participants cannot claim

complete knowledge calls for induction which shall take the form of formulating possible assumptions over the manifestation of these areas and their possible implications.

Data collected reveal a limitation in fully responding to the research aim. Since their hierarchical position places, them as mediators in the implementation of public health policies on an organisational level, in the COVID-19 crisis, their strategic thinking was rather employed towards maintaining their team's morale and effectiveness amid the challenges characterising their default tasks. The rigidity imposed by the normative dimension of the crisis allowed no manifestation of creative thinking, which in a defaults setting might arise in areas which cannot confirm the precedent's effectiveness.

The interviewee's predilection towards flexibility and adaptability reduced my initial assumptions of a significant fracture between the cognitive patterns exhibited on a default setting and those demonstrated within a crisis context. The awareness of ambiguity is one of the key premises setting up an individual's own management of the normality-crisis transition. Though present in a default setting, Pierces's abduction theory (Calabrese and Costa, 2015) is, however, only partially confirmed in a crisis context. The default setting connects goal formulation to terrains which must be addressed and the instrumentalities to deliver them. Performing in the crisis context emphasises the focus on instrumentalities, since an awareness of the tools one could use in their role becomes the basis for building resilience. In their default setting, leaders exhibit a predilection towards risks that influences them to find cognitive stimulation in exploring the unknown. Their focus on tools and resources places factual knowledge on an adjacent level. Consequently, their cognitive patterns are not influenced by whatever external information they might be exposed to in a crisis context but anchored in the certitude that whatever instrumentalities they can rely on a default setting is still available for navigating the particular momentum. Those instrumentalities include norms, infrastructure, and most importantly, people.

Their own team's psychological state and level of resilience become the only instrumentalities that leaders consider might influence the outcome. In re-establishing the same configuration, leaders focus on maintaining their team's morale and the effectiveness of intra-group communication. Consequently, the challenge of performing in a crisis context changes the leaders 'profile from the Directive Type to the Incubating Type (Olson and Simerson, 2015).

However, though the human capital and group cohesion remains a priority, adapting to a crisis context also demands identifying areas to readjust in one's modus operandi.

Findings signal a challenging contrast between the statements provided by participants and the insights transpiring from their account. The participants' statements appear claims related to the importance of intuition within strategic thinking as less relevant compared to the prioritisation of knowledge. However, accounts of interviewees highlight how both their path, as well as the corporate culture which is frequently mentioned as a core argument for career-related decisions, is detrimental to their strategic thinking. As a conclusion regarding such a contradiction, findings appear to validate the literature on the importance of intuitive familiarity.

As a highly regulated context in which a normative dimension was imposed from outside of the organisation, the COVID-19 pandemic allowed little opportunity to confirm or invalidate literature on diagnosis and simulation within a crisis context.

The accounts of participants highlight group cohesion and maintaining their team's morale as their top priorities as transformational leaders. Other measures such as work paradigms have been implemented not through their own initiative but through an input of mediators across the hierarchical decision chain.

The findings I've accessed through my research can provide both contributions to knowledge, as well as practical applications. The contributions to knowledge converge towards self-efficacy in connection to the context, individual responsiveness, and human capital. However, the three dimensions must be connected in synergy which transitory manifestations which also demand self-efficacy. These intermediary phases include acceptance of loss which unites the awareness of context with personal responsiveness, and delegation, which demands responsiveness to human capital. The return to the default setting imposes estimating the time span upon which decisions taken in a crisis mode can be maintained, the implementation, of change and the loss recovery strategy.

The practical contributions are delivered through a framework allowing leaders to easily access all variables affecting each project in which they've been involved. Though every past project is archived, recording is exclusively limited to written documents which might provide a perspective of its actual deployment exclusively if those sources are dated or preserved in

chronological order. Steps and activities which have not been accompanied by documentation risk being overlooked, thus the need for precision in recollection. The precedent can be counted as relevant and trustful knowledge when not invoked through approximation, as a given by a feeble recollection can increase uncertainty if applied as a potential prediction or guideline for decision making. A tool which provides participants a clear vision of the entire deployment of a project they've contributed to could increase effectiveness for all further challenges to which they consider applying learnings from that particular work.

5.3 Contributions

Strategic thinking has been studied for years, but there is always something new and fascinating about this topic. Starting with the people that want to develop strategic thinking for their own development to those who want to contribute to the researcher's community and ultimately help organisations and individuals improve and apply strategic thinking in their daily activities. The main aim of my research was to combine the two goals. The present research has been committed to the clear objective of helping both leaders and organisations to apply strategic thinking at every level. However, findings resulting from the interviewee's participants indicate a juxtaposition between the two terrains as the organisation provides the factual setting in which an individual can direct their cognition, while providing the exact arena to be impacted by the decision-making being articulated through such an intimate process. Consequently, individuals and organisations are inseparable, as leaders are both the product as well as the creators of their own environment. Reasserted by the intervention of each participant, such interdependency demands that strategic thinking be trained within the strict matrix of institutional coordinates. Strategic thinking skills articulate strategic decisions in response to strategic questions such as those raised within opportunities and risks. The latter question has pertinent significance at this point in time as business is in the throes of a global pandemic, which has had enormous repercussions for the way business is run and will be run in the future. There are many variables and unknowns. The need for strategic thinkers has never been higher. Strategic thinking leaders and particularly those with proven success in adapting to crises or disruptive events and ensuring

that the businesses under their leadership survive and indeed thrive, are providing value for all stakeholders and will be greatly sought after. Drucker (2006) discusses the merit of being active and flexible in the strategic thinking sphere in business and of using information in conjunction with ideas. The unexpected should always be anticipated according to Drucker and initiative is important to create one's own destiny (as well as that of the business). Through his namesake matrix, Igor Ansoff (1957) highlighted environmental volatility as a threat and opportunity to business and the tool formulated strategies for future growth. Both opportunities and risks derive from the way internal resources counteract or capitalise on the environmental volatility.

However, the mere concept of volatility highlights the ephemeral character of a context, which should be recalled as a confluence of long-lasting factors with variables which time proved temporary. Nevertheless, such realisation, which inevitably comes in retrospectively, demands that circumstances raising a context be documented timeously.

As core elements of originality, the snowballing method setting up the epistemological deployment of the data collection, as well as the freestyle Narrative Inquiry, ensured that its execution signalled the applicability of the extracted findings in the following areas within organisational functions: leadership, talent management, Learning & Development, quality control, and risk assessment. However, compiling findings in a coherent sequence raised reflection on whether it is feasible and effective to scrutinise a common architecture of decision making which allows application beyond purpose.

As reflected in the conclusions, the only issue that had attracted unanimity beyond circumstances and areas of applicability is the pivotal influence of the precedent as a preliminary framework for decision making, either through replication or through adjustments. When faced with new challenges, risk prevention and the timely detection of possible threats, individuals engage in mental surveys of familiar experiences. As reasserted throughout the data analysis, strategic thinking addresses decision making through management of different levels of incertitude, stressing particular variables which compose a circumstance. However, certitude is approximated through a juxtaposition between the previewed factors and their occurrence and impact within other circumstances. As a common denominator transcending accounts which signal both habitual, as well as isolated events, the awareness of a possible precedent demands an exhaustive recollection of all possible variables which intervened in order to create the initial and ongoing

circumstances, whether stable and predictable or not. Findings in the present research can be applied with the elaboration of a recording tool which documents and assesses all factors which have influenced the decision-making process along a given task with the purpose of validating the respective project as an effective precedent. The purpose that the project has served, as well as the expertise employed, allow a prior classification in accordance with areas of applicability such as product launch, rebranding, and crisis management.

Recreating milestones within the deployment of a project represents a fundamental process to detect one vital issue evoked by every participant in their description of the mere concept of the precedent: boundaries to which they had to adapt (Goldman, 2015). Such constraints can be legal, physical, financial, institutional, as well as strategic or inter correlated. The prerogative of autonomy in decision making is limited by normative boundaries, whether emanating from a statutory background, industry standards, interior regulations, one's own attributions, or the various imperatives such as those transpiring from tenders. Understanding the influence of constraints on decision making leads to the realisation of different circumstances which accurately highlight the applicability of a cognitive pattern on another situation (Thaler, 2015). If some constraints which are related to the company's ethos may remain static, a different purpose may enter a distinctive terrain of standards whereas regulatory regulations may not maintain their relevance following eventual changes of legislation, especially in terrains challenged by a statutory void, like the current case of AI (Caniëls & Gelderman, 2005). One's own attributions may differ beyond the general responsibilities composing the job description.

Responsibilities within a project are evaluated in connection to all participants in its implementation yet work groups can pass departmental limits and incorporate external collaborators (Drucker, 1968). The contribution of those outside one's habitual work group may be overlooked. Furthermore, clients may impose their own standards which highlight their own ethos. Strategic boundaries derive from the sequence of activity and how a direction highlighted by a task which has been executed before in the same project imposes decision making for the others. When invoking the precedent, individuals may remember the impact of decisions in one area while neglecting the place that particular action had within the entire project and the context

which forced it (Avolio, et al., 1991). Consequently, under the pressure driven by a crisis context, the findings may provide the guidelines in the following areas:

5.2.1 AWARENESS OF CONTEXT

The findings converge towards two key directions: reflection upon the parameters which become the lens for the subjective estimation of data (1) and the approach of internal systems present within the organisation in order to extract relevant information within macro factors (2). Each parameter expands or concentrates the perspective on the macro-environment allowing a clear focus on the interests of each group of stakeholders. Filtering information in accordance with the company's internal diagnosis allows a higher precision of factors that indeed must be prioritised in the strategy, signalling points of threats and areas which can open terrains for efficiency.

Leaders are recommended to explore a realistic discernment of the macro contexts they are about to enter. Such evaluation implies verifying whether the manifestations of the context are direct or tangential to the industry and sector they operate in (Goldman, 2015). Neutralising the impact of disruptions implies a scrutiny of additional responsibilities raised by the apparent absence of threats, as operation chains are likely to signal the organisation's interdependency of stakeholders more profoundly impacted by the context (Avolio, et al., 1991), such as reflected in the fractures experienced by the retail sector's logistic flow (Schelepet et al, 2021).

5.2.2 ACCEPTANCE OF LOSS

Regardless of the experiences they refer to, participants signal an approach of negative outcomes not as losses but as opportunities to learn which could either highlight an immediate solution or prepare one for similar deployments in their future challenges.

Crisis contexts are not organically absorbed as opportunities. Capitalising circumstances as opportunities implies identifying the needs created by such contexts after a stage of observation which, in its passivity, cannot be protected from losses. Before such certitude, strategic thinking implies an estimation of the loss an organisation can sustain in the short term (Whipps, 2014).

The short- and long-term demarcation is vital to detect the extent to which the organisation's resources can buffer the impact of a crisis (Antoniou & Ansoff, 2004). Furthermore, the longer

the time span considered in projections, the higher the uncertainty of impact, as circumstances are likely to change, and losses may be reduced than estimated.

5.2.3 SELF-AWARENESS AND REACTIVITY

Participants highlight self-reflection as based on a continuous reassertion of their sense of purpose which becomes the foundation for their own relatedness to their role, with great implication for accountability. Conducted in retrospective, self-reflection highlights issues and contexts in which one's resilience may become vulnerable. Such focus can facilitate the timely development of coping mechanisms which will inevitably prevent reactivity.

Crisis contexts are characterised by elevating ongoing threats to new levels of uncertainty before which leaders must preserve their focus. Such requirement implies identifying one's own pressure points, the variables escalating them, such as unpredictability in emergence or impact severity that goes beyond predictions (Gibbins-Klein, 2017) and recalling self-management regulation strategies (Bandura, 1977) which have proved effective within precedents.

5.2.4 GROUP RETENTION AND COHESION

Participants highlight their team's morale as the foremost issue to address before formulating any strategy. The team's morale is further deconstructed to each individual's values and sense of purpose which establish the approach under which tasks are presented and assigned. Such consideration is fundamental for safeguarding relatedness- which becomes the basis for retention.

Driving survival mode, a crisis may determine that individuals evaluate their opportunities which triggers either benchmarking the industry they perform in or reassessing their transferable skills for an eventual career reconversion. Employee retention represents a permanent objective which remains valid beyond macro contexts, an active indicator for human capital as a core component of an organisation's capabilities (Pasamar, 2019). A low employee retention rate burdens organisations with additional costs of talent management (Drucker, 2006). Crises push leaders towards the challenge of not only safeguarding a stable employee retention rate, but also to prioritise group cohesion (Krishnan, 2004). Consequently, leaders must survey professional,

organisational and role identities, and detect the pillar they should approach for each individual. For a timely response, leaders are recommended to elaborate records of each team member (Fors Brandebo, 2020) with a psychological profile (introvert/extrovert), anchors for identity, and a personal vision of their purpose.

5.2.5 LEADERSHIP DELEGATION

Participants indicate how strategic thinking is manifested regardless of the prerogative to decision making, as the implementation of a task attains a higher effectiveness when communicated in a manner which resonates to those directly involved in delivering it. Such dynamic can only be capitalised through the direct input of group leaders who are inevitably accustomed to their own subordinates' values and mindset. Delegating allows the consolidation of cohesion in any work group, regardless of size. Furthermore, delegating is mentioned as a pathway for indicting one's consideration towards various team members. Nevertheless, the increased autonomy attained by a person in the execution of their own attributions once delegated to higher responsibilities allows a more effective use of complementary skill sets.

The high level of incertitude ignited by crisis moments may generate the additional risk produced by the emergence of a parallel, informal leadership. Such challenge may arise from inside the team, conventionally bodied by members who articulate concerns resented by their peers whose confidence they are likely to gain through such ad hoc representation (Benedetti, 2019). Leaders are recommended to call for such concerns to be expressed, which would transmit transparency and would engage members in conversation, also assuring their participation (Haddon et al, 2015). Furthermore, if the group exhibits such interventions, leaders can invite the respective team members to assist them and delegate co-ordination.

5.2.6 ASSESSMENT OF TEMPORARINESS

Ongoing projects that require suspension represent the first markers for the necessity to view any actions in a revised time orientation between immediate, short term, and indefinite. The assessment of temporariness has also been approached in connection to the inevitable time span

in which the implementation of change will produce outcomes which arise as additional points of vulnerability, alike the case of the effect of remote working on the team's morale.

Evaluating the impact of the crisis both in its concrete manifestation, as well as according to the risk mitigation strategy accommodated occurs within the transition stage. Adopting prevention and control strategies demands not only an estimation of a threat's impact, but also that of the time span in which the risk of a relapse needs to be considered or that in which the organisation succeeds in adjusting its internal synergies to safely function within a crisis (Schoemaker, 1995). Furthermore, one temporary measure may be introduced to be replaced with other such limited span strategies. Leaders should therefore employ appropriate strategic thinking in order to understand the deployment of threats in their various stages of severity and formulate strategies which frame not only these phases but also a large enough interval which allows neutralising any eventual redevelopment.

5.2.7 THE PERMANENCE - POTENTIAL OF TEMPORARY MEASURES

Studies on the end consumers' feedback in connection to measures introduced as an imperative derived from public health policies are mentioned as a starting point to assess the viability and success rate for their eventual implementation as a permanent measure.

Previous surveys which indicated mutations in the consumers' behaviour which could facilitate or prevent such change have been revisited to confirm or invalidate such a prospect.

The precedent highlights methodology and objectives in the assessment of pilot strategies which confirm not only their effectiveness, but also the time span in which they could produce the expected results, whether through their relevance to a given context or through the lifecycle predicted by the consumers' receptivity (Kovoor-Misra, 2020). Therefore, leaders are recommended to monitor not only how strategies deliver their purpose, thus neutralise risks, but also to monitor the consumers' response, which may highlight the potential of implementing on a permanent basis the measures initially adopted for a given time span (Ansoff et al, 2019).

5.2.8 RESPONSIVENESS TO EMERGING VARIABLES

Though unforeseen circumstances could have objectively emerged from outside the organisation, either from public health policies or the supply chain and other external stakeholders, the respondents continuously asserted a particular concern about how the new paradigms for work would generate such a powerful impact on employee morale and team cohesion that it would affect the delivery of individual or group tasks.

Contingency characterising crisis events implies the continuous emergence of events of various manifestations which cannot be predicted in duration, leading towards confusion in regard to their relevance for strategy (Anderson and Anderson, 2002). Leaders are therefore challenged with identifying which of these events should be included as variables and which should be overlooked (Ansoff et al, 2019). In order to facilitate a prompt response, leaders should priorly develop a methodology which allows the timely adjustment of strategic planning to emerging variables, whereas reaching such a degree of versatility implies the ability to recognise isolated episodes (Avery, 2004).

5.2.9 IMPLEMENTATION OF CHANGE

Participants highlight change as a matter for which leaders should assume accountability, neutralising any additional pressure which can be perceived by their teams when faced with the challenge of integrating new systems to their daily attributions.

As organisations function as networks which are further placed in synergies with external stakeholders, change does not affect the structural component in which it is being issued, but echoes along all chains and parties connecting them (Tanveer, 2018). Leaders are therefore recommended towards the effective implementation of changes in order to minimise eventual discontinuities or even disruptions within the interdepartmental cooperation or in the external liaisons (Vaitheeswaran, 2018). Nevertheless, leaders should also consider how to communicate change in order not to affect the brand positioning before consumers (Lee and Chon, 2020).

5.2.10 LOSS RECOVERY STRATEGY

Responses converge towards resource preservation and prevention of a wider magnitude of losses. However, regaining stability is reasserted as a goal without, however, being accompanied by any plans or time orientation for its achievement.

Leaders are challenged with evaluating whether they should accept an organic loss recovery and postpone eventual goals with demand impacting considerable capital inflows or if they should employ resources towards accelerating such process even if it would imply temporarily destabilising the organisation even further (Schoemaker, 1995). The route towards an effective strategy demands anticipating the organisation's capacity of regeneration under various stress factors. Furthermore, leaders should also assess what mid- or long-term goals adopted prior to the crisis context could accelerate recovery and which are recommended to be postponed.

5.3 Contributions to Practice

Various themes provided the basis for data analysis and highlight how strategic thinking prioritises knowledge above intuition. Spontaneity is regarded as contra productive, being assimilated into unfunded decision making. Intuitive familiarity, however, is connected to the knowledge assimilated by each contributor within a project. If inter-peer communication is privileged by clarity, a leader's modus operandi may influence their subordinates' patterns of strategic thinking. Projects are approached through anticipation and retrospection. Anticipation is connected to feasibility studies while retrospection is connected to performance reviews. While anticipation operates on prediction and estimation, retrospection facilitates analysis through concrete results while also integrating self-reflection. Retrospection may become a source of intuitive familiarity depending on how much knowledge is assimilated from a project. The multidisciplinary deployment of an issue deeply influences the acquisition of knowledge and the transformation of strategic thinking towards a holistic approach. Consequently, leaders must prioritise an exhaustive approach to retrospection. The practical contribution of this thesis can be directed towards such a goal by deconstructing each project in order to expand the angles for retrospection. The synthesis of findings mentioned within this paragraph can be regarded as the background for a performance review tool that will be further developed.

5.3.1 PRECEDENT INSIGHT CHART

The chart has been developed based upon the synergies amassed within the conception, development, delivery, and follow-up of a project. A leader's prerogative in terms of decision making is limited under the authority invested by their hierarchical superiors. Projects are brought to fruition through teams coordinated by the leader.

The geometrical representation of projects highlights the boundaries dictating their conception or development. Such boundaries may be normative (both statutory as well as under the influence of industry standards or the organisation's own codes of practice), budgetary, technological, infrastructural, or related to human capital. If projects had not been submitted to any kind of boundaries, they would have been represented as an amorphous shape. The market's volatility demands that I illustrate its impact through dispersed arrows. Since projects may accommodate various sequels such as line extension or improved or upgraded version, I have chosen to integrate such prospects by means of a transversal arrow (from the Hierarchical Superiors to the Sequence).

Figure 7. Precedent insight framework

(Microsoft PowerPoint, 2023)

The initial purpose of this research was that of using the findings to elaborate a guide for developing strategic thinking, a guide which until the data collection phase I had envisioned as a course founded on context-based examples. However, coming across so many inspirational stories made me realise that outstanding leadership transcends theory through diversity of thought, value scale, and character. Leadership should not migrate towards standardisation, but safeguard individuality. Nevertheless, context-based examples could be curated from one's own

experience, an extremely bountiful terrain which continuously teaches us about prediction, anticipation, incertitude, and the infinite variety in which practice can reassemble volatile circumstances. Leader development comes from reflection which is always enhanced by mindfulness and remaining alert when challenged and managing one's way through an experience. Only such duality of presence-retrospection could make us learn about our strategic flair, rationality, and capacity for assessing and reacting to a factor of pressure, issues which remain vital for both self-management as well as leadership. Consequently, reflection remains the best guide and as a researcher, the best contribution I could deliver was to facilitate clarity so that such contemplation would not result in a blurred image.

Leader development through self-reflection is nevertheless imposed under an objective and pragmatic argument: the fact is that time remains the best resource for any individual, regardless of their role in an organisation and better still, instils the moment in which they find themselves on their own path. Bersin (2018) signals the fact that the average employee only has 24 minutes a week in which to learn again. Any practical tool the present research could have produced should have addressed the issue of time efficiency which reaches its maximum manifestation if learning is induced when conducting a necessary activity. As each project is followed by performance assessment, the proposed framework had to be elaborated in a configuration which would have capitalised on this process.

If exercised in retrospect, correlating documents to other lines of communication such as emails, phone-calls, or face to face meetings in order to complete one's perspective on a context is time consuming and ineffective. Even if brainstorming sessions are completed, each organisation has its own guidelines for recording meetings and for the frequency with which such steps might be considered. A methodology which allows a fresh, real-time reflection on factors which have driven a decision, and which can further be revisited post project facilitates an understanding of circumstances both in their apparent importance as assimilated under the pressure of a given moment, as well as in their objective importance as demonstrated post project.

As a tool dedicated to the safeguarding of accuracy, the framework can be applied both along the progress of the project, as well as after its completion. Furthermore, to reassert decision making

from an objective perspective, the framework is formulated in order to be corroborated with all post project assessment methodologies endorsed within an organisation.

This instrument is dedicated to providing an accurate record of a given project in order to be further used as a precedent invoked by strategic thinking. The framework will be applied for each individual project. All components and variables which have affected the project from its conception to its delivery will be analysed in connection to the levels of pressure raised, as well as to the priori and a posteriori satisfaction. Rating the levels of pressure not for the overall work but for each variable affecting its development and delivery will stimulate the person filling the form to reflect on the aspects they considered to be the most demanding, in order to verify, confirm, or invalidate the points of concern they've experienced throughout the entire process. A demarcation between the level of a priori and a posteriori satisfaction can help the person filling in the form to separate the enthusiasm or frustration experienced upon the completion of each task and revisit that experience with the detachment enjoyed post-delivery when they can claim a clear view of the market feedback.

The first issue to consider is the purpose of the project, the departments involved in its conception, development, and delivery, as well as the time duration for which it will be effective. Such data allows the person filling in the form to get a sense of the expertise needed for a project of such magnitude as well as its exact importance to the organisation's business model. Outside data related to the nature of the project is the first thing that validates a previous work as a potential precedent lies in objective parameters amassed under a global concept of resources. This part of the table refers to the instrumentalities leaders relied on for delivering the project, whether human (team), capability-wise (stakeholders), financial (the available budget), infrastructural (facilities), technological (equipment), and normative (intellectual property). Deviations in the resource components in contrast with the resources available for further works that must be strategized and for which leaders are searching for reliable past experiences limit the project's applicability as a precedent.

The limit to which leaders can apply previous works to current projects is highly influenced by the prerogative of decision making they have enjoyed in those particular projects. Their

prerogatives are visible in issues such as deadlines and compliance to various norms which can be imposed upon the overall project or certain areas.

As a fundamental value prioritised in leadership, group cohesion is highlighted in relation to the team participation in decision making. The members' input is however analysed in connection to whether the project demanded a consensus amongst the members of the team. Contested areas and their solutions or the compromises attained are vital to understand the team's ability to timely observe and address variables that may affect the project's effectiveness.

The project's relevance as a precedent is also affected by the level of authority with which its leaders have been endorsed by their hierarchical superiors. Such an issue is approached in the planning approval section which must consider the number of revisions which the project has undergone when submitted to the leader's hierarchical superiors, and the areas addressed in the revision.

Prior to analysing the project's implementation, the person filling in the form is invited to consider eventual deviations from the plan that the team had to integrate. Such deviations are analysed in connection to the degree they could have been anticipated, the factors determining such changes, the decisions influenced by them and the eventual losses they caused. The scale to which the project has been maintained in its original form can be correlated to the areas that required adjustments.

The project's implementation is considered in connection to the deadline and duration. Imposed deadlines indicate a higher level of pressure and may determine a reduced due diligence and creativity compared to projects privileged by the prerogative of an agreed deadline. Deadline extensions may be granted unexpectedly so they should be noted by the person who revisits the project in regard to realistic expectations of delivery. Delays should always be noted so that in further projects teams either adjust the time span or recalculate their work volume.

The immediate feedback represents a revisionary confirmation for the effectiveness of all decisions taken across the conception, development, as well as delivery stages. A higher importance should be given to the criticism received, as arguments raised can highlight variables and risks that have been overlooked across the conception, development, and delivery stages and which should be considered in further projects. The team's reaction to these arguments indicates

their level of focus, observation, market diagnosis, and analytical skills. Accountability reflects an ethical approach.

Nevertheless, building up the precedent should also include eventual sequence work such as line extensions for a new product, which can be analysed in their connection to the original project and the extent to which the exact methodologies delivering the parent project have been reapplied. The connection to the parent project might be an indicator of the latter's success. The reuse of methodologies could confirm an effective *modus operandi*.

Insights provided from each table are concluded by applicability and transferability. Leaders can therefore note whether the insights delivered by the project can exclusively be applied (specific applicability and, consequently, no transferability) in further works with the exact same purpose, as in product launches. In cases of partial applicability, the person filling in the form can record their observations on every component or variable affecting the project. Observations related to transferability can follow the following format: as an, one of the team members contested the initial communication campaign for a product launch, raising the argument of a potential image crisis generated under the cancel culture. Further research within the psychographic profile of the target market segment confirmed this argument. The same threat might arise in similar projects, thus, the same research which confirmed the contestation should be integrated within the initial feasibility studies. The occurrence captured in connection to that particular aspect proved to be transferable.

All elements in the table could be distinguished from one another through an agreed system of coding for record purposes. For example, one-digit codes can exclusively refer to new product launches, two-digit codes to territorial expansions, three digits to shop closures and so on.

Table 2. Precedent insight chart

Label	Description	Level of time pressure	A priori level of satisfaction	A posteriori level of satisfaction	Observations related to transferability	Code (Recording purpose only)
Purpose	I. IMPLICATIONS Rebranding, product launch, etc					
Departments involved Project effectiveness	Permanent/Limited II. RESOURCES					
Human capital Stakeholders	No. permanent members No. collaborators No. external collaborators					
Budget Facilities						
Equipment IP (ex: prototype, untested research, brevet, etc)	III. LEADERS ' PREROGATIVE IN DECISION MAKING					
Deadline for submitting the project plan Decision making prerogative Authority for decision making	X days/weeks Yes/No None (Directives to comply to)/Partial/Full					

Label	Description	Level of time pressure	A priori level of satisfaction	A posteriori level of satisfaction	Observations related to transferability	Code (Recording purpose only)
Areas imposed compliance Areas privileged with the prerogative of decision making Areas privileged with liberty of interpretation for official directives	 IV. TEAM PARTICIPATION IN DECISION MAKING					
Team consensus demanded	Yes/No					
Key areas contested						
Arguments raised within contestations Degree to which the raised arguments were confirmed						
Immediate approval by the superior authority Number of revisions	V. PLANNING APPROVAL Yes/No					

Label	Description	Level of time pressure	A priori level of satisfaction	A posteriori level of satisfaction	Observations related to transferability	Code (Recording purpose only)
Areas addressed in revision	VI PLAN DEVIATIONS					
Deviations from the plan	Yes/No					
Degree of anticipation for the deviations occurred						
Scale to which the plan has been maintained						
Factors responsible for the deviations						
Losses generated by the deviations						
Decisions connected to the deviations						
Areas adjusted (ex: new suppliers, new events venue)	VIII IMPLEMENTATION					
Imposed implementation deadline						

Label	Description	Level of time pressure	A priori level of satisfaction	A posteriori level of satisfaction	Observations related to transferability	Code (Recording purpose only)
Agreed implementation deadline						
Duration of implementation						
Deadline extensions						
Delays						
Positively reviewed areas	IX IMMEDIATE FEEDBACK					
Criticised areas						
Arguments drawn within criticism						
Arguments for defending the issues raised through criticism						
Reception of arguments						
Accountability issues						
	X SEQUENCE PROJECTS					
Sequence projects	Yes/No					
Connection to the previous project	Low/High/Rate					

Label	Description	Level of time pressure	A priori level of satisfaction	A posteriori level of satisfaction	Observations related to transferability	Code (Recording purpose only)
Degree in which the project management methodologies have been applied						
Applicability	Specific/General (indicate in the chosen colour the areas of general applicability)					
Transferability	Partial/Complete (indicate in the chosen colour the areas of transferability)					

Beyond the general applicability of the precedent chart, findings can also be expanded to a crisis context in which strategic thinking is reconfigured in a different matrix of goals, resources, and priorities. The deployment of a crisis highlights 10 distinctive directions that set be considered in leaders' strategic thinking and which can be addressed through the patterns which do not quality as common denominators but exhibited a certain incidence.

5.4 Recommendations

Building a strategy is based on understanding the available data which may provide structure with a direct impact on prediction accuracy or may challenge decision making with ambiguity and thus force speculation. Decision making comes after evaluating the effects of the goals-resources-risks configurations that elevate strategic thinking characteristics. Whether positive or negative, experiences and interactions are valued in accordance with the extent to which they allow extracting of insights, which can add to structure for new challenges that require strategic thinking. Inspirational leadership converges towards the same purpose, either facilitating a more exhaustive comprehension of the rationale and applicability of executed tasks or extending the perspective over unconventional pathways to develop cognition. While for an organisation, resilience demands subjecting risk assessment to an audit of resources, for individuals it is grounded on self-efficacy and requires adaptive leadership. Findings can highlight applicability in the following areas within organisational functions:

5.4.1 TALENT MANAGEMENT

As a beacon for incentive motivation, the company culture should be found at the core of new recruits' insertion, task assignment, L&D, and any other areas in which the organisation can control the employees' exposure to values they can anchor their sense of purpose on (Cutolo et al, 2021) (Gianos, 2013) (Kazmi & Naaranoja, 2015).

Since personal circumstances such as parenthood are mentioned as secondary argument to unstimulating work environments when it comes to career turning points, HRM and line managers should consider increasing employees' control over work conditions and content in order to maintain their retention under optimal values (Drucker, 2006).

When conducted by direct superiors, performance assessments which follow every project can be focused towards extracting the configuration of instrumentalities, limitations, and route revisions to reiterate or invalidate deductions confirmed for previous works (Thaler, 2015).

5.4.2 LEADERSHIP

Leadership should target both deliverables as well as an organisational and a corporate identity. As line managers, leaders have a direct influence on the formation of organisational identity which descends from group cohesion as a reflection of one's individual input through roles (Gu, 2015) (Pasamar, 2019). However, as representatives of the organisation, their communicational skills are fundamental to the creation of corporate identity if task assignment is formulated to reach every individual's sense of purpose (Avolio, et al., 1991).

It is more common for an individual to enter a field without a particular vocation or even interest, thus creating a purpose in accordance with their personal values should be prioritised by a leader. The sense of purpose could be anchored both in the actual outcomes of their work, such as sustainability; as well as in projections of personal growth. Levels of career advancement and the creative dimension of tasks should be synchronised so that an individual's personal goal should be formulated within an organisational background in order to ensure employee retention and investment (Pasamar, 2019). A continuous reminder of the implications of their work reconnects individuals to a sense of purpose while reinforcing their accountability, which is vital for both work effectiveness as well as risk prevention (Bonn, 2001).

To set the terrain towards the acquisition of complementary skills, leaders could familiarise their team with the responsibilities of intersecting organisational divisions or functions, such as the case of sequences within the supply chain or the overview of strategy as a process that highlights its own sequences and instrumentalities (Pasamar, 2019). Such an approach might maintain the perception of a stimulating work environment, while also providing a concrete imagery of their own input, thus raising accountability.

Creating a stimulating work environment can also be attainable through task assignment and delegation which can integrate three successive stages that highlight the complexity of the creative potential within each person's attribution. As goals are exposed, leaders can start by brainstorming to compile various proposals for their attainment to further reveal the incentive of countless pathways by evaluating such suggestions in contrast to strategies which the same team has tested and validated throughout their experience. After assessing risks and scaling effectiveness for both new proposals as well as the application of tested approaches, members are granted autonomy as both a recognition of their vision and as a strategy for accountability (Lyubykh, 2007, Muchiri, 2019).

As a fundamental consequence of transformational leadership, employee autonomy can be ensured in upgraded levels of confidence both for the individuals as well as for their teams thanks to findings highlighting stages of empowerment. A core aspect of such goal, the research has also responded to the recommended strategies and avoidable approaches within feedback formulation.

5.4.3 LEARNING & DEVELOPMENT

Knowledge capital should be accommodated at the core of any organisation, whereas learning and development schemes should be elaborated to ensure employees upskill in a similar rhythm to identified threats to their relevance (such as technological advancements). Line managers could have their input in L&D extended, while knowledge acquisition could be delivered through other pathways rather than the traditional course format (Pasamar, 2019). Beyond reiterating the general modus operandi which descends from the company ethos, in order to consolidate, the instrumentalities must be identified and validated throughout a project. As an employee might become accustomed to on-the-job training and might not perceive the strategy as a development-oriented variable, line managers as leaders can complement brainstorming meetings to speed knowledge sessions in which they verbally remind their team how their own competencies (as associated to comprehended insights and validated routes for task executions) are updated in order to be adapted to new challenges (Simon, 1997).

When applied towards creating leaders, L&D schemes should prioritise team formation and task delegation. Team formation should integrate the appropriate knowledge (for example, deriving from psychology) that allows for previewing the limits, challenges and duration of group cohesion when amassing various personality types, as well as adaptive leadership strategies that can accelerate and strengthen peer cooperation while avoiding the perception of bias. Task delegation should be grounded on strategies to accurately fathom an overview of a particular context both in its present composition, as well as in its possible deployment as envisioned in various degrees of likeliness. When it comes to the concrete content of tasks, L&D schemes for leaders should target identifying activities to delegate, as well as attaining the specialised knowledge as a generalist to approve their delivery (Drucker, 2006).

Findings can be adapted within a scenario-based L&D program for developing one's intuition by exercising insights to extract and superfluous details to filter out when analysing the precedent.

5.4.4 RISK ASSESSMENT

L&D programs could include intuition training for handling the unknown through projections over its exact content and management of available knowledge in order to neutralise risks connected to unfathomed territories (Bonn, 2005). Leaders should not neglect the resonance external factors might have on stakeholders of high influence, since the latter's response can have an increased impact on the former (as highlighted how the Government announcements of lockdown triggered stockpiling) (Drucker, 2006) (Ansoff, 2019). Nevertheless, findings also reveal the momentum and implementation for the suspension of goals and how to communicate or make visible postponed development strategies in order to avoid threats to the organisation's stability and market positioning (Ansoff, 2019).

Though directed towards the exercise of leadership, the precedent insight chart can be applied as a self-assessment matrix in talent management, a diagnosis instrument in L&D schemes, as a performance evaluation tool in quality control, and as a feasibility framework in risk assessment. The research aim demanded that I identify the variations in a leaders' cognitive patterns from defaults settings to a crisis. The precedent insights chart aims to highlight peculiarities from one project to another, indicating both the value as well as the factual knowledge (Simon, 1997) to be considered in the reasoning with which leaders would address every challenge they come across in their work.

5.5 Discussion

5.5.1 THE NORMATIVE BACKGROUND: THE ORGANISATION'S CORE STRATEGIC RESPONSE TO THE CRISIS

Crisis management had to be addressed within the framework of new regulatory guidance. Anthony describes performing within the COVID-19 context as a mixture of leading and following. However, the exact same dynamics characterise a regular leadership context (Kipley, et al., 2012). Exercised within an organisational setting, leadership becomes a matter of agency. The role of leadership is to safeguard the organisation's ethos, which encompasses a set of rules itself. As mediators within the decision chain, the leaders must translate the ethos within each set of temporary rules approved for a project. They are accountable for clarity and accuracy regardless of a project's specifications. The individual contribution falls within the limits of their invested authority. Initiative can be expressed in pathways of attaining efficiency in the limits of given standards (Drucker, 1968). Overlooking such boundaries highlights how norms and methodologies become assimilated when performing in a formalised environment. The leader encounters the exact same mutations amongst their following, thus the challenge within a context of disruption is to extract previous work patterns and overview the absorption of new ones (Goldman, 2015).

Implementing Government guidelines differs from entering a regulated terrain with which the company is unfamiliar. Regulations represent the foremost framework according to which the feasibility of project proposals is verified. Entire components and synergies of new strategic units are created and arranged according to legal limitations. Furthermore, strategic thinking within an organisational setting is trained towards considering the statutory framework as background in decision making. However, complying with an emergency regulation which re-draws, though temporarily, the entire statutory framework on which either a strategic unit or the company's business model is built, redefines priorities.

The regulatory feasibility surveyed within the project proposal phase is replaced with a reassurance that every member's contribution is delivered not through the usual statutory background to which they have formed their due diligence, but to the new legal limitations, as a measure of preventive control (Denyer, 2020). Anthony's outlook on the context mentions prioritising clarity of guidelines and safety. Risk management as the core direction within strategic thinking is therefore oriented towards verifying both comprehensions, as well as compliance with the new guidelines.

5.5.2 CHANGES IN RELATEDNESS AND ORGANISATIONAL IDENTITIES

On an individual level, the extreme changes brought by disruption disconnects one with core components of their identity such as their skillset, their sense of belonging, and their goals- which are questioned in terms of feasibility, rationale, and actual outcome as understood in the degree of satisfaction brought by their achievement (Antoniou & Ansoff, 2004). The COVID-19 pandemic appeared in a transitory context, notably the shift of paradigm driven by sustainability which calls for considering all stakeholders involved. The focus on organisational culture and the growing spread of transformational leadership elevated intrinsic motivation to a similar or even a higher level of consideration from that given to extrinsic incentives (Avolio, et al., 1991). Individuals whose training and career start fall within the transitory period generated by the growing awareness of sustainability may even advance a distinctive approach on incentive motivation in which one's input before other stakeholders is prioritised in the sense of belonging and appreciation. The sense of purpose ended up advocated under the question of giving, rather than receiving. The importance attributed to a sense of purpose is increasing from one generation to another, the millennials and gen Z would even prioritise it above their salary when opting for a new job (Gallup, 2017). Adapting transformational leadership to the transitory stage and the lessons taught by the COVID-19 pandemic imposes awareness of such a shift's values. However, in addition to such responsiveness to macro-changes, a giving-oriented mindset within transformational leadership can also be the product of one's formation as a professional.

Josee's focus on the institution's motto (Serve to Lead) in his statement on how it was the leadership course which he attended for one year at the Royal Military Academy Sandhurst that he can consider as having shaped his strategic thinking can be understood that it is the organisational culture which inspires a following. An overview of the logo in conjunction with his statement can further highlight that in order to create an impact, the organisational culture must articulate a sense of purpose which can be perceived as sufficiently applicable to be approached as guideline for formulating one's own individual ethos (Bonn, 2005). When it comes to adapting

such a pattern in leadership, strategic thinking amasses both the outcome produced, as well as the impact brought by task assignment to every individual under a coordinator's responsibility.

Testing transferable skills outside of one's area of expertise opens a perspective over one's concrete competencies within the growing demand of self-adjustment. Disruption is characterised by extreme change which forces a revision of one's own position within their environment whether anchored in conjunction to their industry, organisation, or profession (Antoniou & Ansoff, 2004). Irrelevance represents the isolated, yet highly plausible scenario within which the effects of disruption can be experienced on an individual level. Prior to the COVID-19 pandemic, one of the most impactful consequences of the dynamic technological advancements and the social and economic mutations they produced on the labour market is reflected in the prospect of going through on average five career changes throughout one's professional life. Such career reconversion requirements were unimagined in a generation span or the exact time distance between one's training and their professional maturity.

5.5.3 LEADERSHIP RESPONSES TOWARDS GROUP COHESION

Understanding the leadership response demanded crossing over from the leadership styles affirmed in a default setting to the eventual values prioritised in a crisis context. A person's background is detrimental for developing a risk-oriented or adverse leadership style, as well as a compliant, or an innovation-driven attitude through which they could later safeguard or challenge conventions. If reaching a position of authority, such aspects would determine a transformational or a transactional leader. A person's upbringing can also reveal the first settings and behaviours which they may further describe as their earliest example of leadership. As a fundamental influence within one's background, beyond direct learnings on leadership, family can be linked to receptivity or aversion to risk, discernment between short- and long-term gains, and timing and values upon which one should set one's priorities.

Participants confirmed group cohesion and a reconnection to the role and organisational identity as the key values to direct their leadership within the COVID-19 crisis. Regardless of how stable roles and work paradigms may appear, the pressure of preventing the loss of identity is notably visible in an organisation's Learning & Development strategy and more particularly in the focus

on upskilling and reskilling which highlights the necessity to update and expand one's knowledge to maintain currency in their competencies and expand them towards intersecting terrains. The loss of relevance is minded both in one's daily task, as well as outside an organisational framework. Both settings have individuals exposed to the emergence of new fields and roles which challenge one's capacity for understanding their attribution, making sense of how they could complement their own input, but also setting goals, guidelines, and even a common language with these new areas of expertise. Transformational leadership is grounded on the impact of the personal example which can only be affirmed according to provisions drawn through empathy (Benedetti, 2019). On an individual level which is further transferred in both areas of transformational leadership, maintaining relevance can be regarded as ensuring survival, thus dominating strategic thinking on decisions which target long term effects (Antoniou & Ansoff, 2004). Consequently, strategic thinking related to self-management starts with verifying the transferable skills to ensure a longer span for resource security within the continuous dilemma of how both one's skills, as well as one's role may become irrelevant.

Risk mitigation is extended further according to accountability, a variable that highlights a similar influence on that of legal requirements, imposed proportionally with authority and responsibility. Therefore, accountability is encompassed within the background of core decision making. Accountability demands that leaders communicate either the due diligence that must be advanced by members in their direct work group to their own distinctive subordinates to ensure there are no fractures in the implementation of new guidelines, but also to the intervention scheme for non-compliance on the part of other stakeholders which fall into the ambit of each member's responsibilities (suppliers or end consumers). An awareness of each member's accountability sets the premise for the authorisation of mindful actions (Denyer, 2020).

5.5.4 METHODOLOGICAL ASPECTS

The reviewed literature highlighted observation and case study as the research methods dominating most scholarly efforts. However, observation and case study have been notably approached in terms of theorising strategic leadership and not its cognitive component. While the behavioural

dimension of decision making becomes evident, the cognitive processes can only be approached through speculation, compromising accuracy.

As a tool which can be transferred into practice where it can support dedicated training programs, scenario planning is also used as a research method for investigating strategic thinking. Scenario planning highlights sufficient virtues which I could have integrated into the methodology, would I have focused on studying strategic thinking in a random context and even in a crisis, to which leaders could have become acquainted. The unique character of the COVID-19 pandemic provides a more insightful terrain than any simulation which would have been designed upon probabilistic occurrences. The direction of action for leaders had been established from beyond the institutional boundaries of the organisation. Integrating elements of scenario planning -though highly useful for verifying and validating an initial extraction of data to be analysed- would have gone against ethics, as it would have placed the interviewees in a situation of criticising the Government and public health policies.

Neuroscience provides the most exhaustive terrain for extracting a methodology, as it connects to various levels of human consciousness. However, neuroscience must be excluded for feasibility reasons, as I do not have access to specific medical equipment, not do I have the knowledge to collect and interpret the data. Nevertheless, though the present thesis is grounded on an interdisciplinary approach, neuroscience exhibits an irreconcilable distance from the scholarly areas approached in the research.

My approach was to gather as much data as possible from the participants by allowing them to share valuable information through stream of consciousness and unstructured interviewing. The study was also to be as in-depth as possible in the insights thus gained. The population of the study was senior leaders. I would attempt to approach them in a respectful way, mindful of their immense experience and skills set, and then allow them to share as much of their personal and business experience as possible. The timeframe was dependent on the constraints set by the pandemic in terms of remote working and interviewing and the demands on them of challenging projects and workload, but it was hoped to accomplish the interviews within two months and to allow as much time to each interview as possible. The number of participants was considered to be sufficient and the method of seeking participants – here, through snowballing- was also considered to be the most effective, as the leaders would recommend other leaders that they knew and who they felt would

contribute most fulsomely to the data gathering. Once such purely cognitive processes are understood, one can further deduct the structure within adaptability and the objectivity behind moral values, two key directions that define an individual's ethos and their personal perspectives on efficiency, as each of these insights could further be correlated for prioritising, scaling, and estimating the delivery of goals.

Butina (2015) proposes the use of a demographic questionnaire as a preliminary phase for proper sampling. However, since the study of strategic thinking should prioritise decision makers, descriptive and exploratory research within the retailer's organisational chart and internal regulations over tasks that complete policy implementation will fulfil this introductory stage, while providing the working variables. Sampling may be extended from the company's executive level towards any positions that are privileged with an autonomy in work. This, I felt, should be achieved through snowballing.

A real-time narration would have privileged the research through a higher degree of accuracy. Furthermore, the interviews have been collected after the public health policies have been lifted, thus the organisation had returned to its default norms. Though not necessarily significant, the time distance may affect recollection, so that a retrospective outlook could highlight a certain detachment which hinders an understanding of the exact pressure experienced across the pandemic. At the same time, detachment may also ensure objectivity and better sense-making of the crisis and the decision that had to be delivered.

5.5.5 LIMITATIONS

The limitations of the study might be said by some research to fall within the area of remote data gathering where the face-to-face interaction of normal interaction is lacking, and that conversations may be limited by physical factors such as surroundings. Another limitation might be seen as the lack of structure within the interviewing process, but I have gone out of my way to establish the importance of the data to be gathered by such a method and its application in the business sphere. Thus, the scope of the study is considered to be a good measure of the aims and objectives and is designed to provide achievable outcomes. When a study covers new ground there is an element of

importance to it. When it also offers further practical application, the importance is heightened. I envisioned a resultant tool for practitioners in the workplace to be used as a training tool in the form of a guide and a course. This would have future significance and help leaders in waiting, especially, to develop strategic thinking skills which are so crucial to a business, and even more so in the throes of global disruption.

In conjunction with observation, active interviewing that reached decisions in real time would have a salutary approach to understanding strategic thinking from a self-critical perspective. Combined with storytelling, active interviewing would have provided a contrast between self-positioning towards an action one is about to get engaged in and the detached impression one holds as soon as outcomes arise. Active interviewing would have ensured analytic self-efficacy. Such a comparative overview remains one of the limits of the present research, as argued by the insightful perspective it may launch, without affecting accuracy.

5.5.6 FINAL REMARKS ON THE PERSONAL IMPLICATION IN DATA ANALYSIS

A self-assessment of one's cognitive and personality style is imposed as an additional verification tool that allows for reduction of the risk of bias within data interpretation. I have therefore focussed on an objective interpretation of narrative facts in the limits to which they have been presented to me, refraining from intuiting, and speculating. Though the inductive analysis grants the researcher full freedom in interpretation, I reject intuition as a potential filter for judgement out of both academic ethics, as well as out of a scholarly aspiration towards reaching the highest degree of accuracy allowed by the used methodology. As a former member of the studied organisation where I have gathered 4 years of experience within roles connected to the supply chain management, no issues which raise the question of unfamiliarity for me as a researcher have been identified in the primary data collection.

5.6 Self-reflection

It is generally accepted that the interview technique is an important method of garnering information and collecting data for specific purposes (Jacob & Furgerson, 2012). The approach that the interviewer takes can ensure that the relevant data is made available, if protocols are put in place and that there is a measure of planning and preparation, and an appropriate interview style is chosen. Amid the more formal planning, it is wise to be cognisant of the dynamic nature of human interaction, which makes for a flexible and creative and open-ended opportunity. When selecting the method of data collection for my thesis, I was drawn to the more informal interview technique, including the life story and career path framework, as I was sure that the respondents would provide valuable information, even unintentional personal insights during our informal interviews.

The fact that I was also a fellow colleague at the retailer would create a more relaxed atmosphere and be conducive to asking questions that perhaps would not have been possible or plausible in a different circumstance: at the same time, I was aware of the risks of non-engagement by respondents who might be wary of revealing too much or being suspicious of my intentions (McDermid et al, 2014). At the same time, I wanted to use a life story chronology to I also chose a novel method of respondent selection, that of snowballing to achieve my aim of having a broad cross-section of leaders' input on and experience of strategic thinking. Self-reflection is integral to every aspect of the interview process, from start to finish, and is an informative and important marker for the perceived as well as achieved result (Kirpitchenko and Voloder, 2014).

In the initial or more formal planning stage, I produced four documents for the interviewees. The interview sheet introduced me, and my academic interests as focused on leadership, strategic thinking and building organisational resilience during disruptive times (very pertinent at the height of the Covid-19 pandemic where the retailer was in largely uncharted waters) and I was intrigued as to whether the leaders had used previous experience to make strategic decisions, or whether they used innovation and out of the box thinking. I informed each interviewee that it would be an "unstructured life story interview", making it clear that it was anonymous and that they could stop the interview at any time. The other documents (Appendix 1- 4) were also designed to reassure them, outlining the broad interview picks-up, and I felt that this would encourage their participation and set them at ease and would be ethically sound.

As far as interview mechanisms and time frames were concerned, the context of the disruption caused by the Covid-19 pandemic determined the parameters of the interview locations and time constraints. All the meetings were held on Microsoft Teams, except one, which was held on Zoom. My choice of snowballing technique was another factor that influenced the interviewing process; this also caused me pressure as the pace was slower, and once again, the pandemic dictated the pace and efficiency of the methods. My concern was that the snowballing method of participant selection was going to delay my thesis submission and that the remote form of storytelling interview situation would not help me build a rapport with the interviewees and thus my objectives would be compromised.

With my first interview, I was nervous because I was unsure of what would transpire, and whether my envisaged expectations would be actualised (Aburn et al, 2021). However, I was relieved and pleased and emotionally touched by the personal story that was shared with me. I felt very connected to my participant and felt empathy with his efforts to achieve more and he had had tough life moments. I felt strong emotions, and this is true of all the participants. The results of the unstructured interviews were beyond my wishes and expectations. The fact that we were talking virtually did not seem to create the distance that I had feared might happen. In fact, I found that the enforced isolation which had occurred during the pandemic made people more willing to reach out when interaction was available. The unstructured format also led to much more openness and personal disclosure, and most participants seemed to enjoy the free flow of discussion. I also shared some of my own life story in these interviews as well, and the shared reality of a lockdown existence where pets or children made noises in the background gave common ground to the interactions.

By the second interview, I was relieved and a lot more relaxed. Things seemed to be working in the way that I had aimed. I felt more confident to approach the subjects, and I listened more actively, not fearing that they might stop the discussion, waiting for me to ask more questions. There were some respondents who were slightly less forthcoming, but by this time I was confident in my ability to ask questions and keep the conversation going. I had learnt that each one had something of value to tell me and to add to my topic. I found that each respondent used a career timeline which blended with their personal journeys. In the process, I was able to extract information about their mindset, and about strategic thinking as a topic. The novelty and beauty

of my research, I felt, was that in subtle ways, the topic of strategic thinking was addressed, albeit not always overtly or in a forced and formal manner. The loose brief that I had provided had been a catalyst for expanded thinking and the interviewees had in their own way run with the topic and instinctively fulfilled the brief themselves with minimal intervention from myself. (Webster-Deakin, 2021).

A positive and rewarding aspect of the interview process was the fact that all the participants were honoured to be interviewed by me: I had the impression that some were proud of me, some were admiring of me and my research and of my workload juggling and being a mum at the same time, and others were encouraging and supporting and happy to share their lives and work with me, and they encouraged me in my studies and life.

A further and moving context was the fact that some of the respondents were under the cloud of redundancy and were emotional and this was a chance for them to relive important moments at the retailer. Altogether, it was a mixed bag of emotions, and all our stories were woven into one in this whole process. On reflection, it became a complex tapestry of life, of which strategic thinking was the underlying theme.

Interviewing in contemporary business settings invariably takes place in an atmosphere filled with urgency therefore nonguided interview approaches find little application in the normal course of events (Jacob & Furgerson, 2012). However, the luxury of a more relaxed and less time constrained milieu gave the interviews depth and breadth: the context of Covid-19 also assisted in making the respondents more available while at the same time making face to face interviews impossible.

An observation that I made and which I feel I instinctively and successfully responded to be the fact that I realised that the interview process involves the whole being- the emotional, thought processes and behaviour. I was willing and able to engage on all these levels with the interviewees and found that the majority responded in kind. Building rapport was very rewarding. In this regard, I consciously used the technique of active listening, which entails involvement with the subject and the respondents, patience, searching for meaning and understanding, and evaluation (Jacob & Furgerson, 2012). It becomes a symbiotic process. I also experienced the gamut of emotions and I felt motivated to become like some of my colleagues and to learn some of their skills. They also helped me to overcome my own fears about public

speaking and interaction- the interview process for this research helped me greatly to develop my own skills and motivation. Instead of being drained, I felt more energetic and alive., especially in the strained and unknown territory of Covid-19.

Through this process, I was so impressed by the strong women I encountered – I so admired their skills, their commitment to work and family life, and could share my experiences with them. I feel too that they felt safe with my approach. I was able to read their body language, their facial expressions, the emotion in their voice and respond accordingly. I felt proud that I was able to build such good rapport with the respondents through a sincere and empathetic manner.

Because they understood the purpose of my thesis, they appeared to be willing to share their experiences, the lessons learnt, career milestones, to contribute for others who might read the thesis, who want to improve their leadership skills and style and to make a difference in their working environments. They were aware that it was a document which would be published (Coghlan et al, 2014, Karsten, 2020).

All the respondents 'stories made me reflect on my journey within the company. I had been with the company since 2016. In that time, I went from shop floor assistant to an operations manager in the retailer's headquarters. I found my journey reflected in those of the interviewees in terms of common ground: each one had started on lower rungs and progressed in time. We had all built loyalty to the company, I considered my workmates my second family and many of the participants had similar stories, such as the one who had to deal with an emergency after hours, and whose manager sent his family a card thanking them for letting him do what he did in the line of duty. This evidenced a level of trust and camaraderie which brought out the best in all concerned. Another of the respondents, who had heard that he was shortly being made redundant said that the retailer was written all over him and that he would never be able to work for another large company. His whole life had been in the company. He had tears in his eyes, and I was very moved by that and amazed by the depth of commitment to and feeling for the company that he had. He had been so loyal that it had been like a marriage to him. In many ways I felt the same loyalty and even now there is a wrench when I think about my time there.

A couple of months after this interview, I found myself in a similar position, finding out that I was going to be made redundant soon. When the announcement was made, I had one or two more interviews to complete. I felt immensely sad that both my research and my role in the

company was coming to an end. It made the research terrain doubly poignant, as I was even more inextricably linked with my respondents than I had initially thought and imagined. This self- reflection note is, to my mind, a letter to my reader, because I want to connect with my reader in the same way that I connected with my respondents, and I would like them to feel empathy for the journey that I have undertaken in my research – a journey which has also run parallel to the journey of my life outside of work. The topic of the thesis is strategic thinking in leaders. My experience has been that this topic has revealed itself as far more multi-faceted than I could ever have imagined. It has encapsulated whole lives and shared realities, heartache, joy, ambition, triumph, and disaster, all set on the stage of an unexpected and unfathomable global pandemic.

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Appendix 1 Interview Sheet

PARTICIPANT NAME:

INTERVIEW SHEET – DOCTORAL RESEARCH STRATEGIC THINKING DURING DISRUPTIVE TIMES

INTRODUCTION:

I am Corina Musetescu, a third-year doctoral researcher at the University of the West of Scotland in London, School of Business and Enterprises and Operations Manager at Sainsbury's. My academic interests are focused on leadership, strategic thinking and building organisational resilience during disruptive times.

The project addresses the strategic thinking leaders who play an active role in building organisational resilience during disruptive times and it would be very interesting to understand how your work impacted the organisation during these challenging times. I would also like to know more about your career journey, what or who inspired you along the way, the lessons you learned and the milestones you achieved and are proud about. This is an unstructured life story interview.

As I specifically mentioned in the consent form you can decline any questions/topics or stop the interview at any point. Also, I would like to check with you if you are happy for me to record the interview. The data will be available at the University of the West of Scotland in London.

Broad research picks - up:

1. Career journey: life story telling.
2. Strategic thinking: what or who influenced or inspired along your journey?
3. Leadership: decision making, influencing.
4. Organisational resilience: building organisational resilience during global disruption.
5. Transformation/change during challenging times.
6. Covid-19 Pandemic context: impact on the ways of working, personal/professional development, organisational survival.

Appendix 2 Participant Sheet

STRATEGIC THINKING PARTICIPANT INFORMATION SHEET

You are being invited to take part in research on STRATEGIC THINKING. Corina Musetescu, RESEARCHER at University of the West of Scotland is leading this research. Before you decide to take part, it is important you understand why the research is being conducted and what it will involve. Please take time to read the following information carefully.

What is the purpose of the study?

Strategic thinking leaders are to be proved as effective in building organisational resilience during global disruption. The aim of this doctoral thesis is to answer the following question: How Can Strategic Thinking Leaders Build Organisational Resilience During Global Disruption? On a more specific note, this research explores the topic of strategic thinking leadership in the context of Covid-19 Pandemic as a trigger for building organisational resilience.

Why have I been chosen to take part?

You are invited to participate in this study because you have been nominated by another participant and considered to be a strategic thinking leader.

What are the benefits of taking part?

By sharing your experiences with us, you will be helping CORINA MUSETESCU and University of the West of Scotland to better understand the STRATEGIC THINKING during disruptive times.

Are there any risks associated with taking part?

This study has been reviewed and approved through University of the West of Scotland formal research ethics procedure. There are no significant risks associated with participation.

Do I have to take part?

No – it is entirely up to you. If you do decide to take part, please keep this Information Sheet and complete the Informed Consent Form to show that you understand your rights in relation to the research, and that you are happy to participate. Please note down your participant number (which is on the Consent Form) and provide this to the lead researcher if you seek to withdraw from the study later. You are free to withdraw your information from the project until it is not more possible/practical.

You should note that your data may be used in the production of formal research outputs (e.g., journal articles, conference papers, theses, and reports) prior to this date and so you are advised to contact the university at the earliest opportunity should you wish to withdraw from the study. To withdraw, please contact the lead researcher on

[REDACTED] Please also contact the Research Support Office on [REDACTED] request can be dealt with promptly in the event of the lead researcher's absence. You do not need to give a reason. A decision to withdraw, or not to take part, will not affect you in any way.

What will happen if I decide to take part?

You will be asked several questions regarding strategic thinking, your role in the company and any major decisions made during COVID-19 pandemic. The interview will take place in a safe environment at a time that is convenient to you. Ideally, we would like to audio record your responses (and will require your consent for this), so the location should be in a fairly quiet area. The interview should take around 60 minutes to complete.

Data Protection and Confidentiality

Your data will be processed in accordance with the General Data Protection Regulation 2016 (GDPR) and the Data Protection Act 2018. All information collected about you will be kept strictly confidential. Unless they are fully anonymised in our records, your data will be referred to by a unique participant number rather than by name. **If you consent to being audio recorded, all recordings will be destroyed once they have been transcribed.** Your data will only be viewed by the researcher/research team. All electronic data will be stored on a password-protected computer file in the researcher's personal computer. Your consent information will be kept separately from your responses to minimise risk in the event of a data breach. The lead researcher will take responsibility for data destruction and all collected data will be destroyed on or before 1st June 2021.

Data Protection Rights

University of the West of Scotland is a Data Controller for the information you provide. You have the right to access information held about you. Your right of access can be exercised in accordance with the General Data Protection Regulation and the Data Protection Act 2018. You also have other rights including rights of correction, erasure, objection, and data portability. For more details, including the right to lodge a complaint with the Information Commissioner's Office, please visit [\[redacted\]](#) [questions](#), [comments](#) and requests about your personal data can also be sent to the University Data Protection Officer [\[redacted\]](#)

What will happen with the results of this study?

The results of this study may be summarised in published articles, [reports](#) and presentations. Quotes or key findings will always be made anonymous in any formal outputs unless we have your prior and explicit written permission to attribute them to you by name.

Making a Complaint

If you are unhappy with any aspect of this research, please first contact the lead researcher, Corina Musetescu at [\[redacted\]](#). If you still have concerns and wish to make a formal complaint, please write to Dr. Daniel Turner at [\[redacted\]](#)

Corina Musetescu
DBA Researcher
University of the West of Scotland
[\[redacted\]](#)

In your letter, please provide information about the research project, specify the name of the [researcher](#) and detail the nature of your complaint.

Appendix 3 Informed Consent

Participant No. 2

INFORMED CONSENT FORM: STRATEGIC THINKING

You are invited to take part in this research study for the purpose of collecting data on STRATEGIC THINKING.

Before you decide to take part, you must **read the accompanying Participant Information Sheet.**

Please do not hesitate to ask questions if anything is unclear or if you would like more information about any aspect of this research. It is important that you feel able to take the necessary time to decide whether or not you wish to take part.

If you are happy to participate, please confirm your consent by circling YES against each of the below statements and then signing and dating the form as participant.

1	I confirm that I have read and understood the <u>Participant Information Sheet</u> for the above study and have had the opportunity to ask questions	YES	NO
2	I understand my participation is voluntary and that I am free to withdraw my data, without giving a reason, by contacting the lead researcher and the Research Support Office <u>at any time</u> until the date specified in the Participant Information Sheet	YES	NO
3	I have noted down my participant number (top left of this Consent Form) which may be required by the lead researcher if I wish to withdraw from the study	YES	NO
4	I understand that all the information I provide will be held securely and treated confidentially	YES	NO
5	I am happy for the information I provide to be used (anonymously) in academic papers and other formal research outputs	YES	NO
6	I am happy for the interview to be <u>audio recorded</u>	YES	NO
7	I agree to take part in the above study	YES	NO

Thank you for your participation in this study. Your help is very much appreciated.

Participant's Name	Date	Signature
Researcher	Date	Signature
Corina Musetescu		

Appendix 4 Debrief Sheet

Debrief Sheet

Thank you for taking part in the study – your time is much appreciated.

The current study aims to make a contribution to the researchers' community by bringing a fresh perspective on a traditional concept, **strategic thinking**. Using interviews, the [results](#) from the current study aims to bridge the gap of knowledge with respect to key questions such as *how can strategic thinking leaders build organisational resilience during global disruption and how their personal/professional experiences have influenced their strategic thinking*.

If you have questions or would like to know more about the current research, you should email the researcher Corina Musetescu at [REDACTED] if you ever wish to withdraw your data from the study, you need to email this address with your participant ID until it is no more possible/practical. You do not need to state a reason and there will be no repercussions. If you have any complaints regarding your experience of participating in this study, you may contact Dr. Daniel Turner (Ethics Board Chair) on [REDACTED]

For more information regarding the existing literature, the following references may be of interest:

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